

***Critical Evaluation of the Decline
in the Textile Industry in Pakistan
and Recovery Proposals***

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**A thesis submitted to the University of The West of Scotland, UK, in
accordance with the requirements of the degree of DBA in the Business
School**

2021

Abstract

Purpose

The existing literature could not offer the causes of financial crises in the textile sector as well as what are the causes of the overall decline of the textile sector of Pakistan. This research aims to present recommendations toward a national policy that best suits the specific development needs of the struggling textile industry in Pakistan, which will significantly contribute to economic growth, export increase, and a better life for a large demographic group in Pakistan represented in the textile work force.

Method

The study had gathered responses from textile owners, senior management, and other stakeholders using the semi-structured interview method.

Results

Findings of this study reveal that the political government negligence, devaluation of the currency, low loans and borrowing opportunities for SMEs, high-interest rates, low focus to publish online financial reports, energy crises, weak law and order situation, obsolete technology and lack of human capital are some of the major challenges which negatively impacted the textile growth. As a result, the textile sector lost attraction and growth from both the national and international markets. Therefore, It is recommended that the textile sector and government officials must collaborate with the purpose to bring these advanced technologies such as industry 4 practices, e-procurement, brick and click, online banking system, laser printing, digital printing, and 3D Printers.

Implication

The textile sector owners and government must invest money in cheap energy sources, the development of ICT infrastructure, and loans for small units. The

government of Pakistan must invest money in developing ICT infrastructure especially in SMEs which are unable to create big changes due to limited employees, vision and mission, and capital. By adopting an e-commerce model such as brick and click, the textile sector can create online information as well as take orders online without wasting time in meetings and handling the customers physically.

Acknowledgement

As much as I was self-motivated in undertaking this postgraduate degree program, I was also encouraged and supported by many people such as my friends and family. I am fortunate to have had the moral support of many loved ones whilst completing this project. I am grateful to Dr. Eugene Kozlovski for his valuable guidance regarding my research. He gave me valuable inputs and constantly encouraged me to undertake the research program. Their unconditional support enabled me to research the right direction. If Dr. Eugene had not provided me with their valuable guidance, I would not have been able to conduct the research properly and thoroughly. Their constructive feedback enabled me to improve myself and the direction of my research. I am extremely grateful to him for taking a timeout for me and his providing me with constructive feedback and answering the questions which confused me while I was conducting my research. I am also grateful to him for the academic support he provided and for ensuring that the best resources were at my disposal for conducting the research.

Above all, I am forever indebted to my parents for their moral, financial, emotional, and intellectual support throughout my academic career including the doctoral program. My wife and my children were a constant support and brought me back to life when I used to feel lost in research. Their love brought me back to life after being tired and exhausted from working for long hours. Lastly, I am grateful to my wife for their immeasurable support and their patience during the production of this thesis; without them, none of this would have been done.

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CHAPTER 1: RESEARCH INTRODUCTION

The textile industry constitutes a pivotal part of the economic and social life in Pakistan. Beyond the sectoral level, the textile profession has important influences on the national economy and exports as well as social and farming life in Pakistan [CITATION Mem16 \l 2057]. The sector's implications extend out of the limits of Pakistan being a prominent global supplier of textile and prime importer of textile machinery [CITATION Yar10 \l 2057]. Historically, cotton has been the top strategic agricultural product of Pakistan providing a source of living for a large group of farmers and ranking the country as the fourth cotton producer and third cotton consumer worldwide [CITATION Law15 \l 2057]. The sector is the major buyer of the country's over-five-billion-dollar cotton production and the largest supporter of exports with over 60% of national export returns generated from textile [CITATION Gov17 \l 2057]. The industry amounts to around half of the manufacturing power in Pakistan. It employs circa 40% of the country's manufacturing labor power with over 10% contribution to the national GDP and a similar contribution to global textile supply. Eventually, it is the 10th international producer of textiles [CITATION Tex15 \l 2057].

As the largest manufacturing sector in Pakistan, the textile industry is by far a main foundation pillar in the Pakistani economic structure [CITATION Cae08 \l 2057]. It has ranked the country among the top Asian and global producers and exporters of textile items with circa 10% contribution to the national gross domestic production (GDP) [CITATION Law15 \l 2057]. With an enormous labor force that includes almost half of the country's working power, over 2000 large medium and small

manufacturing units make the Pakistani textile industry one of the largest in Asia and the tenth producer of textile in the world with a significant share it should not be a generic flow which is the art of the world's spinning capacity that exceeds 5% [CITATION Daw17 \l 2057]. The industry leverages the country's largest agricultural produce, cotton, to contribute to around two-thirds of the country's much-needed export revenue [CITATION Hus17 \l 2057]. Altogether, these factors established the textile industry as the most strategic segment of the economy in Pakistan in terms of earning and employment opportunities [CITATION Spi17 \l 2057].

1.1 RESEARCH BACKGROUND

Although once with incredible proliferation that increased the number of textile plants from a few to several hundred and spinning wheels from under two hundred thousand to more than eight million over the second half of the past century, the industry has significantly declined over the last decade [CITATION Mon12 \l 2057]. Pakistan's share of the international textile market shrank significantly [CITATION Sha14 \l 2057]. The decline was mediated by a range of causes with regional competition from neighbouring countries including India and Bangladesh who have been able to significantly uplift their global market share being on top of the list [CITATION Ahm16 \l 2057]. Nevertheless, the country's power shortage crisis together with the increased cost of production creates added burdens to the muddled industry [CITATION Man16 \l 2057]. Research and development efforts are badly needed to support the industry's global stance [CITATION Sha14 \l 2057]. Yet, little effort has been made both country and industry-wise. To add salt to the injury, the perceived deficient labor system and management practices in the sector have discouraged several workers and rendered the industry further troubled [CITATION Hus17 \l 2057]. The dramatic situation prompted top-level government intervention at multiple levels with strategic plans aimed at tackling the problem. Earlier in the century, in its "Textile Vision 2007", the government allocated a budget of over \$3 billion aimed at increasing exports and enhancing Pakistan's global position as a leading exporter of textiles [CITATION Fib17 \l 2057]. In 2013, the Pakistani government entered "an International Monetary Fund program" with support to the textile industry on the top of its priority list [CITATION Man16 \l 2057]. The "textiles

policy 2014-19” drawn by the Ministry of Textile Industry (2015) provides a new government vision to improve the industry over the stated period. A recent government intervention aimed at reviving the declining industry saw zero-tax on textile export tax and reduction of import tax on some of the industries' requirements in mid-2016 [CITATION The16 \l 2057]. Yet, all these efforts have not so far proved successful in getting the industry back on track.

The sector had its golden era over the last 50 years of the past century that witnessed a tremendous upturn in the number of manufacturing bases from a handful to over 600 [CITATION Ahm10 \l 2057]. This was associated with a more impressive proliferation of spinning machines from about 180 thousand to over eight million [CITATION Rav15 \l 2057]. The enormous sector encompasses several textile industries including yarns, textile materials, and garments [CITATION Tex15 \l 2057]. About a billion US dollars' worth of textile machinery imports makes the Pakistani textile sector a key player on the global textile machinery stage [CITATION Yar10 \l 2057]. Nationally, the textile production value chain has a great impact on the overall economic and social life in Pakistan. It starts with over ten million farmers solely relying on the cotton crop to live and provide for their families [CITATION Gov17 \l 2057]. Furthermore, it affects the enormous workforce that adds value to the raw cotton turning it into yarns and fibers and consequently textile and garments [CITATION Tex15 \l 2057]. However, the chain's implications extend further to affect businesses and exports with notable global impact [CITATION Kir14 \l 2057]. Figure 1-1 is presented with the purpose to draw a comparison between Pakistan and Bangladesh regarding minimum wages in the textile industry. The purpose of this chart is to show how the challenges of the textile industry have negatively influenced the labor wages and decreased their standard of living during the inflation period in Pakistan where the prices of everything are increased due to external debt and depreciation of the currency.

Minimum Monthly Wages in US\$ Market Exchange Rate

Figure 1.1 minimum monthly labour wages comparison (Source: Haq, 2019)

Nonetheless, the once-thriving industry has come to a recession. Since the last decade, the textile industry in Pakistan started an incessant decline that eliminated over 30% of its production capacity [CITATION Rav15 \l 2057]. 2016 saw a harsh drop of about 8% in textile exports against figures from a previous year that in turn did not match figures from years before [CITATION The17 \l 2057]. Many international buyers have shifted to other competitors such as Vietnam and Bangladesh to source their textile imports [CITATION Mem16 \l 2057]. The deteriorating situation had a catastrophic impact on the economy with hundreds of manufacturing outlets have completely closed leaving over half a million workers jobless over the past two years [CITATION Man16 \l 2057]. Ramifications of the slump have rendered over 60% of textile exporters in Pakistan unable to carry on their operations over the past five years [CITATION Man16 \l 2057].

There is a perceived correlation between the textile industry downturn and several factors. On top of these is Pakistan's power supply crisis that has led to long hours

of electricity cuts forcing many small and medium-sized plants to close [CITATION Jam151 \l 2057]. Large survivors who could invest in alternative energy solutions ended up paying extra expenses that impacted the already descending global competitiveness of the industry [CITATION Daw17 \l 2057]. The textile industry slack can also be explained in terms of the increased production cost mediated by uncompetitive taxation together with difficulties associated with securing investment financing, just to add to the cost of alternative power solutions, which has discouraged new investments in the sector [CITATION Bus16 \l 2057]. Figure 1-2 is presented with the purpose to show how much the Pakistani government has taken external debt with the purpose to stable the crises of electricity, gas, and development of the textile and agriculture sector. However, the interest rates on external debts have depreciated currency and ultimately increased the prices of machinery imports. As a result, it has become one of the main reasons to bring a decline in the growth of textile and other sectors.

Figure 1.2 external debt situaton rises for Pakistan (Source: ministry of fnance 1947-2018)

Additionally, the increasing employee turnover in the Pakistan textile industry over recent years can be viewed as the inhibitors of the industry recovery [CITATION Ahm16 \l 2057]. This has been reflected in a lack of skills and innovation in addition to the extra cost needed for new recruitments, overtime, and training [CITATION Nas16 \l 2057]. The labor issue can be examined in terms of the perceived insufficient labor protection regulations combined with myriad examples of unfair management conducts [CITATION Hus17 \l 2057]. All this just adds to the major

challenge of increasing regional and global competition in the industry [CITATION Spi17 \l 2057].

These features combined have significantly impacted the Pakistani textile industry making production sustainability unattainable. As a result, tens of manufacturing units have been forced to close and export orders have been turned away leading to wavering standing for the industry on the global stage [CITATION Spi17 \l 2057]. This scrambling situation of the textile industry in Pakistan and its enormous implications on the economy and social life in the country together with the notable lack of research in this critical economic area stems the necessity of academic and practical research to identify causes of the Pakistani textile industry's decline and suggest viable solutions in support of economic growth and wellbeing in Pakistan.

1.2 RESEARCH GAP AND RATIONALE FOR THE PROPOSED PROJECT

Afzal (2012) conducted a study concerning analyzing how electricity and interest rates increased the cost of production of the textile sector and made it less profitable and attractive for investors. Similarly, another study has investigated the impact of energy crises on the textile sector using the ratio analysis method (Shah et al. 2013). According to Khattak et al. (2011), the challenges of SMEs are different from textile mills because they have limited capital, human capital, as well as technology. Although the study of Afzal (2012) and Shah et al. (2013) provided useful findings many internal and external factors are important to understand. We cannot say that only electricity crises and interest rate is fully responsible for the decline of the textile industry. For example, there is much evidence are available that external debts have been decreased the Pakistani currency value as well as increased the prices or inflation for machinery imports in the textile sector of Pakistan (Haq, 2019). Abbas et al. (2012) have conducted a study on the Pakistani textile sector to investigate how financial crises impacted the textile sector. Their study could not offer the causes of financial crises in the textile sector as well as what are the causes of the overall decline of the textile sector of Pakistan. They have used ratio analysis to measure the financial crises which could not cover all the challenges of the textile sector in Pakistan.

Although there is scant recent literature is available with respect to decline causes of textile sector in Pakistan. However, it is important to analyse the findings of all

previous relevant studies with the purpose to find potential research gaps and future directions for current study. Abbas et al. (2012) have conducted study on Pakistani textile sector with respect to investigate how financial crises impacted on textile sector. Their study could not offer the causes of financial crises in textile sector as well as what are the causes in overall decline of textile sector of Pakistan. They have used ratio analysis to measure the financial crises which could not cover all the challenges of textile sector in Pakistan. Afzal (2012) conducted study with respect to analyse how electricity and interest rate increased the cost of production of textile sector and made it less profitable and attractive for investors. Although the study of Afzal (2012) and Shah et al. (2013) provided useful findings but there are many internal and external factors which are important to understand. We cannot say that only electricity crises and interest rate is fully responsible for the decline of textile industry. For example, there are many evidence are available that external debts have been decreased the Pakistani currency value as well as increased the prices or inflation for machinery imports in textile sector of Pakistan (Haq, 2019). Therefore, it has become important to thoroughly explore and understand all the internal and external factors which negatively influence the overall growth of textile sector. Based on these research gaps, this study intends to critical evaluation of the decline in the textile industry in Pakistan and recovery proposals.

This research aims to present recommendations toward a national policy that best suits the specific development needs of the struggling textile industry in Pakistan, which will significantly contribute to economic growth, export increase, and a better life for a large demographic group in Pakistan represented in the textile work force. In the attainment of this goal, the evolution of the textile industry in Pakistan will be discussed. The current position of the industry will be critically appraised and reasons for degradation will be identified and analyzed. The industry will be benchmarked against similar regional and global industries. Based on the academic and professional assessment of causes of retrogression, specific recommendations will be made for enhanced textile operations in Pakistan for good of the economy and public welfare. The research bridges a gap in the professional development researching in the Pakistani textile sector that has not been taken as seriously as needed both at the economy and industry levels. Understanding the challenges and presenting the recommendation about national policy toward the textile sector can

contribute to the knowledge in the existing literature of the textile sector regarding how the potential challenges of a developing country can be addressed. The researcher is motivated to contribute practical knowledge by uncovering rich insights regarding the decline of the textile industry and how the industry can revive and contribute to the economy of Pakistan.

1.3. RESEARCH AIMS, QUESTIONS AND OBJECTIVES

This study intends to critical evaluation of the decline in the textile industry in Pakistan and recovery proposals. To achieve this goal, the following questions need to be answered:

- What are the causes of the decline in the Pakistan textile industry?
- How competitive is this industry? And
- What can be done to revive the industry and increase its global competitiveness?

Answering these questions, it's necessary to achieve the following objectives:

- Discuss the evolution of the textile industry in Pakistan;
- Assess the current position of the textile industry in Pakistan;
- Analyze causes of the decline in the textile industry in Pakistan;
- Benchmark the industry against its regional and global counterparts; and
- Develop policies to improve the textile industry in Pakistan.

Table 1.1 Overview of research methodology

Research paradigm and approach	The research approach is interpretivism which believes that there are multiple realities therefore it is important to understand these subjective realities using the social constructivism approach.
Research Problem	This study is exploratory because it intends to understand the causes of the decline in the Pakistan textile industry and aims to offer a practical recommendation.
Time horizon	The data is collected once only the stakeholders of the textile sector therefore it is a cross-section study.
Manipulation of context	There is no manipulation of context. The purpose of this

study is to understand the cultural, social, and local context which may impact the decline of the textile industry in Pakistan.

Researcher involvement

The researcher is involved in a thought-out study with the purpose to understand causes of decline and interpret the themes, sub-themes, and keywords in a precise way during reporting of findings section.

Data collection and analysis

The study collected data using a semi-structured interview method while data analysis has been done using thematic analysis.

Ethical consideration

The ethical considerations are strictly followed concerning protect the anonymity of respondents during data reporting of data in the findings section.

1.4. THESIS OUTLINE

In the first chapter, the current study has thoroughly discussed the importance of the textile industry all over the world and specifically in the local context of Pakistan. The research background has presented some statistics with the purpose to show the importance of the textile sector for the Pakistani economy. Afterward, the study has discussed the research gap as well as presented the motivation of the researcher to fill that gap and contributed to knowledge. Finally, the study has a research aim, questions, and objectives for this study. In the second chapter, the current study has discussed the recent trends in textile, evidence, and theory on textile growth, industrial policy indicators, decline, and rise in industrial policy related to the textile sector. Overall, this section identifies the major drawbacks of industrial policy, government capacity, and productivity policies. Afterward, this study has discussed the research gap and construct a theoretical framework for this study. In the third chapter, the study has discussed research philosophy, approach, design, data collection, sampling, population, analysis, and ethical considerations. In the fourth chapter, the current study has constructed various major themes, coding, and an extensive list of common keywords with the purpose to interpret the findings sector. In the fifth chapter, the present study has elaborated the objectives of this study with the research data of findings, and it is also compared with the existing literature.

Finally. The last chapter has discussed the conclusion and practical recommendations for this study.

CHAPTER 2: LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 INTRODUCTION

The free markets have capacity to self-organize and efficiently work and they identified market liberalization, competition, openness, and deregulation as key components of economic growth. Moreover, policies related to specific industries or sectors generally criticise for inducing the organizations to lower the investment and lose the competitive drive (Griffin, 2013). Moreover, Barker, (2017) argued that policies supporting industry or sectors have emerged in developed economies. At odds with conventional notion, Stalling, & Peres, (2009) argued that the countries of Latin America have implemented a combination of industrial-oriented policies and outward-oriented policy approach. The researcher is exploring that how Pakistan government can grab maximum benefits from active participation in market intervention? How much industrial policies are aimed to support existing industrial completeness, organization and customer protection and market competition? Does economic growth effectively trigger by such policies? The literature is reviewed to get in-depth understanding of wider selection of industrial policies that would lead to in depth understanding about the industrial policies development issues and development factors for required outcomes from industrial policies.

2.2 SOME LATEST TRENDS IN THE INDUSTRIAL POLICY

The technology and innovation, skills formation and education, trade, competitiveness, competition regulation and support measures of targeted industry (Vries, 2008). Rodrik and Subramanian (2005) differentiated “pro-business policy” – a policy that targets business development – from “pro-market policy” – a policy that targets free market development. They refer “pro-business policy” to the policies that “aimed primarily at benefiting incumbents in the formal industrial commercial sector” and refer “pro-market policies” to policies that “aimed at stimulating competition and benefit new entrants and consumers” (Rodrik and Subramanian 2005, pp. 215). They reported that in 1980s the high level of Indian economic growth was not triggered by pro-market policies but by pro-business policies. According to Khan and Blankenburg (2009) and Acemoglu, & Angrist., (2010), the countries that are at early stage of development should develop the industrial policy with focus on to support industrial development but at latter stages their industrial policies should trigger the

competition. The next section is on analysis based on Rodrik and Subramanian's (2005) policy classification because it permits to make 'de-facto' difference between the policies instead of 'de-jure' difference. Moreover, differentiation between pro-business and pro-market policy is same as differentiation between structural and market-oriented policy (Corrocher, et al., 2018; Bianchi, & Labory, 2019). However, former focus on industrial policy while latter focus on other policy domains.

"Industrial policy is open to corruption and rent-seeking. Any system of incentives designed to help private investors venture into new activities can end up serving as a mechanism of rent transfer to unscrupulous businessman and self-interested bureaucrats" (Rodrik et al. 2004, pp. 17). According to North et al., (2009), elite tend to distribute rents to sustain political stability that ultimately leads to elite prosperity. Pro-business and pro-market policy can be best possible sources of the rent distribution. If anti-competition policy does not exist it indicates that the economic elites must bear pressure to maintain industry dominance (Park, 2018). Moreover, political support of private sector can be gained through pro-business policy (Rodrik and Subramanian [2005](#)). In other pole, privatization and market liberalization have re-distributed huge number of rents to economic elites in context of the market development (Lele, & Goswami, 2017).

As industrial policy proves highly rewarding to some firms and individuals due to creating more rent-seeking opportunities therefore it is strongly contest (Pack and Saggi [2006](#)). Majority of economists believe that through "picking winners" the policies could be refined. Some economists argue that markets are self-regulatory and there is no need for industrial policy particularly in developed countries where such policies should not exist (Bruland, & Smith, 2013; Wade, 2016). For example, a little space has been left for a liberal agenda of industrial policy after neoliberal application of Washington consensus (Rodrik et al., 2004). Due to such controversy on industrial policy, governments tend to implement policy mix with major focus on those policies supporting a specific industry or sector. As "industrial policy" is a controversial term therefore it has been altogether replaced with a less controversial and new term "competitiveness policy" (Mathews, et al., 2010). However, industrial policy is subjected to many reforms those include labour (Dickinson, 2018), legal (Wang, et al., 2014), infrastructure (Min, et al., 2019), education (Avis, 2018), skills

(Antoniuk et al., 2017), taxes (Pearson, & Foxon, 2012), innovation and technology (Rodrik et al., 2004), international relations, SME loans and skills development (LI Guoping et al., 2017; Barca, 2011). The figure 2-1 is showed the important policies elements of industrial policy which can undermine the positively or negatively influence the effectiveness of industrial sector therefore it is important to understand these elements.

Figure 2.3 Industrial policies elements (source: Avis, 2018; Antoniuk et al., 2017; Pearson, & Foxon, 2012; Rodrik et al., 2004; LI Guoping et al., 2017; Barca, 2011).

Almost all developed countries have initially used infant-industry policy to catch-up industrial development (Mathews, et al., 2010). After II World War, many developed countries used interventionist approach to protect their infant industries (Ayentimi, & Burgess, 2019). Industrial policy was shifted to policy-mix in 1980s with a sound horizontal component (a policy not supporting a particular sector). EU, for example,

has showed this change by giving up all policies that supported specific industries and sectors and resultantly created a competitive advantage within common market (Blackie, & Turner, 2018). France has implied this change by remoulding interventionist policies that were previously implemented at large scale (van Zanden., 2009).

Neoliberal approach towards industrial policy in developed economies is recently contrasted by numerous trends. This suggests that industrial policy should re-emerge (Van-Zanden, 2009). Firstly, recent financial crisis has triggered many governments to actively implement such policies that can save organizations and industries (such as through bail outs), create fiscal stimulus and combat unemployment (Mathews, & Tan, 2014). Secondly, as markets have become globalised it becomes necessary to stimulate the regional development and care for local industry (Bakker, 2013). Thirdly, structural changes within economy further extend the industrial policy to new industries (Alshumaimri, et al., 2010). However, industrial policy developed in organized and strategic manner particularly in aligns with innovation policy and technology. These policies in EU and US are particularly directed towards research-industry cooperation, private-public partnerships and regional specialization and clustering. This new industrial policy has been implemented in EU since 2005 with a sound horizontal component, however with tailored policy measures related to specific industries and sectors of strategic significance (Zourek [2007](#)). As compared to previous neoliberal approach and interventionist' approach, this approach is relatively less extreme. This approach has been labelled as 'matrix approach' by Earle, & Gehlbach, (2015) and as 'pragmatic' by Hendrickson, (2015).

Figure 2.4 Industrial policies

The major components of constant industrial development include industry upgrading, diversification and restructuring see figure above (Hendrickson, 2015). Some countries, particularly East-Asian, have obtained significant success by implementing the combination of export-oriented strategy and protection of infant industry (Bogart, 2018). By studying industrial policy both in China and Thailand, Zhu (2007) observed that a combination of EOI (export-oriented industrialization) strategy and ISI (import-substituting industrialization) strategy have been implemented in both economies while shifting to the export promotion; China since 1980s and Taiwan since 1960s. He further characterized this economic success to the combine implementation of EOI and ISI strategies. Under import substitution agenda, other developing nations have significantly supported the privately owned and public organizations (Amsden [2008](#)). Through infant-industry support policies, many countries (particularly African countries) have provided continuous support to their industrial development (Stevenson, et al., 2013). In this regard, Hutchinson, & Dowd, (2018) proposed that as low-income nations have made little efforts regarding

industrial development therefore more precise industrial policies are needed for these economies to protect and support their industries.

Based on the experiences in Western European countries, Wade ([2012](#)) observed renewed interest among developing countries to reinforce industrial policy, particularly due to increased competition at global level. The neoliberal policy, which had been heavily promoted by Washington consensus in Latin-American countries in 1980s, included financial liberalization and extensive privatization. However, in 1990s, these countries started to move away from such policy trend. After surveying the industrial policies that were implemented in Caribbean and Latin America in 1994 to 1996, Melo ([2001](#)) observed that these economies emphasised on development of new industrial policies. He further added that these new policies “aim to improve the competitiveness of domestic producers in a new, increasingly integrated and open world economy” by means of explicit government intervention (Melo [2001](#), pp. 7). Peres ([2009](#)) has also overviewed industrial policies implemented in Latin American countries and argued that industrial policy, since 1980s, has continuously focused on specific sectors, while the experience was different in Latin America. Chile, for example, strongly relied on horizontal policy approach while government of Peru, Uruguay and Costa Rica supported specific enterprises (Peres [2009](#)).

However, Peres ([2009](#)) argued that Mexico and Brazil have stimulated the technological development by creating technology funds along with other specific sectoral focus programmes. By emphasising on policy framework intending to trigger financial entry in Latin American countries (such as publicly provision of structured finance, market infrastructure, public lending, transactional cost subsidies and credit guarantee system) De la Torre et al. ([2007](#)) clearly differentiated laissez-faire policy, Intermediate policy and interventionist policy variation that particularly targets a specific set of the policy interventions - in highly restricted manner - that provides support to development of private sector and deals with market failures. They also observed many regional institutions that are gradually moving toward this policy.

2.3 TEXTILE INDUSTRY SIGNIFICANCE

In this study, the meaning of ‘textiles’ as well as the range of textile materials (Cloth, a woven or knit cloth, a fibre, filament, or yarn used in making cloth) that might

conceivably fall under this umbrella definition. Therefore, present study is including all textile materials with the purpose to present critical evaluation of the decline in the textile industry in Pakistan and recovery proposals. Reviewing the textile industry in Pakistan is inevitably a multi-faceted process. The sector forms an essential part of the societal and economical scene in the country. Beyond industrial boundaries, the sector has undeniable impact on the country's economy and export revenues on one hand, and on the society and agricultural life on the other hand [CITATION Mem16 \l 2057]. The industry has far reaching implications that go beyond the limitation of Pakistan as a country to involve the global textile industry with Pakistan as a major international supplier of textile and prominent buyer of fabrication machinery [CITATION Yar10 \l 2057]. It involves several trajectories on the national, regional, and global levels.

Nationally, the industry is the largest manufacturing sector in Pakistan and a corner stone in the Pakistani economic system [CITATION Cae08 \l 2057]. It contributes to the national gross domestic production (GDP) with circa 10% [CITATION Law15 \l 2057]. It employs a massive labour force that amounts to almost half of the country's work power covering over 2000 organisations of different sizes ranging from small to large [CITATION Daw17 \l 2057]. The sector makes best use of Pakistan's largest agricultural crop, cotton, to generate over 70% of the country's much needed export returns [CITATION Hus17 \l 2057]. Combined, these factors make the textile sector in Pakistan an essential strategic part of the country's national economy in terms of income and employment opportunities [CITATION Spi17 \l 2057]. In 2013, Pakistan had "1,221 ginning units, 442 spinning units, 124 large spinning units and 425 small units" specialised in textile production [CITATION The131 \l 2057].

Regionally, the industry has made Pakistan the eighth biggest supplier of textile in Asia. The country ranks amongst the top 5 producers of cotton in the continent and enjoys "the third largest spinning capacity in Asia after China and India" [CITATION The131 \l 2057]. Globally, Pakistani is the tenth producer of textile in the world with a significant share of the world's spinning capacity that exceeds 5% [CITATION Daw17 \l 2057]. The global significance of the Pakistani textile industry is not limited to textile production and exports; it influences the international market of textile

machinery with purchases worth of over a billion US dollars [CITATION JCR10 \l 2057].

The areas covered in this literature review are perceived the most pertinent to answering the research questions, achieving its objectives, and fulfilling its aim. The research raises key questions as to the variables that led to a sluggish textile industry in Pakistan, its rivalry in the regional and international arenas and ways to uplift it. Answering these questions, the research undertakes an evaluation of the industry, an assessment of its current position, identification of the causes of its decline and a benchmarking of the textile industry in Pakistan with its regional and international rivals. The aim is to generate proposals that fit the specific evolving needs of the stumbling textile industry in Pakistan. This is meant to notable contribute to a better economy, increased exports, and welfare of a large social group in Pakistan identified as people working in the textile field.

To achieve this goal, the review covers the evolution of the textile industry in Pakistan, a theoretical framework of its decline in terms the industry decline theory and the industry's current position together with perceived factors impacting this stagnation. Furthermore, the review examines the Pakistani textile industry through the lens of regional and global benchmarking. It covers studies both in the academic and professional literature including theories and industry expert views. Doing so, the research fills a vacuum in the textile industry developmental studies in Pakistan that has not received as much interest as it should both at the economical and industrial levels.

The textile industry literature in general and the Pakistani textile industry literature in particular together with the industry decline and revival literature are broad subjects that are too difficult to be covered all at once, on one hand. On the other hand, examination of all these areas together is seen as an unnecessary process that would overwhelm the research with a literature review that is unnecessarily significant to its subject matter, aims and objectives. Therefore, the rational of the chosen parts of literature is to keep the research on track within the context of its objectives with a review that is seen as closely related to its subject matter. Due to

the nature of the case discussed, a lot of practical and contemporary literature is reviewed.

Studying how the Pakistani textile industry evolved both in academia and practice is meant to shed light on the foundation of the industry and its golden age so that the industry slack and its causes are easier to understand and identified in comparison to the industry's recent situation. The industry deterioration theories are highly significant in the trial of fitting the decline of the Pakistani textile industry into a theoretical framework based on its practical development. This is perceived key to synthesising typological and professional proposals for recovery, which is the aim of this research. The controversial contemporary literature of the textile industry in Pakistan is perceived crucial to better understanding of the industry fall-back.

Focusing on the practical and professional side of literature is intended to explore as much as possible of the variant expert perceptions of the industry stagnation, its causes and proposed possible solutions. This is important to both the realistic evaluation of the industry decline and the development of effective revival recommendations in support of the study's aim and objectives. Finally, benchmarking is intended to place the Pakistani textile industry within the context of global competition both during its peak and decline. This is significant to identifying the competitive advantages and disadvantages of the industry within the changing global rivalry environment so long to clarify what can be done to withstand international competition and reclaim the industry's top position in today's global industry standards, which is the main aim of this study.

2.4 THE EVOLUTION OF THE PAKISTANI TEXTILE INDUSTRY

2.4.1 Pakistan's cotton production

Many authors and sources appear to agree that the historic wealth of Pakistan's cotton as the top farming produce was the major incentive for the growth of the textile industry in Pakistan [CITATION Pak63 \l 2057], [CITATION Ass77 \l 2057] [CITATION Wer79 \l 2057] and [CITATION Int67 \l 2057]. Historically, the strategic agronomic crop of cotton aka white gold in Pakistan has been the main source of living for the country's large cotton-growing community [CITATION

Law15 \ 2057]. The agri-business employs 1.3 million growers with over ten million people who depend on the cotton harvest as the sole provider for living including family members [CITATION Gov17 \ 2057]. They amount to circa one third of the overall farming community in Pakistan estimated at 5 million farmers [CITATION Rav15 \ 2057].

Figure 2.5 Pakistan's cotton crop production by region Source: (Crutchfeld, 2018)

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The cotton crop is grown over an area of thirty thousand square meters constituting about 15% of the agricultural area of Pakistan [CITATION Pak17 \ 2057]. Cotton growing areas are shown in the map below. The harvest and its ancillary products is a real asset to national economy with around 10% contribution to the country's GDP and over 50% share of the country's hard currency returns as over 60% of the harvest is exported in the form of raw or manufactured materials while the rest is consumed locally [CITATION Pak17 \ 2057]. Unsurprisingly, the Pakistani textile industry has always been largely influenced by the wellbeing of cotton production. The good yield ranging between 200 to 300 kilograms per hectare back in the fifties and sixties of the twentieth century triggered the development of the Pakistani textile

industry and the cotton yield booming of over 760 kilograms per hectare back in the eighties and early nineties marked the peak of the industry [CITATION Pak17 \l 2057]. The figure 2-3 has showed the crop production distribution by the districts of Pakistan. Furthermore, this figure also highlighted how much different province of Pakistan are contributing toward crop production.

Figure 2.6 Pakistan's cotton growing areas and yield (Source: Crutchfeld, 2018)

Consequently, Pakistan ranks as the fourth global cotton supplier and the third largest cotton consumer in the world with a crop worth of over 5 billion US dollars mainly sold to Pakistani textile manufacturers and partially exported abroad [CITATION Sti16 \l 2057]. The fluctuation of cotton production has always had its impact on Pakistan's textile industry [CITATION Ade16 \l 2057]. The Pakistani cotton production grew rapidly between the early years of the Pakistani textile industry in early 1960s and the surge of the industry during 1990s from around three hundred thousand tonnes to over one million three hundred thousand tons [CITATION Ade16 \l 2057]. During that period the development of the cotton yield was notably correlated with the evolution of the textile industry in Pakistan [CITATION Ahm10 \l 2057]. However, the formula changed by the advent of the

twenty first century and a dichotomy started to appear between the two trajectories of production [CITATION Ahm16 \l 2057].

With some downfalls due to occasional drought and to miss-governance practices sometimes, the cotton production continued to surge with over two million tonnes produced in 2008 and a dramatic increase to over two and a half million tonnes in 2015 [CITATION Cru18 \l 2057]. The country's cotton production is expected to exceed two million tonnes in 2018 with a 6% rise from 2017 due to over 15% expansion in cotton-cultivated areas estimated at about three million hectares [CITATION Cru18 \l 2057]. The current upsurge is also associated with a significant increase in raw cotton prices combined with government subsidies including supported fertiliser and power prices together with low-interest loans and decreased duties [CITATION Cru18 \l 2057]. This fluctuated increase in the cotton production has kept Pakistan on the list of the top global producers of cotton. According to Aazim (2019), many politicians are involved in the cultivating the sugar cane on due to increasing the number of sugar mills as a result the sugar cultivation is decreased the focus on cotton cultivation. The reduction of cotton cultivation has decreased the quality input of textile industry in Pakistan (Aazim 2019).

Nonetheless, cotton yield per area in Pakistan is still perceived as way behind its developed rivals such as the United States of America [CITATION Bok16 \l 2057]. This slack is attributed to certain aspects that characterise the Pakistani cotton farming including underdeveloped irrigation systems, archaic agricultural methods and scarcity of research and development and their applications that are badly needed especially in terms of controlling pests that have harshly hit and affected the cotton yield on various occasions [CITATION Spi17 \l 2057].

A study by Zafar, et al., (2016, p.12) identified "factors affecting cotton production" between "1965" and "2012" found "that the major factors were government expenditure on research and extension and short-term credit extended to farmers by commercial banks and Agriculture bank. The elasticity of supply response with respect to research and extension was 0.21 and 0.6 in the short-run and longrun respectively. The elasticity of supply response with respect to agricultural credit was found to be 0.43 in the short-run and 0.66 in the long-run." [CITATION Ade16 \p 12 \l

2057]. The study suggests “that a 10 per cent increase in the provision of short-term credit will result in a 3.2 per cent increase and 7.4 per cent increase in area planted to cotton.” [CITATION Ade16 \p 12 \l 2057]. It proposes that an uplift in state spending on researching and development would lead to a significant expansion of cotton growing areas both on the short and long terms [CITATION Ade16 \l 2057].

Development of cotton farmers skills by state, non-for-profit organisations and privately-owned companies together with loan facilities by banks were also suggested as solutions for an enhanced cotton production in Pakistan [CITATION Ade16 \l 2057]. The aforesaid proposed solutions for the improvement of cotton harvest in Pakistan are seen crucial to the development of the textile industry in the country as it is largely dependent on the cotton harvest and a better cotton yield in quantity and quality would certainly contribute to a healthier textile production in Pakistan [CITATION Sad14 \l 2057]. However, the inhibits of cotton production are not perceived as a key cause for the Pakistani textile industry decline. In fact, despite its unessential problems, Pakistan’s cotton harvest has seen fluctuating rise in production as explained in figure 3 below. Adversely, the textile industry in Pakistan has been in asymmetry with the increase in cotton production starting from the beginning of the past decade [CITATION Sti16 \l 2057]

Figure 2.7 Figure 2-5 Pakistan's cotton production and yield 2007- 2018 (Source: Crutchfeld, 2018)

2.5 THE TEXTILE INDUSTRY IN PAKISTAN

The textile industry in Pakistan is undoubtedly a cross-sectional subject. It has significant reflections on several features of life in Pakistan including economy, agriculture, social life, employment, gross domestic production, national returns, and other auxiliary areas [CITATION Far12 \l 2057]. Furthermore, its interterritorial implications cannot be denied as one of the largest in a continent that enjoys an important share of the world's textile and garments supply market [CITATION Ahm16 \l 2057]. More widely, its impact on global textile trading is immense with two-way contributions in relation to the export and import of raw materials, manufactured products and machines and equipment [CITATION Yar10 \l 2057]. Together, these features make the industry a curious and inviting area of research hence outcomes are likely to have far-reaching reflections involving not only the Pakistani economy and society, but also the Asian and global textile industry in general. Therefore, the choice of this research's subject matter and its importance stems from this key characteristic.

For Pakistan, the textile industry is by far the largest economic and agronomic sector- hence the strategic cotton crop involvement- and eventually the foundation pillar of socioeconomic life in Pakistan [CITATION Sad14 \l 2057]. This is clearly manifested in the industry's significant contribution of about 10% to the state's gross domestic production [CITATION Law15 \l 2057]. Equally important to the country's socioeconomics is the huge workforce that run the sector which amounts to around 50% of Pakistan's labour force spread over thousands of different-sized enterprises [CITATION Gov17 \l 2057]. Being the major consumer of the country's cotton harvest, the industry provides living for about 10 million Pakistani farmers while at the same time generates over 60% of the country's exporting income, just another key contribution to Pakistan's welfare [CITATION Hus17 \l 2057]. Consequently, constituting circa 50% of Pakistan's industrial force, it goes without saying that the textile business is a key element of Pakistan's economy at the financial, industrial, agricultural and recruitment levels [CITATION Spi17 \l 2057]. This underlines the aim of this research and makes its intended contribution to enhancing this sector a contribution to the wellbeing of Pakistan.

According to the prime representative of the Pakistani Textile sector, All Pakistan Textile Mills Association (APTMA), the colossal industry encompasses a large number of influential organisations in “the textile spinning, weaving, and composite mills” including “396 textile mills out of which 315 are spinning, 44 weaving and 37 composite units. These spinning mills have production facilities of texturing, mercerizing and dyeing of yarns; weaving mills have sizeable number of air-jet looms, and the composite mills have manufacturing facilities from spinning to finished textile products under one roof.” [CITATION All18 \l 2057]. The industry enjoys an installation capability accounting for “9,661,366 spindles, 61,608 rotors, 10,452 Shuttleless / Air jet Looms and 1897 conventional looms [CITATION All18 \l 2057]. The sector manufactures different kinds of woven threads, “yarns” and textile materials including bedsheets [CITATION All18 \l 2057].

However, Shah, et al., (2014) explains how the Pakistani textile sector's capacity developed over the past couple of decades. According to him, between 1999 and 2000, the industry included “about 443 textile units, 8,477,000 spindles, 149,780 rotors and 9944 looms” [CITATION Sha14 \p 44 \l 2057]. But, between 2003 and

2004, it witnessed a significant expansion in its capacity which saw “about 456, Spindles to 9,590,000 rotors to 146,640 and looms to 10,646 [CITATION Sha14 \p 44 \l 2057]. A further capacity growth was observed between 2005 and 2006 with “textile units 461, spindles 10,437,000, rotors 155,104 and looms 8747” [CITATION Sha14 \p 44 \l 2057]. The sector’s capacity expansion continued over 2006 and 2007 to include “567 units, 1198000 spindles, 11,809,000 rotors and 9000 looms” [CITATION Sha14 \p 44 \l 2057]. While The Express Tribune, (2013) reported the Pakistani textile industry capacity as “1,221 ginning units, 442 spinning units, 124 large spinning units and 425 small units” [CITATION The131 \l 2057].

Examination of the Pakistani textile industry changeable capacity trajectory reveals that the total number of textile units, machinery and equipment invested into the sector changed from about six and a half million units in 2000 to around nine and a half million in 2004 to over ten and a half million in 2006 to over eleven million in 2007 to less than ten million in 2018 [CITATION Sha14 \l 2057] and [CITATION All18 \l 2057]. This can translate into a 12.85% increase in invested capacity in 2004 in comparison to 2000. It also means a further increase of 8.75% in operation capacity between 2004 and 2006 with a slight extra rise of 4.88% in 2007 from previous year. Nonetheless, the figures show a significant capacity drop of 12.10% in 2018 from 2007. Notably, the sector’s invested capacity in 2018 is almost the same as that of 2004.

This fluctuation in the industry’s operational capacity is quite important as an initial indication of the sector’s tumbling progress over the past decade [CITATION Bus16 \l 2057]. It can be seen as a reflection of the industry crisis that left the sector almost standstill since 2004 with no significant forward progression. A crisis that has made both incumbent and new investors clearly reluctant to put extra funds into the sector and has put them away from investing in new units and machinery [CITATION Hus17 \l 2057]. However, some optimists such as [CITATION Jab17 \l 2057] believe that the textile industry in Pakistan is progressing steadily and rapidly. They base their judgement on the static statistical figures including the industry’s contribution to the economy, the number of people it employs, the quantity of cotton produced in Pakistan and the claimed government incentives [CITATION Jab17 \l 2057].

It is also contended that, continentally, Pakistan is the eighth largest producer of fabrics amongst the Asian countries and one of the top five suppliers of cotton in the region; only China and India enjoy spinning capacities higher than Pakistan putting it third continentally in this key textile sector [CITATION The131 \l 2057]. Internationally, Pakistan's textile production amounts to the tenth worldwide with an important 5% contribution to the world's capacity in spinning [CITATION Daw17 \l 2057]. It contributes to the intercontinental textile market with a 10%-share [CITATION Tex15 \l 2057]. Advocates of Pakistan's advanced textile industry point out the cross-production-influence of the sector on global economy through its purchase power of textile machines and equipment which is estimated at one billion US dollars at least [CITATION JCR10 \l 2057]. They refer to evidence such as slight the year-on-year and quarter-on-quarter rises in exports over the past few years. However, they condone the fact that with all the increases, figures are still below peak years.

For example, a circa 8% surge in the past quarter of 2018 from the same quarter in 2017 is expected to bring the overall exports of the year to around 13 billion US dollars [CITATION Ran17 \l 2057]. However, 2017 figures were only very thinly higher than 2016's which witnessed over-a-billion-USD dropdown from the previous year that constituted a further plunge from 2014' figures of around 13.8 billion dollars [CITATION Ran17 \l 2057]. As a result, there are evidence that despite the ostensible changes in export and production figures and the provided government enticements, there are still major issues that hold the industry back and impact its regional and international rivalry [CITATION Daw17 \l 2057]. Such inhibits include major matters such as the power supply and its uncompetitively high cost, banking and financing hurdles and troublesome and bureaucratic taxation system [CITATION Hus17 \l 2057]. However, there is almost consensus that the Pakistani textile industry once achieved impressive advancements and boomed as a highly competitive business on both the regional and global arenas [CITATION Ahm10 \l 2057].

2.6 THE GOLDEN ERA OF PAKISTAN'S TEXTILE INDUSTRY

The industry experienced an impressive booming during the second half of the twentieth century that saw a remarkable surge in fabric manufacturing facilities from a few to over 600 units [CITATION Ahm10 \l 2057]. The booming period was linked to an inspiring explosion in spinning machinery that incredibly jumped from under two hundred thousand to over eight million machines [CITATION Rav15 \l 2057]. The surge resonated in the international textile machinery market with over a billion US dollar worth of textile equipment purchase that made the industry a key international player in the textile supplies market [CITATION Yar10 \l 2057]. The development had wider implications on the Pakistani life given the colossal workforce needed to produce the value-added finished products from raw cotton including a wide range of products such as fibres, yarns, fabrics, and apparels [CITATION Tex15 \l 2057]. The result was increased exports and plenty of the much-needed hard currency inflow into the Pakistani economy that led to thriving businesses within a sector capable of playing a key role in the global textile industry [CITATION Kir14 \l 2057]

A key issue of this research is evaluating how the Pakistani textile industry boomed and what factors were associated with the phenomenal heave in production capacity and export capability. This is of multiple benefit for the purpose of the study as it directly and indirectly addresses three of its objectives. First, it fulfils the objective of evaluating the industry. Second, it contributes to understanding factors that led to the industry decline and third, it helps understanding its current position and developing proposals for its revival. The typological and practical perspective of the rapid growth of the Pakistani textile industry that reportedly started by the late forties and early fifties of the twentieth century involves Burns's, (1939) industry expansion theory, [CITATION Joh97 \l 2057], [CITATION Mil06 \l 2057], [CITATION Mur06 \l 2057], [CITATION Cae08 \l 2057], [CITATION Ahm10 \l 2057], [CITATION Law15 \l 2057] [CITATION Spi17 \l 2057] and others.

2.6.1 Cotton

Historically, Pakistan's strategic agronomic crop of cotton aka white gold has always been the most important resource for the Pakistani textile industry with ongoing impact on its development [CITATION Mil06 \l 2057]. The crop production change has always had its impact on Pakistan's textile industry [CITATION Ade16 \l 2057].

Therefore, changes to its production, yields, growing areas and international price fluctuation are seen as a threat to the major industry resource which is contributing to its stagnation [CITATION Bok16 \l 2057]. For example, the improvement in the cotton yields up to 300 kilograms per hectare back in the fifties and sixties of the twentieth century triggered the evolution of the Pakistani textile industry and the its booming up to around 800 kilograms per hectare in the eighties and early nineties marked the peak of the industry [CITATION Pak17 \l 2057].

Similarly, the rapid growth in the cotton production during the same period from around three hundred thousand tonnes to over one million three hundred thousand tons largely contributed to a surge in the industry [CITATION Ade16 \l 2057]. During that time, cotton yield improvement was notably correlated with the evolution of the textile industry in Pakistan [CITATION Ahm10 \l 2057]. By contrast, the industry went down when cotton was hit by draught, pests, agricultural diseases, or miss-governance practices [CITATION Law15 \l 2057]. However, the 2015 dramatic increase in the cotton production to over two and a half million tonnes lead to an increase in textile production and exports of the year [CITATION Cru18 \l 2057]. Although the country's cotton production is forecasted to rise by 6% from 2017 and exceed two million tonnes this year, potential threats to the crop may threaten the already troubled industry [CITATION Cru18 \l 2057].

2.6.2 Power supply

The power supply crisis in Pakistan can be regarded as a key threat to the Pakistani textile industry that puts it, from the industry change theory view, on a fundamental changing direction as it threatens one of the key resources of the industry- power [CITATION Mcg04 \l 2057]. The serious Pakistan's power supply crisis can be considered as evidence of the fundamental changing direction of the textile industry in Pakistan with the long hours of electricity cuts forcing many small and medium sized players to quit the industry [CITATION Jam151 \l 2057]. For large participants who could invest in alternative energy solutions, it's a doubly threat as it also threatened their capital investment resources with extra expenses that impacted global competitiveness of the industry [CITATION Daw17 \l 2057].

This can also be seen as a threat to the industry's main activities with the power shortage crisis leading to increased production cost and adding an extra burden to the muddled industry [CITATION Man16 \l 2057]. Reportedly, the country's electricity problem sits on top of the list of inhibits for the industry development [CITATION Mai17 \l 2057]. Thousands of small and medium sized industry participants found themselves obliged to close and leave the industry as they were unable to cope with long hours of electricity cuts [CITATION Mai17 \l 2057]. This fundamentally changing environment of the Pakistani textile industry has posed high risk to participants forcing some to leave and mediating a developmental risk for survivals represented in cheaper alternative options available form international competitors, which threatens their production activities and export sustainability [CITATION Man16 \l 2057].

2.6.3 Labour system

The industry's perceived deficient labour system just add salt to the injury with a fundamental threat to the industry's human resource as many workers have been discouraged to continue working in the sector due to improper management practices in the sector [CITATION Hus17 \l 2057]. Coupled with notable lack of labour protection, lots of examples of unfair practices by textile firms' managements against employees have triggered serious risk to the industry's resource of workers [CITATION Hus17 \l 2057]. The risk has translated into increasing employee turnover in the industry over recent years [CITATION Ahm16 \l 2057]. So, in addition to the fundamental and developmental directions, the inadequate labour system in the industry can be understood as putting the industry on an innovative change direction perceived in the incurred lack of skills and innovation that are badly needed to enhance the industry's troubled competitiveness [CITATION Nas16 \l 2057].

2.6.4 Research and development

Categorising the changeable direction of the Pakistani textile industry, it can be viewed ranging between both the constructional and the infrastructural with fundamental menace to its operations and main resources; Consequently, embracing thorough industry-wide research and development through building alliances and coalitions with industry players including the government can be the

best way to addressing such threats and protecting the industry from decline [CITATION McG04 \l 2057] and [CITATION Sha14 \l 2057]. Yet, little efforts have been made both on the business and governmental levels to improve the industry's deteriorating situation [CITATION Zia15 \l 2057]. Presumably, the industry doesn't allocate enough resources and efforts to research and development nor does it leverage contemporary technical tools to provide innovative products that match those available from global competitors [CITATION Sha14 \l 2057]. It uses traditional techniques which makes it struggle to meet the standards of sophisticated global buyers [CITATION Mem16 \l 2057].

2.6.5 High production cost

A double threat to the Pakistani textile industry is inherent in the high cost of production. This does not only threatens exhausting the main financial resources and investments but also puts its competitiveness at risk as its products have proven more expensive than international competitors' and buyers are justifiably shifting to cheaper competitive alternatives available in the global market [CITATION Sad14 \l 2057]. As a result, the fundamental and developmental changes in the global environment of the industry have forced the Pakistani textile industry into a constructional-infrastructural change direction where its main investment resources and operational activities are at serious risk [CITATION Mcg04 \l 2057] and [CITATION Har83 \l 2057]. This requires exhaustive reconsideration of different expenses related to the industry by a coalition that includes the government together with industry participants [CITATION Jam151 \l 2057].

Let alone its scarcity, the high cost of energy has been a major threat to the industry over past years [CITATION Mai17 \l 2057]. Under current regulations, Pakistani textile manufacturers are obliged to use local liquid gas at a rate that is double its regional rivals'; electricity cost is also almost 50% more expensive than it is in other Asian countries[CITATION Ran17 \l 2057].The perceived high production cost of the industry has prompted governmental intervention to decrease cost through a bailout of about 200 million Rupees in addition to tax incentives to be paid back to textile exporters [CITATION Aft17 \l 2057]. However, the country's highest ever budget deficit and lack of cash have restrained the government from fulfilling its promises; consequently, the much-needed subsidy has not been paid to the industry

on one hand [CITATION Aft17 \l 2057]. On the other hand, export tax refunds have been stuck into a bureaucratic process and the industry's competitiveness is still under real threat of high cost, as a result [CITATION Zia15 \l 2057].

2.6.6 Corruption and terrorism

It argues that factors like incompetent or myopic bureaucracies and corruption by private sectors increase the probability of government failures more than probability of the market failures (Bae, & Mah, 2019). Neoclassical economics emphasis on documenting government failure cases and argues that these failures are mainly due to factors like corruption and incompetent or myopic bureaucracies (Fraser, & Kelly, 2010). The previous studies have highlighted that there are many terrorism attacks, political instability, and high level of corrupt politicians in Pakistan (Azeem et al., 2017; Nadeem et al., 2020). Therefore, it has increased the high taxes and bearing high cost of production as well as low level of competitive advantages compared to other Asian countries such as China and India. Due to terrorism attacks, the textile industry is also negatively influenced as buyers and employees are feeling insecure and unsafe Pakistan (Azeem et al., 2017; Nadeem et al., 2020). The government has not enough financial support as they must pay high instalments of interest on national debt and facing budget deficit from many decades. The previous and current political governments of Pakistan have borrowed US\$92 billion and above dollars from IMF, China and USA, which pressurizes the Pakistani currency by paying instalments at higher interest rate and by devaluation. But unfortunately, this money is being used by corrupt administration and politicians in form of making their personal assets. Resultantly, this corruption leads to produce many burdens for businesses in form of heavy tariffs, taxes, exports and import duties etc.

2.6.7 Benchmarking and rivalry

Benchmarking is key to explaining the Pakistani textile industry within the changing rivalry context of the global textile industry and understanding its ability to withstand international competition in today's global industry standards. [CITATION Har83 \l 2057] highlight rivalry assessment and appraisal of competitors and their products as a determining factor in deciding what stage the industry is going through. If it's making profitable and competitive products that attract customers' attention, the industry must be thriving in its evolution or booming stage and managers can decide

to carry on their business activities and make more profits [CITATION Har83 \l 2057]. However, if the industry is no longer profitable and is unable to generate competitive products, it must be declining and heading towards the end of its lifecycle; therefore, executives need to choose between leaving the industry or adapting an “end-game” strategy [CITATION Har83 \l 2057].

They argue that market leaders who offer competitive products can sustain industry downfalls even during declines as they dominate product supply and surpass competitors [CITATION Har83 \l 2057]. Additionally, [CITATION RNi98 \l 2057], [CITATION DLu93 \l 2057] and [CITATION McG04 \l 2057] recognise industry's lack of competitive features and its inability to withstand global competition as a major threat that can change the industry's direction and land it in a deteriorating stage where participants will be obliged to apply special strategies to address the developing environment of the industry. The presumed lagging of the Pakistani textile industry behind regional and global competitors is understood to be one of the main reasons for its stagnation [CITATION Jam151 \l 2057].

Threats of rivalry to the Pakistani textile industry can be classified into two categories: rivalry from traditional textile powers such as China and India and competition from evolving textile powers such as Vietnam and Bangladesh that have been recently able to dramatically develop their industries and increase their global market shares with highly competitive products and prices [CITATION Ahm16 \l 2057] and [CITATION Zia15 \l 2057]. Benchmarking comparisons between the textile industry in Pakistan on one hand and each of the above rivalry powers on the other hand are discussed below.

2.6.8 Benchmarking of the Pakistani and Chinese textile industries

While Pakistan is the tenth producer of textile in the world with 5% share of the world's spinning capacity [CITATION Daw17 \l 2057], China is the largest global producer with over 40% share of the global textile market [CITATION Tex17 \l 2057]. The Pakistani textile industry contributes to over 60% of national exports against 5% contribution by the Chinese, constitutes around half of the country's manufacturing power against the Chinese that amounts to less than 5%, employs over 40% of Pakistan's workforce against less than 0.05% employment share for the Chinese and contributes to about 10% of Pakistan's GDP against about 1%

contribution from the Chinese [CITATION Yul10 \l 2057]. However, investment in the Chinese textile industry is more than double the amounts invested in the Pakistani [CITATION Yul10 \l 2057].

More importantly, availability of cheap resources and a supportive taxation system are key to industry global competitiveness [CITATION McG04 \l 2057]. In this regard, labour cost in Pakistan is almost triple the cost in China, electricity cost is more than \$ 0.10 per unit higher than in China, industrial construction cost is over 50% higher in Pakistan, and the Chinese taxation system is clearly more supportive to the industry with overall levies about 30% less than Pakistan's; while export services expenses such as customs clearance and port charges in Pakistan are almost double the cost and time of the same services in China [CITATION Yul10 \l 2057]. This has clearly contributed to a higher rivalry for the Chinese industry that translates into over US\$ 255 billion textile exports against around \$ 12 billion Pakistani exports [CITATION Tex17 \l 2057] and [CITATION Aft17 \l 2057].

2.6.9 Benchmarking of the Pakistani and Indian textile industries

Like the Pakistani, the Indian textile industry is the largest manufacturing sector in the country and the second largest employer with over 40 million workers and 20 million more indirectly involved in the sector, while the Pakistani is the largest in labour force [CITATION Muh12 \l 2057]. Compared to Pakistan's tenth rank [CITATION Daw17 \l 2057], the Indian textile industry stands second in the World after China with around 15% contribution to India's manufacturing power against about 50% contribution by the Pakistani, and while the Pakistani contributes about 60% to national exports, the Indian industry's contribution is no more than 17% [CITATION Muh12 \l 2057]. Pakistan is "the third largest spinning capacity in Asia after China and India" [CITATION The131 \l 2057] with a 5%-share of the world's spinning capacity [CITATION Daw17 \l 2057]. However, India is the world's largest supplier of yarn with 25%-share of global yarn supply and has 12%-share of global fibre fabric market [CITATION Muh12 \l 2057].

With over US\$ 105 billion in size, the Indian textiles industry is more than double the Pakistani and might become 4 times the size of the Pakistani industry with forecasts that it'll be over US\$ 200 billion by 2021 [CITATION Ind17 \l 2057]. Although the Pakistani industry contributes about 10% to the country's GDP, the 5% contribution

of the Indian Textile Industry includes over US\$ 40 billion exports which is almost 4 times the size of the Pakistani textile exports; moreover, India's textile exports are expected to rise to over US\$ 175 over coming years [CITATION Ind17 \l 2057]. This clear advancement of the Indian textile industry over the Pakistani is largely attributed to its lower production cost and lower-cost resources, availability of talented and skilled labour, better leverage of technology and researching to offer internationally competitive products and more supportive regulatory and taxation system than that available to the Pakistani industry [CITATION Ang10 \l 2057].

It can be argued that the Indian textile industry success is based on good understanding of the global textile industry changing context and its ability to build internal and external coalitions to increase its competitiveness. For example, nationally, the government and online trading platforms have formed a coalition aimed at developing the country's looming sector [CITATION Ind17 \l 2057]. Internationally, alliances have been established with global markets such as China, Australia and Africa for mutual trade benefits [CITATION Ind17 \l 2057]. Other examples include tax preferences for imports of hi-tech machinery and innovative exports that add value to the industry and increase its global rivalry [CITATION Ind17 \l 2057]. All the above-mentioned factors can be regarded as positively impacting textile industry and leading to its development. However, the Pakistani textile industry is seen as lacking such success factors which has led to its shrink.

2.6.10 Benchmarking of the Pakistani and Vietnamese textile industries

Although it is an emerging industry that arguably evolved after the country joined the World Trade Organisation in 2007, the Vietnamese textile industry has been able to achieve rapid development and prove good level of global competitiveness over past years [CITATION Amb17 \l 2057]. The industry includes over 6000 specialised organisations compared to over 2000 Pakistani companies [CITATION Hou17 \l 2057]. While the Pakistani textile industry has been struggling to attract foreign investment into the sector, the emerging Vietnamese industry has been able to entice over a billion US dollars' worth of foreign investment with 15% of the sector operated by foreign investors [CITATION Jam151 \l 2057] and [CITATION Amb17 \l 2057]. Moreover, foreign investment has been significantly increasing with

about 12% uplift in 2017 pumping an extra US\$ 16 billion into the sector, something the Pakistani industry is far from [CITATION Akt18 \l 2057].

As in the Pakistani, the Vietnamese industry is one of the largest employers in the country with a labour force of about two and a half million workers [CITATION Hou17 \l 2057]. Nonetheless, in contrast to the perceived deficient labour system in the Pakistani industry, the Vietnamese labour system looks organised and advanced with workers enjoying good protection in terms of working hours, overtime and contractual regulations; furthermore, the system facilitates transfer of skills and talent through relevant talent import regulations [CITATION Amb17 \l 2057]. Such practices have landed the Vietnamese industry on the right trajectory within the context of the changing global textile industry, which has ranked it the third largest global exporter of clothing items with 7% share of international markets compared to Pakistan that ranks 10th with no more than 5% share of the global market [CITATION Amb17 \l 2057].

Despite the large contribution of the Pakistani industry to national exports of 70%, the 16% contribution of the Vietnamese industry to the country's exports amounts to over US\$ 24.5 billion, which is double the size of the Pakistani. The Vietnamese textile industry can be justifiably viewed as a developmental change in the context of the international textile business as it has successfully leveraged variables of the industry environment and available resources to take a developmental direction [CITATION Har83 \l 2057]. Concurrently, it can be seen as an emerging threat to the Pakistani textile industry with new competitive products and services the Pakistani industry has not been able to match [CITATION McG04 \l 2057].

2.7 BENCHMARKING OF THE PAKISTANI AND BANGLADESHI TEXTILE INDUSTRIES

With similar significance to the economy as in the Pakistani industry, the Bangladeshi textile industry employs over 65% of the country's labour with 5 million working in the sector compared to about 50% labour share for the Pakistani; the Bangladeshi industry has over 80% contribution to exports compared to 70% for the Pakistani industry [CITATION Fas17 \l 2057]. Nonetheless, although with some similar challenges to those of the Pakistani such as labour problems and power

supply deficiency, the Bangladeshi textile industry was able to uplift its exports by 8% in 2016 While Pakistan suffered a drastic drop of over 14% in exports for the same period [CITATION Saj16 \l 2057] and [CITATION Akt17 \l 2057]. While the Pakistani industry's share of international market fell by 1.7% in 2017 to US\$ 12 billion, the Bangladeshi textile share grew by 4.2% to US\$ 31 billion [CITATION Haq17 \l 2057].

The ability of the Bangladeshi industry to cope with the sector's technical advances has allowed it to make advanced competitive products and attract imports from developed global markets with over 60% of its exports have been going to the European Union [CITATION Mat16 \l 2057]. On the opposite side, according to All Pakistan Textile Association (APTMA), the Pakistani industry has lost about 15% of its competitiveness in modern technology which, in addition to survival threats to the industry, has left local sales outweighing exports [CITATION Haq17 \l 2057]. Moreover, the perceived competitiveness of the textile industry in Bangladesh has attracted more foreign investment into the sector which reached around US\$ 400 million in 2016 with 11% increase from the previous year, while the investment in the Pakistani industry which is predominantly Pakistani amounted for US\$ 560 million with about 45% fall from 2006 figures [CITATION Akt17 \l 2057] and [CITATION Haq17 \l 2057].

Ultimately, benchmarking the Pakistani textile industry with regional counterparts reveals that the industry is struggling to keep pace with changing context of the regional and global textile industry. This is evident in the industry's major slacks in terms of growth, exports, investment, and technological advances. The Pakistani industry downturn can be attributed to several threats including threats to its resources of cotton, energy supply and investment funds in addition to menaces to its operational activities such as labour regulations, innovation, and novel products. These risks have seriously impacted the industry global competitiveness and left it way behind regional and global powers in terms quality and exports. The decline stems from the industry's inability to develop in line with the global industry change trajectory. Therefore, major reforms in relation to taxation, import-export regulations, investment, labour protection, technology and innovation are badly needed for the industry to get back on the right track and maintain its sustainability.

2.8 EVIDENCE AND THEORY ON THE RELATION BETWEEN INDUSTRIAL POLICY AND GROWTH

However, which industrial policy is highly effective in triggering the growth is still not clearly understood. But according to some scholars, certain policies are effective in supporting business development but under conditions by effectively stimulating the growth (Sung, 2018). This section contains a brief discussion on literature related to this topic. Using the data obtained from Chinese firms, Aghion et al. (2012) conducted the empirical analysis and proposed a theoretical framework to test whether sectoral policies (tax, tariffs, and subsidies) are effective in terms of productivity and competitive advantage. Based on research findings, they suggested that growth can be successfully triggered by the sectoral policies if they are implemented on competitive sectors (Fischler, 2012). In the same way, Allan, et al., (2015) used the data on UK based firms and found that investment subsidies positively affect the employment and investment. According to Acemoglu et al. (2013), R&D subsidies are not effective in terms of productivity growth. They used the data on US based firms and found that R&D subsidies negatively affect the productivity growth when allocated to incumbents. They further added that productivity growth substantially increased when R&D subsidies simultaneously target new market entrants along with incumbents, incumbents are taxed heavily. By summarizing more empirical evidence on relationship between subsidies and firm performance, Bosker, et al., (2013) concluded that R&D subsidies are positively associated with public support. They further added that relationship between public support and productivity is still inconclusive. In this regard, Lee, et al., (2019) conducted a theoretical study and proposed that weak competition not only leave long-run negative effects but also prevent the catch-up. According to Steinmueller, (2013), anticompetitive policy is most appropriate for countries that are at initial stages of the development because this policy supports or protects infant industry development and allows the countries to experience faster technological convergence and growth.

After studying many case studies, Rodrik and Subramanian (2005) concluded that the industry development triggers the growth. However, it was already proposed by Stern, et al., (2017) that bank and government support to business enabled the economies –that were “backward” in 19th century – to catch-up the technological

frontier. For example, TASSEY, (2017) also supported this view. Moreover, Lee (2011) studied Korean firms in 1970s and observed industrial growth because of incumbent industry protection. In this regard, Khan (2008, pp. 57) stated that “protection and subsidies in Pakistan proved to be extremely effective in driving investment in sectors that had previously been neglected”, and “import substitution, as a method of developing new capabilities, was initially extremely successful in both India and Pakistan.” Khan and Blankenburg (2009), like Rodrik and Subramanian (2005), classified industrial policy into two groups: horizontal, weak policy and targeted policy. The first group includes those policies that discourage rent-seeking behaviour to sustain productivity across competitive markets. While second group includes the policies that specifically target sectors or firms to make them competitive (Hernández, 2016).

Based on Khan and Blankenburg`s (2009) argument, the possible scenario may be that the focus of countries` policy from strong vertical industry support now shifts to horizontal, weak support as catches-up of industrial development. Khan and Blankenburg (2009) proposed that pro-business policies are required when industry development is at early stage because such policies help to protect and support incumbent industry. However, pro-market policies are required at later stages of the industry development because such policies maximise market competition and intends to spread technology and innovation by setting-off Schumpeterian procedure of the creative destruction (Khan and Blankenburg 2009). According to Possas and Borges (2009), competition policy should be gradually enforced. In this regard, Koyama, (2014) overviewed industrial policy implemented in 8 countries (including Korea, Taiwan, Singapore, UK, Japan, Italy, France, and Germany) and proposed that these countries have implemented more interventionist and protectionist policy not only in industrialization phase but also at different industrial restructuring phases. However, these countries tend to adopt highly liberal policies since 1980s. This relates with progress that have been made under community law, WTO law, and other business agreements that collectively lead to implement more limited policy toolbox, like trade subsidies (Soofi, 2017).

If implementation of pro-market and pro-business policy triggers the industrial development at industry or macro level, these policies may possibly trade-off each

other (Aranguren, et al., 2010). Pro-business and pro-market policies are described by Rodrik and Subramanian (2005) as opposite policy packages. This trade-off, on one hand, imply that maturity level of industry determines which policy should be invoked; either pro-market or pro-business policy (Stiglitz, 2018). As developing countries have weak institutional settings, therefore pro-business policies in combination with incumbent industry protection should be implemented as such combination play a very significant role as short-term temporary solution to the market failures (Wade 2012). Moreover, Greenwald and Stiglitz (2006) challenged the traditional theory – trade stimulates the growth – by arguing that limited trade may result in industrial development, growth and technological spillovers. Pro-market and pro-business policies, on other hand, are inherently opposite to each other and simultaneously implementing both policies may decline the overall effectiveness of any of these policies. Buts and Jegers (2013) used the data on Belgium firms and found that subsidies (such as grants that intend to invest in the fixed assets) are positively associated with market share of companies. This shows that subsidies basically distort competition (Kemp, & Never, 2017).

How much thesis of sequentially implementing pro-business and pro-market policies and a possible trade-off between these policies contradicts with re-emergence of industrial development focused industrial policy as is currently witnessed in both developed as well as developing countries? By using highly restricted definition, Valila (2006) analysed the industrial policy and proposed that there is conflict between objectives of the industrial policy and objectives of the trade and competition policy. He further added that materializing this conflict is not practically needed as is needed in horizontal policy. Similarly, (Barbieri, et al., 2010) argued that there is conflict only between old industrial policy of EU and competition policy whereas new industrial policies increased tendering, cooperation, and transparency. Possas and Borges (2009, pp. 461) also shared these views with particular emphasis on the competition policy (considering it as essential component of the industrial policy). They argued that “the potential conflict between industrial policies and competition policies tends to fade away in relatively advanced developing-but-industrialized countries because in such countries industrial policy focuses on competitiveness and technological development”. Another possible scenario is that pro-business policies are largely implemented in countries with relatively less

industrial development as compare to pro-market policies (Griffin, 2013). However, pro-business policies may possibly remain significant in industrialised economies, but without opposing pro-market policies (Barker, 2017).

2.9 THE STRONG CASE FOR INDUSTRIAL POLICY (IN THEORY)

Making a case for the industrial policy is too easy. According to development economists, market imperfections over which industrial policy related theoretical arguments are exist, however, they are usually pervasive (Massi, & Nem, 2018). Both asymmetric information and collateral constraints collectively result in incomplete insurance and credit-market imperfections (Massi & Nem, 2018). Failure in monitoring efforts leads to generate less efficient labour-market arrangements. For example, learning spread out from the producers who have adopted new procedures (Chen, 2016). Labour can switch from one employer to other, taking with them their “on the job training”. The projects that are lumpy as compared to economy size require coordination etc. the researchers investigate the developing countries` performance by using “new” growth theory which is based on the externalities in new-product creation and in knowledge (RodriguezClare & Klenow, 2005). Contemporary development theory, on other hand, is based on the concept that performance of markets in developing economies remains poor.

Many studies have discussed market imperfections from different perspectives, particularly in context of development countries. For example, Foster and Rosenzweig (1995), through a classic study, provide insights into impact of learning by spill over and by doing on adoption pattern of high yielding varieties in agriculture of India. Moreover, Tolysbayev, et al., (2015) conducted a comprehensive analysis of how incomplete risk market and costly monitoring shape land leasing contracts and the subsequent consequences in different agricultural settings. Similarly, Pingkuo, & Yi, (2019) summarised different financial-market imperfections, particularly those which have increased the expansion of such microfinance arrangements, not relying on the collateral. By studying Indian caste culture, Munshi and Rosenzweig (2003) investigated how such additional-market social arrangements shape and constraint labour market operation. Moreover, Singh, A. (2011) studied the agricultural system and documented how bargaining and unequal power in household adversely affect the efficiency of allocated resources and labour

decisions in agriculture of Africa. By summarising large number of studies, Yean, & Heng, (2011) showed that different borrowers paid largely different interest rates. They concluded that only credit-markets imperfections can explain such huge variations in Malaysia. Cornick, (2014) looked at Japanese multinationals` location decisions in U.S and provided an evidence of the spill overs that are related to geographical agglomeration.

Instead of viewing market imperfections as an isolated instance, they should be seen as parcel and part of what they mean to be immature and as a reason why economy does not develop automatically (Morales, 2013). Fundamentally, development means structural change that involves producing new goods by using new technologies as well as to allocate the resources to new activities instead of traditional ones. The classical 2-sector development model is based on this concept (Whitfield, & Buur, 2014). Moreover, Morales, (2013) have recently documented this strong empirical fact in their work. In this way, structural change refers to a process that provides a fertile land for countless market shortcomings as listed above. Investing in new markets requires finance; however, absence of track record makes new industries excessively risky for private lenders (Haller, 2014). For this purpose, complementary inputs and services are required that are not likely to exist due to absence of substantial operational scale of an activity (Weiss, 2018). This needs training managers and workers, who are free to move to copycats and competitors. This leads to generate learning by doing that is beneficial for others. The deck under these circumstances tends to stack against those entrepreneurs who want to diversify in non-traditional domains (Kattel, & Lember, 2010). The reason why poor countries always remain poor is that markets of such countries do not perform as much as they can to promote the needed structural transformation (Naqvi, 2018).

This fact could not be denied that institutional shortcomings and government failures in enforcing contracts and defending the property rights are also a basic stumbling block. They may sometime act as major constraints for economic growth (Intarakumnerd, 2016). Regardless of all above listed reasons, development requires a perfect night watchman. Through literature review on development, we can have good empirical and conceptual reasons why marker imperfections act as constraints for full appropriation of private social returns in such growth supporting investments (Danhui, 2014). Even if institutions are quite decent, the problem will remain same.

Moreover, “Good governance” refers to the ability of generating and implementing policy initiatives require to minimise the effects of market shortcomings and imperfections (Danhui, 2014). The developing countries like China, Taiwan and South Korea did not make their institutions suddenly perfect, but gradually developed through the implementation of policies to cope with market hindrances that their investors encountered in new tradable industries (Danhui, 2014).

Kormishkina, & Koloskov, (2017) highlighted two kinds of explanations. Firstly, tradable are very special as they bear disproportionately from market imperfections; resultantly economic diversification and structural transformation get blocked. I have discussed these market imperfections earlier, here I added the presumption that these are predominate in the tradable. Secondly, speciality of tradable is mainly because, contrary to tradable, they bear disproportionately from contracting incompleteness and institutional weakness characterised by low-income environment (Kormishkina, & Koloskov, 2017). For both explanations, there is certain evidence, but this does not matter that which among both is dominant over other. Whatever the case, there is secondary role for the subsidizing tradable (Cornick, 2014). As currency undervaluation performs subsidization function therefore it works well. Tradable economic practices, regardless of the market failures, are scalable as small economies tend to expand their output without diminishing returns (contrasting to domestic services). We can say that currency undervaluation is similar to industrial policy, i.e., favouring some sectors than other (Barnes, et al., 2017).

Based on this discussion I can shed the light on another misunderstanding. Industrial policy sceptics, in reaction to above listed market failures, often realise that policy intervention should be there, but highlight those horizontal policies are needed instead of preferential policies that discriminate the activities. Learning spill overs, human-capital externalities and financial market failures are perfect remedies, uniform measures directly targeting the education, R&D and financial markets remove the counter arguments (Gulin, & Ermolov, 2015). However, horizontal interventions should be considered for limited cases without thinking it as definite alternative of vertical policies. Practically, most interventions (both horizontal and vertical) favour few activities and not others (Lester, et al., 2013). For instance, the policies that tend to improve financial intermediations through conventional banks partially target the enterprises in formal sectors having access to outer finance, while

discriminate against informal and small enterprises (Maskus, et al., 2013). On other hand, the pollicise targeting the microfinance have entirely opposite effect. Moreover, accelerated depreciation not only facilitates capital-intensive activities but also discriminate against the labour-intensive activities (Weiss, 2018). Intellectual-property protection and R&D subsidies helps the firms in undertaking patentable innovations, however, not support the firms that produce “cost-discovery” externalities (knowing what could be profitably manufactured at home) (Morris, et al., 2012). Exchange-rate policies – typical horizontal policies – support tradable activities but at expense of the non-tradable activities. Therefore, policy makers should not ignore the asymmetric impacts of horizontal interventions and should ensure that they ultimately favour the activities that suffer disproportionately from market failures in question (Thrasher, 2013).

We highlighted the point in Hausmann and Rodrik (2006) that public inputs –highly required by producers- are specific to activities in question. Only few interventions are truly “horizontal” where set of specific inputs are required to produce particular good/service. Here specificity means that if these specific inputs are deployed to another activity, they would be less productive (Thrasher, 2013). Thus, to what extent an input is specific can be measured by the degree to which an input will be less productive in alternative use (Duman, & Kureková, 2012). The examples of these inputs are machinery and physical installation, set of particular intermediate inputs, employees with specific skills, logistic system for delivering the outputs and transporting the inputs, marketing and procurement system for obtaining information about customers and suppliers, systems of contracts and property rights that is legitimate and respectable in front of society, set of regulatory rules and standards on labour norms, product characteristics, consumer protection and financial rights that influence other stakeholders` behaviour and so on. These requirements or inputs are developed with intention to solve the requirements of those activities that already exist but are not supportive for the potential activities (not yet exist) (Hausmann and Rodrik 2006).

Often, the governments through their acts show that they cognize the particularity of public inputs and private needs, even while maintaining the novelty that they are not engaged in industrial policies. Many countries of Latin America, for example, officially detached from industrial policy in 1980s to 1990s while reorienting their economic

strategies. Still, their policies for export processing zone and direct foreign investments focused on providing public inputs for these activities instead of focusing on “across board” policies (Rodrik 2004). Therefore, tax incentives were offered to foreign investors so that they can overcome their inadequate familiarity with the host countries, get navigation through local rules and regulations, subsidies for their training employees, sites with committed infrastructure and protection against weak local legal regime (Nahtigal, 2014). Good infrastructure, fast-track custom processes, flexible labour activities and cheap inputs are basic requirements of the firms operating in the export processing areas. Whatever the case, governments are actively engaged in industrial policies by providing specific public inputs that benefited specific economic actors (Weiss, 2018).

2.10 INDUSTRIAL POLICY INDICATORS

This study includes only that policy data which covers maximum aspects of the industrial policy. However, this goal is challenging due to many reasons. Firstly, there are insufficient indicators of industrial policies (Vries, 2008). That is why, many authors have analysed the industrial policy with restriction to just one dimension. For example, they empirically analysed either the effect of policy subsidies, tax regulations or competition policy. For instance, Rodrik (2008) used the data on State aid that was reported to European Commission by EU members, to measure and analyse the industrial policy. Secondly, as measures and definition of industrial policies are industry and country specific therefore it does not contain data on cross-country comparison. Khan (2010), for example, observed differences in measures of the subsidies across OECD. Khan (2008) argued that in both developed and developing countries, the analysis framework for the industrial policy should be broad so that it can capture the effects of policies targeting different stages of industrial development, vertical and horizontal policy, policies targeting different sized firms, policies that stimulate industrial upgrading and policies with focus on structural change (Honeyman, & Goose, 2016). These challenges clearly depict why there is no empirical evidence regarding the impact of different aspects of industrial policy overgrowth (Loadman, & James, 2010). The below given table has been constructed based on the details of variables regarding the industrial policy with the help of collecting data from previous relevant studies (Tutino, & John., 2016; Dr Paul & Govekar., 2007; Thomas, 1993; Steedman, 2007; Szostak, 2014; Betts, 2007; Walt,

& Martin, 2014; Dutta, 2006). These industrial variables are directly or indirectly influencing the production, growth, import, and export of textile sector therefore it is very important to considered and understand the meanings of these industrial variables.

Table 2.2 Industrial policy variables from WCY (1995-2011)

Variables	Industrial policy variables from WCY (1995-2011)
Exchange	Exchange rates support the competitiveness of enterprises (1997-2011)
Research	Laws relating to scientific research do encourage innovation (2004-2011)
Regulation:	Technological regulation supports business development and innovation (2005-2011)
Funding:	Funding for technological development is readily available (1995-2011)
Ventures:	Public and private sector ventures are supporting technological development (2007-2011)
Legal:	Development and application of technology are supported by the legal environment (1997-2011)
Labour:	Labour regulations (hiring/firing practices, minimum wages, etc.) do not hinder business activities (1995-2011)
Creation:	Creation of firms is supported by legislation (2002-2011)
Ease:	Ease of doing business is supported by regulations (2003-2011)
Framework :	The legal and regulatory framework encourages the competitiveness of enterprises (1997-2011)
Tax:	Real corporate taxes do not discourage entrepreneurial activity (1997-2011) Environment: Environmental laws and compliance do not hinder the competitiveness of businesses (1995-2011)
Immigration:	Immigration laws do not prevent your company from employing foreign labor (1995-2011)
Competition:	Competition legislation is efficient in preventing unfair competition (1995-2011)
Ownership:	State ownership of enterprises is not a threat to business activities (2007-2011)
Subsidies:	Subsidies do not distort fair competition and economic development

	(2003-2011)
Incentive:	Investment incentives are attractive to foreign investors (2007-2011)
Market:	Capital markets (foreign and domestic) are easily accessible (2004-2011)
Investor:	Foreign investors are free to acquire control in domestic companies (1995-2011)
Contract:	Public sector contracts are sufficiently open to foreign bidders (1995-2011)
Protection:	Protectionism does not impair the conduct of your business (1995-2011)
Customs:	Customs' authorities do facilitate the efficient transit of goods (1997-2011)

Source: (Tutino, & John., 2016; Dr Paul & Govekar., 2007; Thomas, 1993; Steedman, 2007; Szostak, 2014; Betts, 2007; Walt, & Martin, 2014; Dutta, 2006)

2.11 THE CLIMB, FALL AND AGAIN CLIMB OF THE INDUSTRIAL POLICY

Naturally, economics is subjected to trends and fashions. Thus, is the current attention to re-emergence of industrial policy only a passing trend that would likely be faded away soon? This is the conclusion of recently published article in “The Economist Bemoaning” with title “The return to a misguided ideology of “picking winners”. If literature on industrial policy is reviewed, it would be revealed that industrial policy has never moved out but persist under different guises and names and has been equally applied in developing as well as developed countries, even with the opposite flow of currently appeared strong ideologies (Dr Paul & Govekar., 2007).

Since long, the era after II-World War was assumed as “golden period” of the industrial policy because governments of developed countries mutually agreed that coordinated and balanced expansion, increased technological progress, appropriately developed multilateral arrangements both in finance and trade and accelerated provisioning of public goods/services offered best possible ways to ensure better living standards along with prevention of destruction and return to waste of inter-war period (Szostak, 1991). To attain these objectives, broader policy toolbox was embraced at large scale so that multilateral steady trade liberalization coexisted with relatively strong capital controls, and dynamic demand management with indicative planning and industrial policies (Thomas, 1993). Resultantly, unprecedented growth was observed in the developed nations due to accelerated

technological progress and high investment rates, often associated with active export demand but underpinned by rising wages and full employment (Steedman, 2007).

As a result of this broader policy consensus, a relatively favourable environment was cultivated for development and growth in poor economies, allowing them sufficient policy space to practice “big-push” strategies in multilateral trading framework with combination of high industrial development, strong capital formation and shift of economy from rural economic momentum to more urban (Szostak, 2014). These elements together accelerated the growth throughout developing world in combination with committed support measures that were employed to increase technological capabilities, maximise agricultural output (with strong check on food prices) and to bolster financing arrangements (i.e. by creating national development bank (s)) (Betts, 2007). These strategies were export-oriented in East-Asian “tigers” while other countries such as South Asia and Latin America prioritised regionally integrate or domestic markets for growth (Walt, & Martin, 2014).

Technology, trade, and industrial policies were those economic development policies that provided compulsion and incentives to enable the domestic enterprises to accelerate their learning and translate the rents into productive growth (Amsden, 2001). Since last 5 decades, an uneven growth in the industrial development has been observed, however it can be concluded that achievements due to these initial strategies were relatively significant, despite of limitations and flaws.

Strongly accepted by majority of economic professions, overwhelming evidence, and better understanding result in renewal of the interest within industrial policy (Walt, & Martin, 2014). Developed East Asian states had successfully implemented the industrial policies for rapid absorption of technology, knowledge, and know-how from other countries, to understand them at broad space and diversify them into more sophisticated new products (Harrison and Rodriguez-Clare, 2009; Lin, 2009; Rodrik, 2007). World Bank launched “Commission on Growth and Development” in 2006, which was a significant step towards reconsideration of the industrial policies. Based on its work, Commission on Growth and Development concluded that economist have insufficient knowledge about growth process, particularly in context of relationship between training, technologies, and education, and in terms of growth. According to Costa, et al., (2010), the growth economists may explicitly concern

wrong model. They also argued that one policy may not necessarily work well in all countries because every country is different from other in terms of capabilities and institutions. Therefore, it is suggested to countries to make experiments and learn from mistakes so that increased returns and comparative advantage can be created (Daddi, et al., 2016).

According to World Bank, 2012 cited in Gershman, & Thurner, (2018), “the role of industrial policy and export promotion” is controversial, though important component of this country-specific approach. World Development Report 2013 subsequently discussed “targeted investment climate” and provided the justification towards the selection of productive transformation strategy (World Bank, 2012 cited in Gershman, & Thurner, 2018). Moreover, the renewed interest in industrial policy emerges from increasing realization that shifting towards liberal policy system had brought little upgrading and diversification in economic activity than what “structural adjustment” initially had promised. The controversial changes required in productive structures in order to sustain job creation and future growth (van der et al., 2017).

Moreover, the global financial crisis of 2007-2008 also plays an important role in re-emergence of the industrial policy (Zacharias, & Ma, 2015). This crisis reminded that weak states and unregulated markets provide inefficient institutional environment to manage societies and economies. It importantly shifts the interest towards more inclusive and sustainable strategies, particularly in developed countries, with inclusion of possible role of industrial policy to develop green economy and infrastructures and to address undue hollowing in skills and manufacturing (Inwood, & Keay, 2013).

However, industry policy became disrepute amongst economists during 1980s to 1990s, but still many countries continuously used it under different names, even when some of the economic professions rejected this reality (Park, et al., 2016). Now looking again at these decades, it is revealed that the countries that disobeyed the traditional wisdom and undertook heterodox policy package obtained better economic performance as compared to those countries that had fully embraced conventional policy package that leads to macroeconomic volatility and de-industrialization (Froy, 2013). Based on this and some other relevant evidence, policymakers and economists are shifting away their focus from whether to embrace

the industrial policy or not towards the scope and objectives of the industrial policy along with focus on “how to do it” appropriately in every condition (Inwood, & Keay, 2013). Next section contains the overview of different frameworks used to address productive transformation issues, with aim to practically develop a good policy with maximum avoidance of past mistakes (Caloffi, 2017). The figure 2-6 depicts the actual position of Pakistani exports after 2002 which is continuously declining compared to India. There are many causes behind it such as terrorist attack, energy crises, lack of international investor interest, and political corruption which negatively influence the overall production of textile and other sectors therefore the percentage of exports decreased after 2002 to date. The present study aims to explore causes of textile sector decline which also determines why the exports of textile industry is decreased after 2002. Therefore, these factors will be given the overview that which policies should be developed to improve the exports of textile and other sectors.

Figure 2.8 The world bank (Exports of goods and services (% of GDP) - India, Pakistan

2.12 ECONOMIC FRAMEWORKS AND MODELS FOR THE PRODUCTIVE TRANSFORMATION STRATEGIES

The current discussions on industrial policy and productive transformation have been renewed and reshaped by the addition of various economic traditions. This paper recognizes what innovative approaches have contributed to development economics

(Natsuda, & Thoburn, 2018). First part comprises of most of recently developed conceptual and interesting frameworks and approaches that have been drawn on evolutionary, institutional, neoclassical, and structural traditions (Lauridsen, 2018). By highlighting different objectives and perspectives, these frameworks and approaches suggest different dimensions and components of the structural transformation strategies and policies. They also provide important policy principles and distinct insights that help policy makers to perfectly design the industrial policies (Mazzucato, & Penna, 2016).

In the next part, researcher presents distinct perspectives and frameworks that are different in analysis in terms of scope and rationale of the industrial policies. However, they show convergence on idea that the governments should be proactive in shaping, orienting, and facilitating industrial development process. Moreover, catch-up process should be relevant with challenges that contemporary economies are facing. These frameworks are viewed as complementary approaches and tools while developing region-specific productive transformation strategies and catching-up policies. While viewing together, they provide deeper insights into dynamics of productive transformation strategies and of the catching-up process. Resultantly they contribute to design best policy in both developed and developing countries.

2.12.1 Managing the productive industrial transformation: A structuralise macroeconomic policy frame

According to structuralist economics, changes in economic activity act as major driver of employment and growth. Literature on this tradition focuses on investigating this relationship by undertaking holistic approach with considerations of trade, technology, sectoral and macroeconomic policies (Natsuda,& Thoburn, 2013). Structuralist approach plays an important role in poverty reduction and promoting employment and growth. The policies that aim to facilitate dynamic reformation and restructuring of trade and production argue that “growth can only address poverty concerns if it generates new jobs to keep pace with a rising labour force” (Ocampo, Rada and Taylor, 2009, p. 1). Thus, diversification across and within sectors is main driver of employment and income growth for low-income countries (Imbs and Wacziarg, 2003; UNCTAD, 1964).

According to Ocampo “the strategy of industrialization and export promotion advocated by ECLAC was also tied in with short-term macroeconomic policy because of the institution’s obsession with maintaining competitive exchange rates, which were viewed as an essential ingredient of proactive policies to foster production sector diversification” (Rodrik et al., 2004). A recent research has justified the ECLAC’s “obsession” to maintain competitive exchange rate by proving that real exchange rates act as main determinant of the economic growth. In 1970s, Southern Cone countries` experience showed that when move towards the liberalize trade is combined with opening balance of capital account; it may lead to non-occurrence of possible real depreciation (Blackie, & Turner, 2018). However, this combination may also yield totally opposite outcome: real appreciation that may be disincentive for industrialization and exports. For productive transformation strategies, it is important to wisely manage exchange rate across entire business cycle. Ocampo used this analysis to recommend a development and growth strategy that couple countercyclical macroeconomic policy together with proactive strategies for the diversification of production structure, with major priority giving to industrialization.

2.12.2 Following (latent) comparative advantages: A new approach to facilitate growth

Commission on Growth and Development, 2008 reported the limitations in neoclassical economic approaches in saying what they can state about development and growth and the policies to manage all these processes (Beekmans, et al., 2016). The traditional trade and growth models that are developed under neoclassical models describe growth in context of accumulated production factors, particularly human and physical capital, as well as technology (Behuria, 2019). According to Gereffi, (2014) a country should specialize in those products that give comparative advantages to the country, and policy discussion should largely focus on the “residual” derives from exercises created by this approach (Ovadia, & Wolf, 2018). Market failures clearly justified the state intervention in sense that neoclassical economic wisdom must document government failures (Getahun, & Villanger, 2019). It argues that factors like incompetent or myopic bureaucracies and corruption by private sectors increase the probability of government failures more than probability of the market failures (Bae, & Mah, 2019). Basing on “perfectly competitive norm” and unnecessarily polarized policy debate on “market failure” vs. “government

failure”, this approach is greatly damaging the development policy through prevention of rich analysis about how different learning processes and institutions can stall or promote structural transformation in historical circumstances and specific set of early conditions (Barkley, & Dudensing, 2011). Contrary to such nuanced enquiry, traditional policy view under this tradition promotes unduly simplistic worldwide policy rules like “get the government out of the way” or “get prices right” (Choi, et al., 2011).

Role of governance and institutions has been clearly highlighted by latest approaches in neoclassical framework (Choi, et al., 2010). These variables have not yet been integrated well into frameworks and models, resultantly they have significantly low power to provide policy recommendations regarding to strengthen the relationship of these variables with growth (Colette., 2015). By adopting GIF “Growth Identification and Facilitation” approach; Justin Lin and Volker Treichel addressed this shortcoming and suggested 6-steps methodology for identification and targeting the sectors for government support and investment in region-specific context (Pansuwan, & Routray, 2011). According to this approach, State should proactively overcome coordination, externality and information issues that are inherent in newly developed sectors and activities (Lin, 2017). However, this approach argues that failure of previous industrial policy was mainly because these efforts were made based on strategy that disobeyed the comparative advantage concept (Lin, 2017). Instead of this, it recommends that industrial policies should be developed with focus mainly on industries and economic activities and they should also obey some rules: i.e. focusing on those goods/services that have shown dynamic growth for about 2 decades in fast growing economies with same endowment structures where per capita GDP is about two times high (comparator economies), among such goods/services prioritize those in which private domestic enterprises have already penetrated spontaneously (Heide, et al., 2013). However, efforts of productive transformation beyond the “latent” boundaries of comparative advantages encounter failure and slow down the economic performance (Thoburn, & Natsuda, 2018).

Being a practical-oriented approach, it has clear applications. After assessing this approach, Chang agrees with its statement that higher deviation from comparative

advantage makes the industrial policy riskier (Kim, C., & Hong, M. (2010). However, this approach cannot recognize that these risks have been already taken by many countries while industrial policies of these countries have shown high deviation from “comparative advantage”: “many success stories were based on moves that were far more daring than what their rule would suggest” (Chang, 2013, 41). As this approach has emphasised more on the comparative advantages thus has not considered dynamics of learning, capabilities, and technological upgrading. Through consideration of these aspects require to consult evolutionary economics (Feser, 2014).

2.13 INNOVATION, TECHNOLOGY AND LEARNING

Many studies have tried to address the question, how to create and accelerate the innovation and learning and how capabilities can play a significant role in structural transformation (Hansen, et al., 2018). The focuses of evolutionary economics include dynamics of analyses learning and economic development, accumulated domestic capabilities and technological change as main drivers of structural transformation (Bogliacino, 2012). That is why evolutionary economics is considered as non-linear, incremental, and complex process. According to economists, comparative advantage is “made” rather than “given”, and developmental states tend to design such institutions and policies that are supportive for learning processes (Haeri, & Arabmazar, 2019). Economists called those economies as high-performance economies that have deliberately moved away their productive structure from “lower-quality activities”, that are characterized by flat learning, diminishing returns, low wages and low productivity, to “higher-quality activities”, that are characterized by high growth rate of output, high wages, rapid productivity growth, high technological progress and sharp learning curves (Liang, et al., 2016).

By expanding “infant industry” related arguments to case study of infant economy, Greenwald, and Stiglitz (2013; 2014) discussed how well-designed policies on intellectual property, industry and trade are helpful in developing learning societies. They argued that “creating a learning society is more likely to increase standards of living than the small, one-time improvements in economic efficiency or those that derive from sacrifices of consumption today to deepen capital” (Greenwald and Stiglitz, 2013, p. 45). Moreover, their approach for learning, technology upgrading,

and knowledge is originated from neoclassical tradition. They develop this approach based on analysis of market failures due to production and distribution of knowledge and information and of market failures due to innovation and distribution of finance knowledge (Lauridsen, 2010). They emphasize more on understanding learning structure of an economy- particularly how to spread it across sectors. Such understanding leads to finally conclude the important policies about how to encourage exports, manufacturing, and other sectors to ensure fast productivity growth and accelerated learning (Martin, & Martin, 2017).

Mazzucato (2013) has recently overviewed how State can play an important role in technological capabilities development for the “innovation-led growth” in middle-income and developed countries. Based on evidence, she argued that primary entrepreneurial drives and consequent risk taking that lie behind development of modern technologies (such as wind and solar energy, GPS, voice-recognition software, touch-screen devices, and Internet) has provided less as compared to what overestimated venture capital and private sector has suggested, but more than what State has acknowledged. Germuska, (2013) argued that public policies of many countries, of US, have played very important in development of these innovations as well as other relevant capabilities when the risk was at peak.

Both in political arena and literature, there are vivid debates on industrial policies and each debate express radically diverging view (Avis, 2018). According to traditional liberal approach, liberalize is most appropriate policy for every country and is best in all conditions because dynamics of free markets allow the countries to discover their comparative advantages (Antoniuk et al., 2017). This rationale primarily based on the assumption that product markets correctly direct the investments regarding to which actor it should respond (Pearson, & Foxon, 2012). It is prime responsibility of government to ensure the availability of stable and constant macroeconomic environment (Rodrik et al., 2004), where rules of game are clearly defined with provision of basic human goods. Without any intervention, it would alter already allocation of necessary resources (LI Guoping et al., 2017). This approach generally overlooks market failures which is its major drawback (Barca, 2011), because it centrally influences growth of income and productivity in long run, particularly in

domain of innovation and knowledge (Hall and Jones, 1999, Griliches, 1979 cited Mann, 2018).

Literature on the technological capabilities considers technological change most crucial for economic development of emerging countries but market failures usually hindered this development process (Howe, 2016; Etzkowitz, & Viale, 2010). This approach argues that industrial success of a country heavily depends on its capacity to embrace and become expert in existing technologies, though not come closer to technological frontier (Bogart, 2011). Market failures make it impossible for technology to be freely available; also, it cannot be wrapped up without risks or costs. Thus, it is most important for organizations to make purposive and conscious efforts to build technological capabilities and invest in technological based learning processes (MacNeil, 2013; Prisecaru, 2017; Sharp, & Weisdorf, 2012).

This approach of technological capability provides a solid platform to government to justify policy actions in selective and functional manner see figure above (Sharp, & Weisdorf, 2012). However, selectivity is most important because offering equal support to entire industrial sector could be expensive and also could be not effective due to technologically differ learning processes (Lall, 2004). Moreover, some activities require little support and protection if information is freely available and learning process is comparatively brief. On other hand, complex activities involve high externalities and entry costs, and newcomers cannot enter until they are incentivized through specific policies (Sommer, 2015). However, market failures could not establish case for the intervention alone. Interventions are risky and costly thus require a vigilant assessment of long-term effects benefits and costs (Majerowicz, & Medeiros, 2018). This capacity development and policy learning process is an essential process both for TF practices and industrial strategy and successfully worked in experiences of East Asian countries (Helmedag, 2019; Morris, 2010), see figure 2.7 industrial policies toward capacity development and policy learning. This figures 2.7 provides understanding that capacity development and policy learning process requires communication between firms and government along with experimentation and mutual learning in institutionalized process that is also required in the context to bring transformation in textile industry of Pakistan.

Figure 2.7 Industrial policies toward capacity development and policy learning

2.14 TECHNOLOGY FORESIGHT (TF) AND INDUSTRIAL POLICIES

TF (Technology Foresight) is systematic exercise that aims to look into long future of innovation and science technology so that well-informed policy decisions could be made (Irvine and Martin, 1984). TF was initially incepted in Japan and since its inception it has helped economies and societies in defining strategic domains where long-term future of technology and science would lead (Barker, & Ishizu, 2012). Over last few decades, many giant companies, developed countries, developing regions and other organizations have adopted TF practices at large scale (Reischauer,

2018). Here the question arises whether TF practices really help the developing countries to be advance one? In fact, it is hard for developing countries to get closer to developed countries due to lesser technological development and inadequacy of resources (Kappeler, 2017). In this regard, TF and industrial strategies are crucially important because both pursue same purpose that not only needs to be aligned with but also help strengthen NIS (National Innovation System) (Ooi, et al., 2017). TF thus, needs to move far away from just pursuing supposition of where future will probably go and should focus on fostering the efforts to make stakeholders` interests consistent with commonly agreed future vision (Liu, 2018).

2.14.1 What is technology foresight?

Rapid technological change has tremendous contribution in current economic development due to bringing about unprecedented productivity growth (Yao, & Lin, 2016). Resultantly, trade and industrial structure has become more reshaped due to addition of various sets of complex activities which ultimately results in horizontal and vertical fragmentation in value chain at global level, with space for foreign buyers and outsourcing by MNCs (multinational companies) that not only drive the development process but also ensure internal coherence of the process (Baldwin, 2011; Nuvolari, 2018). Consequently, a window of new opportunities gets open for developing countries in form of various strategic investments to get closer to developed and technological advance countries (Nuvolari, 2018).

TF practices have capacity to overcome these emerging complexities because TF systematically embodies the programs that help to study priorities and innovation plans to foresee, direct and shape potential future technological changes (Maw et al., 2012). For this purpose, it involves active participation of different actors like civil society, industry, experts and government that collectively define a common vision of potential future (Miles, 2010). Experts from private sector and science/academia play very crucial role among all TF participants because they better understand technological issues from policy maker perspectives and thus help to minimize the uncertainty associated with unprecedented technological changes (Schäfer, 2018). The purpose lies behind these TF exercises is that overall positive games with expected, and more effective outcomes can be generated particularly with respect to effective technological advancement and more sustainable socio-economic benefits

which is not possible by isolated initiatives each actor individually take (Jacobi, & Andersen, 2016).

Existing literature on TF refers it an exercise composed of variety of different activities such as anticipation, systematically looking forward, looking ahead activities, forecasting, technology road-mapping, prognostic amongst others, futures research, and strategic intelligence (Miles, 2010 and Phaal et al. 2004). In 1970s, Japan – the country where TF was initially incepted – used to entitle its national technological planning studies as “forecast activity” that was initially performing as “technology foresight” in very refined manner (Miles, 2010). Later, in mid of 1980s, Irvine and Martin (1984) presented their seminal work that immensely inspired old Japanese traditions in TF and S&T, based on which these “forecasting” practices are nowadays called as “foresight” activities. However, this difference is unimportant. Typically, close circles of various experts perform forecasting activities and predict future contingencies on basis of deterministic precision (Chia, et al., 2019). Resultantly, their outcomes represent a common vision of entire world with specific point of the view. TF, on other pole, reflects broader vision of entire world with strategically integration in policy strategies. The resultant outcomes represent insights for future oriented S&T policies, which not “predict” but “create” the future (Miles, 2010) with intense focus on learning process (van Dijk, 1991) and dialog amongst various actors and disciplines (Elzinga, 1983).

Moreover, seminal work of Irvine and Martin (1984) enables us to define and understand TF as it is conceived today and encourages the world to proliferate the TF exercises. Following Japan, France took initiative to exercise “foresight” activities in 1980s and after France, Sweden, Canada, and Australia started these initiatives (UNIDO, 2005). TF, however, gained momentum during 1990s and got expended in UK, US, Germany, and Netherlands. While one country was performing foresight activities, other countries planned to engage in same activities to be competitive (UNIDO, 2005). In fact, TF was highly appreciated as most valuable tool for identifying market oriented, forward looking, and fast innovation policies mutually agreed by private sector and government. Recently, developing countries have widely embraced foresight activities as strategic tool so that they can get closer to technological frontier (Rothkopf, 2012). It is generally assumed that cutting edge

technologies are only considered for industrialised countries which is now has been overcome. This narrow indication is often discussed in literature as “leap-frogging” (Helmedag, 2019).

The most prominent characteristics of TF include (1) due to its future predicting capability, TF influences technology direction to “make the future happen” (Miles, 2010). Due to having strong legitimacy and encouraging participatory approach which helps to build consensus, TF has potential to increase accountability, awareness, predictability of probable technological advancement, transparency and provide responsibility and ownership (Elzinga, 1983); (2) through participatory approach, TF ensures the involvement of various actors who may help in expanding possible range of potential strategies instead inclusion of single actor`s narrow interest (Barker, & Ishizu, 2012). Moreover, TF significantly facilitates the stakeholders to make strategic decisions, particularly buy or make new technologies by considering organization and local knowledge endowment (Lall, 2004). (3) There are various levels at which TF can pursue such as national, supranational, regional, local and organizational (Hollingsworth, 2012). At all levels, TF aims to manage socio-economic and demographic heterogeneity; the actors generally face during analysis process. (4) As TF tries to reorient and link innovation and science at regional and national level, that is why it is inherently connected with NIS (Reischauer, 2018). By “wiring up” network among governmental bodies, universities, society and industries at large scale, TF is trying to foster the overall impact of economy (Martin and Johnston, 1999, and Andersen and Andersen, 2014; Ooi, et al., 2018). TF exercises also attempts to address many failures that are intrinsic to S&T policies and innovation activities. For example, see figure 2.8:

Coordination failures:	Different views hold by NIS stakeholders about the value of S&T may lead to create coordination failure among them. Thus it is very crucial to balance such interest so that bounded rationality and rent-seeking behaviours could be wiped out (Liu, 2018).
Market failures:	Usually long-term investments are involved in S&T programs that are weighed against possible short-term temporary losses (Crafts, 2015).
Communication failures:	When actors from different disciplines (particularly who are specialised in various types of communication and subject languages) with diverging interests are called together to define common vision, it generally leads to create communication failure (Aguilera, et al., 2014).
Political failures:	Governments need to adopt long-term perspectives with respect to innovation that should not be coincided with political perspectives that are to maximise consensus on short-term temporary political interest regarding upcoming election which is generally termed as "dynamic inconsistency" (Yao, & Lin, 2016).

Figure 2.8 Different types of industrial related failure

2.14.2 How is technology foresight related to industrial strategy?

Due to globalization, services and manufacturing become more complex, completion becomes stronger and fast technological changes have totally transformed economic activities of developing countries (Pietrobelli, & Puppato, 2016). Moreover, production has been internationally organized and fragmented along GVCs. Though, advance technology and massive knowledge is extensively available but there is needed to fully exploit and employ them in coherent business strategies (Vecchiato, & Roveda, 2010). Learn and be specialised in technology has become important paradigm and it is necessary for developing countries to identify potential opportunities for productive and technological specialization to not only catch up but also forge ahead (Vecchiato, & Roveda, 2010). Thus, isolated response of individual actor cannot tackle these complexities, also cannot guarantee that economies catch-up and develop (Featherston, & O'Sullivan, 2017). As interdependencies are emerging from competitive setting at global level, therefore it becomes important to

develop and implement appropriate strategy so that responses from private sector, research organizations and government can be orchestrated (Crews, 2019).

Sometimes, TF exercises do not comply with concrete identification as well as designed policy strategy in terms of promoting catch up. In this report, we develop a central argument that is “TF practices should be consistent with business development strategies (Cespedes et al., 2017) because both pursue same objective to develop industries through technological catch up (Choi, et al., 2014). Researchers give a brief introduction in next section regarding how the idea of business strategy was initially conceptualised and has evolved with passage of time and why it is important for industrial strategy to consider role of the innovation, emergence of the GVCs and recent changes in industrial sector that would increase the researcher understanding to propose a better strategy for the textile industry of Pakistan.

2.14.3 Lessons from the East-Asian “tigers”

Experiences of East Asian economies (such as Singapore, Taiwan, South Korea, and Hong Kong) are good examples of how a good industrial strategy in consistent with TF framework promotes fast technological development and industrialization. Though Asian Tigers have not followed same development approach but (Lall, 1996) has identified some major characteristics of their applied industrial strategy. Firstly, horizontal, and selective policies have simultaneously and interchangeably been used in these countries (except Hong Kong). All countries, for example, have been invested to develop advance technical skills of human being with selective support to some sectors such as innovation, protection of local market and export subsidies. Secondly, they actively pursue capability development in long-term frame (Lall, 1996). Thirdly, each country used FDI in different manner. These countries favoured indigenous firms over foreign companies as they wanted to promote capability development at local level, directed their practices to exploit magical effects and restricted the overseas entry (Featherston, & O’Sullivan, 2016). The countries that rely on multinational companies to promote the technological development generally target the international investors to be engaged in technology intensive and more complex functions (Singapore and Hong Kong) (Linstone, 2011). There are some principles that guide how to successfully implement these policies. Asian Tigers constantly select and target those activities that offer better technological benefits,

linkages and learning opportunities (Paliokaitė, et al., 2015). To foster learning processes, these countries have made heavy investment to generate skills through infrastructures and education. Moreover, extending learning to strategy designing and implementation not only facilitates to learn lessons from previous mistakes but also helps to improve them (Vishnevskiy, et al., 2017). This kind of flexibility in decision making and the policy learning systematically allowed private institutions – with active participation of public sector – to cover the gaps in risky areas (Shah, et al., 2013). Fourthly, these countries have constantly used exports as a tool to early enter in global markets (Amankwah 2016).

2.14.4 Change in industrial policies

In early 1990s, globalization and technology both forces have geographically fragmented the industries by adding values in many countries and improved functional incorporation of these practices. Currently, this process is called as “Global Value Chains”. Nowadays, all productions are completed in more than one country (Gereffi and Sturgeon, 2013, Milberg and Winkler, 2013). Moreover, in 2009 the global exports of the intermediate goods exceeded collective export value of final goods and capital (WTO and IDE-JETRO, 2011:81).

However, these developments present some opportunities and some challenges for governments and firms of developing countries (Francisco et al., 2013). Regardless of presence of some potential barriers in certain value chains and markets, it is empirically evident that interaction between local suppliers and global actors can be stream of learning experiences and knowledge that may foster capability acquisition and learning process and inspired other companies not involved in this value chain (Pietrobelli and Rabellotti, 2008). It does not mean that initial interaction between global buyer and local supplier is enough. Minimum accumulation of previous skills is required for local supplier to get engaged in contract with global actor (Morrison et al., 2008). For example, there are some contracts that were terminated due to inability of supplier to improve his capabilities to initially expected levels. For this purpose, many countries have formulated different programs with major focus on their local firms to become supplier of global actors. This new setting is of great importance for both TF exercises and industrial policy (Gereffi and Sturgeon, 2013; Pietrobelli et al., 2016; Vecchiato, 2015). Thus, only finding competitive advantage of a country is not as much important as tailoring it in accordance with requirements of

GVCs is important. Defining multifaceted programs and policies in consistent with requirements of GVC organizations is a challenging task and needs to carefully consider systematic nature of GVC organizations. Moreover, explicit consideration of local IS (innovation system) and interaction between IS and GVCs is also necessary in this regard (Morrison et al., 2008; Pietrobelli and Rabellotti, 2012, 2013). Relationship between GVCs and Innovation system is two-way because GVCs not only support innovation, firm learning and improve local innovation system (Morrison et al., 2008) but also stop them. Moreover, IS also leave a strong impact on function, performance, and capabilities of local organizations within GVCs. Public support, absorbing capabilities of domestic firms and effective blend of various technological efforts may encourage the leading firms to upgrade the processes, source high value local products and locate high value activities (Pietrobelli and Rabellotti, 2011).

The debate on economic rationale behind value chain and other public policies particularly in domain of GVCs is a part of broad debate on markets and state's role in development processes and existence of coordination and market failures as we have discussed earlier (Nogueira et al., 2016). These matters are problematic particularly in field of innovation learning and technologies, where internationalization may provide a fruitful contribution via integration into GVCs. Policy justification in context of GVCs are as follows (Miles, et al., 2017). Firstly, when an organization signals the means and potential needed to integrate into GVCs, externalities on some other organizations are expected to emerge (Graefe, et al., 2010). Secondly, coordination failures do not encourage the suppliers to improve their production, thus leading companies would not provide them support (Featherston, et al., 2016). On other hand, in short-term contracts, both suppliers and lead firms may less engage in upgrading their activities and learning than it is socially desirable (Gershman et al., 2016). Finally, entry obstacles in some segments (such as product conception and branding) and considerable market failures strongly influence rent distribution among GVCs (Pietrobelli and Staritz, 2013). Simply speaking, GVCs is reshaping and raising the need of effectively designed industrial strategy and their consistency with long-term planning and TF exercises.

2.14.5 Industrial strategy and technology foresight and its importance for the developing countries

For developing countries, there is strong need for coherence between TF exercises and industrial strategies (Vishnevskiy et al., 2015). This is because developing countries often face bad institutional development, extensive market failures (Rodrik, 2000), and poor coordination of science and society with the public policies. Resultantly, the common purpose is poorly understood by the public and other actors (Tavares and Wacziarg, 2001). In such conditions, it is generally unexpected that all actors would easily and naturally align with outlined vision of TF. Mostly, information flow is not smooth and substantially marked with asymmetries, inter-firm coordination is occasional and poor and games rules are not as enforceable and solid as they would be (Georghiou, & Cassingena Harper, 2011). Contrary to that, developed countries have better aligned actors and NIS that immediately respond to incentives introduced by either government policies or market. Simply, the 'signaling' impact of TF exercises often consider sufficient to describe whether behaviour is consistent with long-term objectives or not (Kwakkel, & Pruyt, 2013). Moreover, developing countries generally need a different kind of TF exercises because these countries are rarely frontier innovators, rather use the technologies that developed abroad according to their local conditions and contexts (Gallouj, et al., 2015). As TF ultimately aims to promote catch-up process, that is why it helps the developing countries to discover existing technologies which suit best to level of their NIS development, their technological needs, and which closely relevant with their industrial policies to improve technologies (Farrington, et al., 2012).

Literature has proved that forecast of the technology realization timing is major issue that is inherited in developing countries in context of technological development (Iden, et al., 2017). Generally developing countries are behind in technological development and adopting new technologies – either through transfer of technology or through efforts of domestic firms – might be hindered by many constraints that results in delaying of technology realization (Förster, 2015). Absence of appropriate policy standards and regulation, poor research infrastructures and lack of financial and human resources are some examples of these constraints (Piiirainen, et al., 2016). Mutually consistent TF and industrial strategy helps to minimise the likelihood of inconsistency that is relatively strong in developing economies. However,

achieving positive outcomes in short run often increase the tendency of overlook benefits generated by long-term investments (Ascher, 2009). But this issue can be solved through common vision of public and private sector for future, also by turning commitments into actions (Martin and Johnston, 1999). While making investments in prominent strategic areas of future, industrial strategy and TF should create, strengthen, and nurture the physical and institutional infrastructure that brings about innovation. Such investments enable the countries to reorient their policies if mistakes and failures occur (Tuomi, 2012).

2.14.6 Industrial strategy and technology foresight policies for achieve

Literature review clearly identifies some common features between industrial strategy and TF exercises which are as follows. First and foremost, important feature is involvement of private sector that should be occurred through participatory approach. This approach has twofold scope: firstly, it increases the importance of these practices by defining the basic content of public policies that are usually unknown from Government (Hausmann et al., 2008, Hausmann and Rodrik, 2006). Secondly, it guarantees responsibility, accountability, and ownership throughout process. It is commonly known that effective, competent, and well-organised institutions act as backbone for successful industrial policies and innovations (Battistella, & De Toni, 2011). Therefore, participatory entities (such as Ministries of Education, S&T, Industry and Planning) should encourage all actors to widely adopt such behaviours that show consistency with long-run benefits of the TF practices (Battistella, et al., 2015). For example, "Innovation councils" can not only support long-run strategies (with longer duration than the government) but also can minimise government tendency to favour benefits of short-term investments and overlook long-term gains (Crews, & Farrington, 2017). Understanding GVCs logic as well as underlying power of TF-industrial strategy relationships is another important condition that ensures the success of industrial policy and TF exercises (Vivanco-Aranda, et al., 2011). GVCs currently serve as major source of technology and information for developing nations. Countries can approach specialization niches through GVCs, but for this purpose the countries should have necessary technologies and skills to handle powerful leaders of large chains (Piirainen, et al., 2017). Next section includes the discussion on three cases (Brazil, Chile and South

Korea) where coherent relationship between industrial strategy and TF is more prominent (Fabbri, 2016).

2.15 GOVERNMENT CAPACITY, INDUSTRIAL POLICY AND INFORMATION

Generally, governments make regular intervention in their economies to pursue high growth rate. These interventions are conceptually justified by the market failures, which may exist in different aspects of an economy such as production of specific goods, provision of the infrastructure, interactions among organizations and accumulation of the human capital (Weber, et al., 2019). These policies collectively termed as “Productivity Policies,” while narrow focus on specific sectoral support is traditionally termed as “Industrial Policy” (Su, et al., 2010). According to standard-welfare theory, policy should have the capacity to redress the failures, ideally closer to distortion as much as possible (Poteralska, & Sacio-Szymańska, 2014). However, some government interventions (such as in infrastructure and education) are large as well as uncontroversial while others (like targeting particular economic aspects for support etc.) are relatively more (Read, et al., 2016).

In this section, the literature review on this area has been placed in simple but organizing framework. Finite resources, lack of government attention and capacity are some rough rankings on which policies are prioritized. In this regard, there are two dimensions including probability of market failure and probability of developing policy to successfully redress it. In first part of this section, literature review includes the discussion on first consideration over sectoral or vertical interventions then horizontal interventions in relation with factor markets, finally across horizontal interventions in relation with spatial and cluster policies. Finally, this section discusses how government can improve information management and can fulfil political demands of economy productivity industrial policies.

2.15.1 Identify effectual Productivity Policies

Government should take following two main considerations while prioritizing the policies.

2.15.1.1 Likelihood of significant Market Failure

This consideration is related to information: is it possible to identify magnitude and nature of an important market failure with great confidence? We usually ask two main questions in this regard:

- 1. Can we clearly identify a market failure on the basis of available data?*
- 2. If so, whether it is the point where the policy needs to focus, or is there any other market failure (s) or distortion (s) that is possibly more important?*

Substantial information is required to address these questions. Instead of noting that why a particular product isn't being produced and why desirable outcomes are not being generated, policy makers should focus on identifying and quantifying the market failure that drive these outcomes (Lee, et al., 2012). However, addressing these questions is also essential. As government have only limited capacity and bandwidth therefore pursuing single policy will automatically exclude other one (Hussain, et al., 2017).

2.16 LIKELIHOOD OF SUCCESSFULLY REDRESSING A MARKET FAILURE BY GOVERNMENT

Government capacity to develop and execute accurate solution of observed market failure is most important. Here, the traditional concerns are coordinative, executive and diagnostic capacity of a government along with its potential to distortionary seeks rent (Acheson, et al., 2011). Existing literature explicitly or implicitly divides space of policy into horizontal and vertical market failures as well as interventions (Nuvolari, 2018).

Figure 2.9 Market failure by government

Vertical/Sectoral Interventions: When it is thought that producing specific product create externalities that generate higher social returns than the private returns, the policy that seeks to maximize production of this product is considered “vertical” (Maw, et al., 2012) see figure 2.9.

Horizontal Interventions: The market failure that is not relevant with particular product but to lesser or greater degree pertain to economy wide is termed as “horizontal” (Schäfer, 2018). However, these interventions show relevancy with factor markets with range from public education to infrastructure provision to common innovation subsidies. Benefiting sectors generally use this factor more intensively than others (Chia, et al., 2019). Moreover, these interventions simultaneously affect multiple sectors (some not currently exist) therefore considered as “*ex-ante* horizontal”, whereas vertical policies only target production of particular good at a time. However, this difference is opposite (Bresser-Pereira, 2017) where the policies that disproportionately affect specific sector are considered as *ex post* vertical. For example, we have included cluster and coordination policies in this group (Walder, 2016). Productivity advances simultaneously require pursuit of appropriate policies, provision of the factors, exploitation of potential opportunity and resolution of an issue involving intensive efforts of various organizations (Sung, 2018). Naturally, this coordination does not occur. While resolving coordination

failures in particular sector if we think that there are specific externalities linked with “sector *per se*”, then these interventions are generally treated as horizontal (Fischler, 2012) see figure 2.9.

Conceptual identification of market failures can be done in any category of interventions. Same is the case with government failure in policy design to improve them (Allan, et al., 2015). There are several examples of cities, even in advanced countries that proved fail in generating quality secondary education for purpose of governance (Bosker, et al., 2013). Though infrastructure seems straightforward from execution perspective but is often weighed down by corruption. This may discourage the societies to make investments (Lee, et al., 2019). Spatial or cluster policies mostly face both of these problems, particularly these policies are highly sensitive to government capacity to simultaneously coordinate multiple subcomponents (Steinmueller, 2013). About vertical policies, there stand an old concern that selective sector may possibly capture that political process which guarantees continued treatment (Karakoç, 2018).

On other hand, horizontal service providers have arguably and substantially more leverage to protect their privileges, by having capacity to precisely affecting many sectors simultaneously (Amankwah-Amoah, 2015). According to Chang (2009), fewer “leakages” may be linked with targeted vertical/sectoral policies, due to easy monitoring of the beneficiaries. The comparison between vertical and horizontal policies may not argue that the governments will mismanage former in unique way (Van Arsdale, 2013). Next sections contain the brief discussion on both classes of interventions in terms of information required to establish an important and clear market failure. Later on, the discussion includes various considerations regarding governmental execution of remedies. Finally, the researcher discusses basic agenda to design such interventions that are not only easy to implement but also insulated from government failures.

2.16.1 Vertical/Sectoral Policies

Marshallian externalities are generally assumed to be responsible to promote particular sectors (Hosny, et al., 2014). Being local externalities, they lead to increase productivity with respect to industry size and may generally arise for number of reasons such as input-output relations, labor pooling and knowledge

spillovers at local industry level but cannot capture the products' market prices (Singhal, & Singhal, 2019). Through simple example, Harrison and Rodríguez-Clare (2010) indicated that how to take world prices in case of multiple equilibrium. It is generally argued that a country that is specialized in a particular product without externalities would be more efficiently specialized in that product with externalities if there are some interventions.

2.16.2 Evidence about Market Failures from Data

It is empirically proved that, documenting, and quantifying these affects is difficult, let alone allow ranking the goods on basis of their individual potential for rents or externalities (Schlögl, 2015). In his study with title "*Industrial Policy for the Twenty-First Century*", Rodrik (2004) says, "I start from generic market failures, but then I take it as a given that the location and magnitude of these market failures is highly uncertain." Later on, Hausman, & Klinger. (2006) and Harrison and Rodríguez-Clare (2010) supported this agnostic view after reviewing literature on industrial policy.

Worsening data further compounded this problem. Production becomes highly fragmented with passage of time and major proportion of trade composes of trade of intermediate inputs via GVCs, trades tasks of countries, not goods, however, official statistics measure only the later (Reati, 2014). Instead of exporting high technology iPhone, China prefers to export medium or low skill tasks with 1-2% value added in product. In China, electronics is lowest value-added sector (Koopman, et al., 2008). By probably focusing on externalities relevant with tasks, we should have data on final products. Identification of externalities based on officially reported export statistics has been fundamentally misled (Khan, 2018).

Recently, the body of knowledge has raised the second challenge that the exports success about vertical or sectoral growth is less than about some "big hits," that account for large proportion of export value. Here, the "hit" refers to match between a specific geographic market and highly disaggregated product (Easterly, et al., 2009). According to Bernard et al. (2012), about 40% of US exporting firms export only one product to same destination. Moreover, large firms stand out as a group from rest of the firms due to which exporting is rare. Thus, successful exporters are differentiated from unsuccessful exporters not based on sector specialization level but on the basis of "big hits". From this it is indicated that a policy targets the entrepreneur instead of

a sector (Bernard et al., 2012). On all these points, the empirical blindness leads the literature to develop shortcuts to highlight potentially better sectors. Here is a brief discussion on three of these shortcuts.

2.16.3 Distortion, considerations, or market Failure causes

If we even knew that a specific good on average offered significant externalities, the great heterogeneity in process through which even narrowly defined good is produced in the countries should provide us a pause. Recently published academic papers highlighted the huge differences in quality (Lee, et al., 2014; Zeev, et al., 2017) and productivity level (Perez, 2010) in highly disaggregated categories of goods across countries and firms. This difference is also vast even in highly disaggregated HS (Harmonized System). A 750 ml “red wine” bottle may sell in \$2 or in \$40,000 (Domaine de la Romanee-Conti Romanee-Conti Grand Cru). The shoes of Manolo Blahnik – women leather Shoes Company – may cost \$1,500. This cost is 100 times higher than cost of common pumps of Payless brands. These deviations in unit values represent the difference in companies` ability to produce high quality products, their design capacity, marketing, human resources, and implementation of various sets of the inputs (Sutton 1998). The difference between “what” is produced, and “quality” measured by the unit values is basically a categorization/data problem and the code of Harmonized System is more disaggregated as compared to classification of 10-digit level as “leather shoes, high fashion” or “red wine, gourmet”. Product space map usually represent the transitioning of many countries among these specific goods (Sutton, 1998).

According to Baldwin (1969), and Rodríguez-Clare (2007), if a sector is expanded with the potential externalities, it does not essentially mean that they will occur automatically even if sector is inappropriately organized (Allen, 2011). For example, in start of 20th century, US copper mining brought about a valuable knowledge network both in metallurgy and chemistry that laid down a strong base for subsequent industrialization and diversification but same industry in Chile was almost died (Maloney and Valencia 2016). In early of 1980s, both Republic of Korea and Mexico started to assemble electronics, but currently only Korea is producing truly original electronic devices in Galaxy. All this leads to a very cautionary lesson, Stiglitz and Greenwald (2014) for example, concluded that the Korean government tendency to protect and encourage its various sectors was very important for

national learning and skills acquisition. Moreover, protection and targeting may not be considered as sufficient and most direct remedy of major market failures due to capabilities acquisition. Most of the observers of East-Asian miracles in NIS (National Innovation systems) emphasis more on horizontal strategies of learning as compared to vertical targeting strategies (Cirera and Maloney 2017).

2.17 THEORY OF LEARNING AND CAPABILITIES STRATEGIES

A significant amount of literature on technological change, development and growth has focused on capabilities role in structural transformation (Liu, et al., 2010). The more structuralist authors such as Hausmann et al., (2011) emphasis on investigating the impact of capabilities on technologies and products that economies and firms can produce; and on how particular technology and product portfolio or structure relates to capabilities for more diversification. Belaud, et al., (2019) inspired by evolutionary process put a strong emphasis on knowing the impact of capabilities on learning as well as catching-up processes. However, still there is no universal theory about capabilities that can recognize where capabilities reside, how these capabilities develop, and what kind of policies are supportive for them and connect them with learning as well as catching-up processes (Angelova, 2017).

2.17.1 Industrialization via global value chains (GVCs)

Increasingly structuring global economy across entire GVCs (global value chains) leads to increase international trade, employment, and output all over the world. Recent liberalization of investment and trade and rapid technology advancement has resulted in “fragmentability” of the production that acts as major source of emergence of global value chains (Szostak, 2014).). Moreover, multinational companies have also fostered the emergence of such chain by adopting competitive strategies because MNCs tend to locate low value-added and labour-intensive activities in low-wage economies and retain high value-added tasks in high-wage economies. In developing economies, GVCs act as steppingstone not only for workers but also for firms because these chains provide the opportunities to initiate catching-up process by integrating into global economy (Betts, 2007). From industrial policy and productive transformation perspective, GVCs have capacity to act as important catalysts and learning network for creation of productive employment, productive capacities and capabilities. Through learning, both productivity and

performance can be improved within value chains that in results promote job creation, dynamic catch-up processes and productive transformation in an economy via spill over effects (Walt, & Martin, 2014).

Though GVCs are important for global trade and production, however there is limited understanding of relationship between global trades and increasing “fragmentability” of production in tasks, and between structural transformation, catching up and industrialization (Dutta, 2006). Moreover, there is huge research gap on how economic upgrading and GVCs can generate more and better jobs, develop capabilities and generate learning opportunities. The first initiative in this regard was undertaken by UNCTAD, it warns the countries that trade more and earn less in GVCs context (Betts, 2007).

By presenting the framework of a vertical upgrading and specialization in global value chains, Walt, & Martin, (2014) discussed industrial policy in GVCs context and argued that since 1990s, GVCs have actively participated in transforming global trade and have significantly influenced the industrialization as well as de-industrialization processes (Dutta, 2006). Instead in final products, the trade in intermediate products/services has been rapidly grown those results in increasing import of the contents of exports. Moreover, they refereed economic development in GVCs context to as “vertically specialized industrialization” – an upgrading process into high value-added activities, either in new value chains or in existing chains so that more value could be added as whole (Berg, et al., 2010). This process is not automatic and even when this process is successfully and deliberately pursued, overall economic gain may possibly not match with broader social gains (Dutta, & Dutta, 2006).

According to Dutta, & Dutta, (2006), viewing industrial policy from GVCs perspective involve different elements than viewing it from industrial policy perspectives. This is because, GVC emphasises more on firms instead of States and markets, with business strategy as main driver of upgrading local supplier firms and international lead firms. For this purpose, the role of State becomes different, i.e. to promote industrial upgrading and activity and capacity of local firms and to capture additional value that has been added in value chain (Dutta, 2005). Moreover, the policies should consider power and interests of lead enterprises in global value chains and

should influence the link between low value-added local firms and global lead firms with respect to regional and international networks of cooperating and competing suppliers (Stearns, 2007).

2.18 ABSENCE OF COMPLEMENTARY FACTORS AS WELL AS DISTORTIONS

Based on these examples, a major question arises whether heterogeneity in quality, development and productivity within products experience any swamp. It means, whether “how the product is being produced” is more important as compared to “what has produced”. In such cases, market failures should be highly focused with more attention on horizontal considerations like managerial quality, education, NIS, entrepreneurial environment or institutions instead of production itself.

2.18.1 Issues of Product Market

The focus of vertical policies is mainly on externalities from production side while give limited attention to the demand side consideration, particularly rents (Caruso, 2018). In his classic Airbus Boeing discussion, Krugman precisely discussed that the industrial policies should shift rents – coming up from escalating rent to scale - to home country. Exclusively, this is an important point. It is generally preferred to be remained in those goods where countries can enjoy certain market power and are free from ferocious competitions with tight margins (Zeev, et al., 2017). Resultantly, there emerges a need to develop such strategies that seek to imitate the rich countries or successfully established leaders (Peters, 2017). As competitive and very rich countries or leaders are already engaged in the production of those goods therefore entry in these goods become difficult. In 1980s, the Nokia`s misadventure in television is a common example of this – firm failed due to fully saturated market (Blomstrom and Kokko 2007).

Regarding to identify externalities, Harrison and Rodríguez-Clare (2010) raised a fundamental and most relevant point. If World Bank reliably estimate as well as publish on their official website the importance of externalities related to all goods, then it would become possible for many countries to choose those sectors to enter to capture same externalities (Karak, 2017). However, this would lead to bring down the prices at global level, with potential to eliminate the benefits. Thus, it is suggested to countries to only enter in those goods where they can have great benefits without assuming market failure that will be registered better by the market

signals (Hutchinson, 2017). However, the presence of *inter*-industry externalities may mitigate this argument that is, when spillovers ensue to entire economy then they aren't being registered within price of goods. In "*Who's Bashing Whom*" Tyson (1992) forwarded these arguments to defend semi-conductor industrial sector in US (Hirschi, 2018).

As there is high need for developing countries to learn more as compared to developed countries, therefore developing countries have high potential to extract more benefits (Schuster, 2018). For instance, in the Costa Rica the earliest Intel plant may teach economy wide important lessons about nature of global marketing networks, best ways of turning old firms to new one, importance of precision (tolerances) and how quality inputs can be provided to international supply chain on time - Silicon Valley has these skills already (Pinchbeck, 2013).

As whole, having information about magnitude and existence of market failures with respect to other distortions, whether intrinsic comparative advantages are there or not and what market is perfect for a product, is quite important (Majumdar, 2012). As discussed earlier that acquiring such kind of information is very tough. In this regard, we give a brief discussion on 3 rules of the thumb to demonstrate the usage of 2 guiding questions (Jones, 2010).

In order to address the question how to quantify negative externalities, growth regression has been considered as common approach that shows negative coefficient for resource reserves, production or exports. These have not been proven robust (Lederman and Maloney 2006, 2012). However, some respectable analyses unsurprisingly found positive affect of it, such as sub-soil wealth (Sala, 1997; Manzano and Rigobon 2001; Brunnschweiler and Bulte 2008). Given above examples of US and Chilean suggest both stellar and modest experiences with the copper. Nigeria, on other hand, has underperformed but Norway has established highly innovative gas and oil industry based on substantial linkages. Norway is the world's richest country and is the creator of "Norwegian School of Petroleum Exploration". By promoting the manufacturing industry, Nigeria is supporting this sector in same way as US did with its copper industry or Finland, Sweden, Australia and Canada did with mineral resources (Majumdar, 2012). Managing volatility and exchange rates around the natural resources are universally acknowledged problem,

however, curse is not considered as curse when most of times it remains as clear blessing. Based on heterogenic nature of experiences it is suggested that we should emphasis more on how instead of what gain. Thus, problem primarily stems from weaknesses of the institutions and of national innovation systems and activities are not just affected by extractives but also by both kinds of weaknesses.

Learning skills through doing is through a very compelling logic but whether the concrete empirics are associated with this concept and whether possible market failures related to particular goods have been documented in Atlas, is still unclear (Belich, 2009). While starting with this concept, we are not sure that whether the relationships documented by them emerged from supply chain or not (Bowden, 1886). It could be assumed that consumers of developed countries consume higher-end boutique goods and show high level of value diversity which is clearly depicted by production structure of such countries (Imbs and Wacziarg 2003). Secondly, even if Complexity Atlas reflected the production considerations, still underlying common factors are unknown, particularly those associated with complexity – for example number of production steps as Levchenko (2007), and Krishna and Levchenko (2013) conceived in the production process. Thirdly, even if the factors are known, it could not be assumed that deficiency of large number of advance skills acts as major constraints for production of complex goods. For example, Blanchard and Kre- mer (1997) and Levchenko (2007) proposed that weak contract is a major constraint to produce more complex goods, and there can be absence of feedback from production of complex goods regarding the improvement of institutional environment, hence there may be no externality. Fourthly, as we have no idea about what “complexity” measure is, excepting that it is strongly associated with per capita income, the robustness of complexity with respect to growth regression is of ambiguous import. Fifthly, the analysis of export data of final goods does not reflect the tasks actually undertaken by the country – for example, instead of producing sophisticated goods (e.g. iPod), China is exporting assembly tasks (Levin, et al., 2010).

As whole, we cannot guarantee that whether any market failure pertaining to specific good is there to redress, and if it so, whether it is helpful to use “Atlas of Complexity” to locate it (Evans, 2001). By sharing the perception of “Monkey & Tree” analogy, the

approach captures the economic evolution (as monkey can easily jump from one tree to another likewise it is easy for certain goods to get transformed to others), which leads to a continuous process of dynamic growth (Hausmann and Klinger 2006; Hidalgo et al. 2007). This may help to identify trajectories in space of goods on the basis of successful experiences across other countries, closely similar to Akamatsu's (1962) proposed "Flying Geese" development pattern. By keeping 2nd guiding question in mind, it cannot be ensured that by assembling complex products and accumulating new capabilities, Korea will become able to produce highly sophisticated products as Mexico did. While rephrasing our "what" vs. "how" question, importance of monkeys from quality perspective may become high than the trees they climb (Manoranjan, 2005). In other words, better monkeys have capacity to climb faster and jump to highly distant trees that enhance the probability of exploring new parts of forest that were previously undiscovered (Nwokeabia, 2009). The economy-wide, more horizontal considerations like well incorporated innovation systems, education and upgrading organizations policies results in production of better monkeys. In this regard, Honeyman, & Goose, (2016) argued that usage of such mapping may lead to raise the question "why there is no tendency among countries to move into those goods that seems alike so that expected market failures (weak monkeys) could be surfaced (Honeyman, & Goose, 2016).

2.18.2 Smart Goods

According to Hausmann and Rodrik (2003); Hausmann, et al., (2007) many other authors, high-tech or technologically sophisticated goods produce knowledge spillovers, which triggers growth (Lall, et al., 2006). By offering more conceptual and logical statement and successive empirical implementation of this view, Hausmann and Rodrik (2003) proved that the export basket having goods produced by developed countries (high EXPY is an example of highly sophisticated export basket) show positive correlation with economy growth. Lederman and Maloney (2012) proposed that inclusion of different covariates like investment over the GDP not only undermines the results but also raise the question whether we should focus on the products that influence or on environment focusing on high level of investments (stronger entrepreneurship, favorable business environment or absence of market failures) (Olson, 2002).

However, we should still take the demand considerations into account. Whether with list of sophisticated goods or Atlas, we will always have a common equilibrium offset, particularly from the countries having read these papers (Pinchbeck, 2013). The ambiguity in these three shortcuts appears to support agnosticism of Rodrik (2004) about our abilities of identification and quantification of market failures associated with particular products. Resultantly, we focus more on activities instead of goods, for example targeting to raise quality of management, education, reliable energy, basic infrastructure etc (Inikori, 2002). It is a fact that disruptive new technology has potential to shift basis of the comparative advantage, this statement also supports the above view. In other words, the strategy that was documented in past as effective one may neither remain as desirable nor be feasible in future (Hallward-Driemeier and Nayyar 2017). In context of our first 2 criteria, these may appear at relatively low rank on certainty of magnitude of proposed market failure.

2.19 HORIZONTAL (FACTOR MARKET) INTERVENTIONS

Several areas of market failure particular to factors of production—broadly horizontal-oriented policies—have been accepted as requiring substantial government intervention. Many are directly concerned with the *how* of producing goods.

2.19.1 Can we clearly identify a Market Failure?

Various factors of production markets are characterized by long-term failures. Both infrastructure as well as services it renders relate to number of market failures, for instance in classic form of the public goods, merit goods (externalities of positive consumption), decreasing costs (result in natural monopoly) or externalities (such as network externalities) (Tutino, & John., 2016). For primary as well as secondary education, the social rate of return is more than private rate of return (Moretti 1999; Dr Paul & Govekar., 2007). In other words, educated employees may increase overall productivity of their co-workers who are less educated or countries with relatively high human capital tend to learn more from others. Classically, inadequate collateral or information asymmetries lead the credit markets to face failure (Szostak, 1991). Market exchange is generally more affected by information asymmetries. Resultantly, there arises the need to create such institutions that may minimize the inefficiencies linked with the contract incompleteness. This includes social norms,

regulatory frameworks and rules of law (Thomas, 1993). Moreover, innovation also suffers from appropriation externalities, which is why patents, tax write-offs and subsidies have been accepted as remedial policies since long (Steedman, 2007).

Logically, this supports the public organizations that circulate information of best practices, such as university departments and research institutes specialization in fundamental research and agricultural extension schemes. There are many studies that highlighted coordination failures between these kinds of non-market organizations in NISs (National Innovation System) with central focus on highlighting the failures related to acquisition of capabilities by firms.

It is generally not clear that bottleneck or market failure that has been identified is the highly critical barrier (Szostak, 2014). According to Pritchett (2001), the less influence on growth rate of education can possibly be due to some other factors. Moreover, incentives rewarded to unproductive or less productive activities bring about failures to supply side. For example, many countries have established tax write-off or subsidies for Research and Development expenses with less to show off it, regardless the fact that these policies succeeded elsewhere (Betts, 2007). However, the main failure may be in innovation (accumulation of the knowledge capital) per se, it may also be due to the presence of problem pressed in accumulation – such as capital markets, management quality, labor restrictions, insufficient demand or barriers to both entry as well as exist (Maloney and Rodríguez-Clare 2007; Cirera and Maloney 2017). Moreover, Hausmann and Rodrik's (2003) viewed externality as subset of the knowledge externalities, however this may not necessarily means that potential entrepreneur may enter market when others can freely ride on someone's investment and suitability of specific product for the market can be identified. But rather it may reflect local entrepreneurs' inability to identify productive opportunities at first place (Walt, & Martin, 2014). From management perspective, Bloom et al. (2013) argued on the basis of experiences of large Indian textile firms that investments by firms in the managerial advancement could pay to them within a year, but firms generally do not make such investments. Bruhn, et al., (2013) observed same for small size companies in Mexico. According to Betts, (2007), it is unclear that whether it is defective credit markets, missing institutions or information asymmetries that diversify the risk.

Simply, same two questions should be asked about horizontal-based policies that have asked for vertical-oriented policies. It has been said that massive literature has documented market failures surrounding these domains instead of related to particular goods.

2.19.2 Coordination (Cluster) Policies

Similar to factor markets policies, the cluster and coordination policies approach to “how” of the production. These policies though have geographical and industrial focus but have not presumed externalities characterizing specific goods (Walt, & Martin, 2014). Governments should focus on resolving coordination failures and on increasing clusters across product and geographical space (Dutta, 2006).

2.19.2.1 Can a Market Failure be clearly identified?

Countries cannot fully exploit their comparative advantage due to coordination failures. For example, if possibility of tourism is clear in a particular zone but nobody will build the hotel until the roads are built. In other words, it is useless to build a road which goes nowhere (Berg, et al., 2010). For manufacturers, it is important to have knowledge about nearby electrical grid, transport or logistic networks; however, providers will not invest unless they are not assured about demand (Dutta, & Dutta, 2006). Basic plans for infrastructure and transport should be developed at early phases because as it helps to coordinates subsequent city development that eventually influences productivity. In poor countries, many production factors may absent simultaneously and results in these coordination failures (Dutta, 2005).

In clutters, the industries or grouping firms may enable these complementarities to be realized (Porter 2000; Duranton and Puga 2004). Firstly, big cluster of companies will efficiently construct undividable facilities like infrastructure to pay fix cost to special input providers to enter local larger market. Secondly, larger market better match employers with employees, buyers with suppliers or financiers with entrepreneurs (Rice, 2004). Thirdly, in clusters, the direct interactions among economic agents facilitate the learning about market evolutions, new kinds of firms or new technologies. Labour pooling, knowledge spillovers at industry level and local input-output relationships are the various externalities that emerges when large clusters of companies come close in same sector or industry (Krugman 1991; Marshall 1920). Generally, more urbanized economies have many producers

although in different sectors or industries but at same place. Management consulting firm, for example, can grab the benefits from nearby located manufacturers, financial service provider and business schools (Rosenthal and Strange 2004).

Generally, the industrial clusters emerge from concentration of various economic activities and market forces, and this growth usually takes long time period (Liu, 2005). The initial factors which stimulate the emergence of natural clusters may vary, such as R&D facilities, suitable environmental conditions, availability of well-educated workers or availability of necessary raw material (Brinley, 2002). Strategic actions performed by private groups like credit cooperatives, industry associations and export business entities or large players such as multinational company or university) leads to develop coordination. According to Saxenian (1994), the role of Stanford University in surfacing of IT cluster in the Silicon Valley was very dominant. In Colombia, the association of flower growers acted as main player in solving the issues related to access to US market and issue of air transportation (IDB 2014).

Geographical agglomerations persist over millennia. According to (Davis and Weinstein 2002; Maloney and Valencia 2016), these are very powerful coordination issues. However, organizations may not be able to organise and cooperate themselves in a way to grab the advantages associated with these kinds of agglomeration economies (Dutta, 2006). As these external advantages can neither be priced by markets nor be internalised by the private players, therefore eventually results in coordination failures (Walt, & Martin, 2014). According to big theories of (Rosenstein Rodan 1943; Murphy, et al., 1989 cited in Berg, et al., 2010), coordinated and massive policies are needed to get start the industrial regions (Dutta, & Dutta, 2006).

It is necessary for governments to take initiatives such as establishment of SEZs (special economic zones like technology or industrial parks or export processing zone) that could offer variety of infrastructure facilities (such as uninterrupted supply of electricity), access to the land without government interferences and financial incentives (such as subsidies, tax breaks) (Hausmann, et al., 2005). These kinds of regulatory and policy changes and public investment may include large number of private organizations to not only enter but invest (Dutta, 2005). In the same way, development corridors, particularly those which provide transport linkage between

two main hubs of the economic activities, can cluster the firms not only along corridors but also at their centres. This helps to develop the surrounding regions by catalyzing the investments from outside and within the region (Steedman, 2007).

Generally, the growth poles look similar to development corridors and SEZs in sense that they also attract the organizations to make investments in the area through infrastructure development, tax incentives and other kinds of business support incentives to build up the capacity private sector (Barker, 2017). They however simultaneously involve coordinated investments within group of different industries typically built around specific opportunity or resource which is already existed at particular location (Stalling, & Peres, 2009). These industries grow through forward and backward demand and supply linkages that in turns triggers the growth process of secondary services as well as other relevant industries. In this way, growth poles appear broader than development corridors or SEZs.

The dispersion observed in quality or productivity across countries and within goods can be ascribed as inability to grab the benefits associated with such externalities. However, cluster policies consider as more appropriate to improve productivity – mean to improve “how” of the production (Rodrik 2008). This focus, however, can undermine the view that coordination failures do not directly affect the sectors, industries or goods but the technology or activity that in turns lowers the overall productivity of a firm (Feser 2002). While designing the policy, this point holds high importance. For example, if trade protection is provided to a specific sector in SEZ through tax breaks, export subsidies and tariffs, it may trigger a cluster to emerge, however cannot address the coordination failures preventing to adopt a new technology and thus tends to increase firm profitability without this new technology. Similarly, if incentives are provided to MNCs with intention to stimulate the cluster, it may not probably work if vertically integrated large firms show less confidence on other firms `output as inputs within their production, or if local companies are unable to act as providers. Moreover, an inorganically emerged cluster may not have dynamism due to lack of collaboration, trust and flow of tacit knowledge among companies (Duranton 2011). While in few cases, it is hard to know that whether the cluster is weak or not exist due to these – one or multiple – failures, or due to absence of basic comparative advantage. For example, Export processing zones

should not be developed at the place where tourist destination is not nice. Here, the danger is that embracing a cluster may lead to the fair assessment of fundamentals (Nuvolari, 2018). Cluster policies focus only on regional or local dimensions that may omit main dimensions of those interdependencies that may have actual implications for the competitiveness (Maw, et al., 2012). Both informal and formal business linkages naturally occur at almost all spatial levels (such as labor pool at local level, knowledge shared at worldwide level). If non-remedied complementary factors are not there, cluster policies can be counterproductive (Schäfer, 2018). Labor becomes sufficiently immobile when strong frictions exist in the labor markets, resultantly cluster policies will not deliver the benefits generally connected to labor pooling (Chia, et al., 2019). Land is an example of immobile factor. In this case the most concerning fact is that there are different activities for which land can be used such as open green spaces and agriculture (Bresser-Pereira, 2017). In order to strengthen the cluster, conflicts with other policies may raise which, if not resolved, will increase the likelihood of pulling-off agglomeration economies (Walder, A2016).

Above discussion emphasis on to identify and quantify a specific market failure through which market intervention could be justified. This is generally considered as main challenge for the policy makers. Generally, this is insufficient to conceptually show that externalities can exist around factor or good; but the policy makers should know whether a specific intervention is expected to produce higher growth as compare to one that has been relocated in development agenda. After getting the idea about possible influence of intervention, policy makers should weigh this intervention against the possibility that it will be appropriately implemented.

2.20 INDUSTRIAL POLICIES DEVELOPMENT

Industrial policy practically faces twofold objections. Firstly, informational objection according to governments cannot identify the degree of certainty and precision with which relevant markets, sectors or firms are subjected to market failures (Naqvi, 2018). For example, Pack and Saggi (2006) enlisted all informational requirements that intend to suggest impracticality of the industrial policy. To express this critique, it is generally saying “governments cannot pick winners,” – highly effectual conversation stopper. Practically, when omniscience is not there, activist governments will almost always miss their targets, waste their economies resources

and support their economic activities without positive spillovers (Krabben, & Dinteren, 2010). Secondly, industrial policy considers as open invitation to rent seeking and corruption. When governments actively support the organizations, it becomes relatively easy for private firms to extract the benefits and puts the demands that not only distort the competition but also transfer the rents towards politically linked firms (Romanova, & Bukhvalov, 2014). Instead of searching out the ways to reduce costs and expand markets, the businessmen and entrepreneurs spend most of their time to ask for favours. To what extent this debate on the industrial policy is centred to both assertions is notable. Instead of revolving around economic merits associated with industrial policy, the debate revolves around conflicting views about relative importance as well as occurrence of these hindrances. For opponents, these objections provide fertile ground to dismiss industrial policy. By pointing out East Asia, the opponents argue that it is possible to successfully do the industrial policy.

In above literature, researcher argued that these objections are not fatal on their face value. In other government policy domains, same opposing arguments can also be made by accepting a helpful public role from all sides. Though example of East Asian tigers is useful but may not be helpful very much. Indeed, these countries were special as indicated by Summer's analogy. To address the objections raised by critics, we need very comprehensive answer. This requires serious considerations of their implications while designing industrial policy. It also disused above precisely do it.

To settle down the debate on feasibility of the industrial policy, the government need to conduct an empirical study and discover the conditions under which industrial policy appears effective. However, there are number of empirical studies that have tried to do it. Interestingly, both critics and proponents have the empirical evidence. Relying on case evidence, proponents pointed out many instances where developing countries have successful nurtured world-class enterprises that have government support-

Largely relying on "cross-industry econometric" studies, opponents suggest that through common industrial policy tools government cannot achieve the required productivity benefits. It has found by many studies above in literature that either

there is negative correlation between industrial-policy interventions and performance, or there is no correlation at all. Such kind of econometric studies covers all cross-sectional issues of growth empirics such as complications due to omitted variables, linear specification, measurement issues etc (Rodriguez 2006, Durlauf et al. 2005). However, the difficulty goes much deeper particularly when governments systematically use the industrial policies – despite the fact whether these policies target economically undesirable or desirable ends, correlation of interventions with performance across the industries cannot describe their desirability.

2.21 RESEARCH GAP

A recent study has conducted a swot analysis by using the secondary data up to the period of 2016 for textile sector (Kanat, et al., 2018). Their study has revealed that high cost of production, energy crises, and political instability are main causes of decline in textile industry. However, the results of secondary data are unable to reveal the financial, political, economic, structural, technology, human capital, and any other issues which can also negatively influence the growth of textile sector. Nizamani (2017) conducted study and found that both domestic and foreign shocks are responsible in the decline of exports of Pakistani textile industry. However, there are many other studies who have highlighted that high cost of production, political instability, energy crises and many other factors which are responsible to decline in the exports of textile industry (Afzal, 2012; Kanat, et al., 2018; Shah et al. 2013).

Other studies are also used the literature review-based approach in which they collected only few evidence from secondary data resources of Pakistani textile industry (Cororaton, et al., 2008; Khan, et al., 2010; Shah, et al., 2012). Based on above given discussion, it is found that there is no study found which have addressed the decline challenges of over textile industry in which both textile mills and SMEs are included. According to Khattak et al. (2011), the challenges of SME are different from textile mills because they have limited capital, human capital, as well as technology. Furthermore, most of these studies have investigated the decline of textile industry using ratio analysis or other quantitative methods which cannot determine accurately the subjective realities such as financial, political, security, economic, structural, technology, human capital, structural, and government related factors which have negatively impact the textile sector growth in Pakistan. Therefore,

present study aims to bridge this gap by adopting interpretive method with the purpose to deeply explore the decline causes of textile sector as well as recommend the policies with the purpose to create improvement in textile sector of Pakistan.

CHAPTER 3: CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

3.1 INDUSTRIAL DEVELOPMENT FACTOR OF A COUNTRY

Economic geography is all about understanding the patterns and processes of the economic development. It is very important to clearly explain these processes because globalization and internationalization have not only made social and economic interrelationships very complicated but have also increased the complexity level of arenas in which such interrelationships actually play out (Dicken, 1998; Lee and Wills, 1997; Thrift, 1998; Yeung, 1998). In 1960s, capitalism encountered huge crisis due to limitations associated with Fordism and weak branch-plant economies that it created. Lack of autonomy in local decision making, limited occupational opportunities and the inability of corporate sector organization to provide favourable industrial environments for local economic growth are main factors that suffer these economies a lot (Gillespie, 1983; Scott and Storper, 1992). Nowadays, analysts are paying high attention to indigenous development as well as local capacities so that self-sustaining economic development can be generated in Pakistan.

In context of economic geography, numerous empirical analyses and theoretical frameworks have been emerged over last two decades. At local level, they used different combination of the processes related to competition and market, knowledge and technology, transaction structures, labour markets, internet and networks relations and embeddedness and culture to explain capacities of local places to adapt to, and cope with change and dynamics of local economies. However, empirical analyses are limited in scope to support such varied and elaborated theoretical propositions as all are too much ambiguous, frequently contradictory and even inconsistent (see the critiques, for example, in critiques in Gertler (1992), Sternberg (1996), and Taylor (1986). Dynamic question, too often, are addressed

through cross-sectional static data obtained from several survivor surveys. While discussing medium and small sized enterprise in terms of their contribution to regeneration of economy, Blackburn and Jennings (1996) commented that there is wider problem gap amid general theories and level of our empirical knowledge, which requires much ingenuity and research in order to test different assertions within literature.

Now, we have another series of reasons why there is need to review the claims that theoretical frameworks have about economic geography of the processes of domestic economic growth. In this discipline, the increasingly complex theoretical frameworks are facing critiques not only from outside but also from within the economic geography domain. Currently, they are being criticized from within the field of economic geography, on four grounds. Firstly, they faced critiques due to selection of empirical case-studies which are supportive only for those theories that involved dependent variables (Staber, 1996). Secondly, it is argued that these theoretical frameworks have neglected or relegated fundamentals and imperatives of capitalist markets, particularly the firms' need to generate profits for survival of business (Hudson, 1999). Thirdly, these are criticised because of privileging reciprocity and trust in supplier-buyer relationships, as these characteristics are in fact illusory or even transitory (Pratt, 1997). Fourthly, by focusing on realism, these frameworks neglected the important role of power, subordination, and domination in developing business relationships (Taylor, 1999).

Economists such as Krugman (1995) öas 'anticlarity' (The Economist 1999) viewed these theoretical frameworks harshly from outside the economic geography. Firstly, range of discursive economic geography frameworks used in-depth interviews having "close dialogue" with businesspersons as a selected methodology, which are the economists' new "stylized facts" based mathematical frameworks of economic geography (Clark, 1998). Simply, it is argued that mathematical models are rigor due to employing just stylized facts (efficient markets, agglomeration, returns to the scale etc.) (Northover, 1999), that are unrealistic thus need to unpack (Martin, 1999). Contrary to that, "soft" economic geography theories are more likely to be realistic, however, are relatively less rigorous. Yet, they are not tested in rigorous way. A third way, however, is emerging as an alternative (compare Fingleton, 2000), which goes beyond the hypothetical dualism between qualitative, "soft" geographical methods of

knowing and quantitative, "hard" economic models (Plummer and Sheppard, 2000). In local political economics, now there exists a dynamic research program with focus on development of quantitative models critical for orthodox economic understanding of regional growth and economic restructuring processes (Fingleton, 1999; Martin, 1999; Webber and Rigby, 1996). This section of the chapter includes the investigation of variety of regional economic development theories, which have been extensively used in context of economic geography that would help to understand the textile industrial growth of Pakistan. The researcher also tries to develop such dimensions through which development of textile industry can be triggered in Pakistan.

3.2 THE ROLE OF HUMAN CAPITAL INVESTMENT

Through literature review, it is revealed that there is strong association between human capital and economic development, particularly in modern economies. However, the role of this association is slightly described during Industrial Revolution. Though education is considered as cradle for industrialization but was inessential, particularly in Britain, for the economic growth (Mitch, 1993; Clark, 2005); and generally, in Europe. In this line of reasoning, Galor (2005) identified that "in the first phase of the Industrial Revolution, human capital had a limited role in the production process, and education served religious, social, and national goals." These observations, however, were based on average workers' skills or education and may hide the scientifically savvy entrepreneurs and engineers' role in skill distribution. According to Mokyr (2005a), this "density in the upper tail" is very important for the diffusion and innovation of technology throughout industrialization. Besides average education, entrepreneurial, science and math skills are also very important for economic growth (Hanushek and Kimko, 2000; Gennaioli, La Porta, Lopez-de-Silanes, and Shleifer, 2013).

For unified economic growth theory, it is very challenging task to describe minimal role human capital investment played when industrialization was at early stages. According to majority of industrialization theories, investments in human capital go side by side with growth in human lifestyle and living standards. Industrial Revolution 1.0 seems to be very compatible with reasonably flat human capital investments rates. In fact, there are lots of evidence that suggest that parents should not invest

too many resources and should not spent too much time on children during their early growth (Clark 2007, Mokyr and Voth 2010). David Mitch, for example, observed an outright decline in main expending British economy sectors such as education, cotton textiles. When enrolment figures of elementary schools were parochially surveyed for the period of 1818 to 1833, Mitch (1982) observed that enrolment remained steady at 42%. According to Flora et al. (1983), the number of British children of age between 5 and 14 enrolled in the primary school was 11% in 1855. This shows that there would not be significant rise in the education for full one century, once the industrialization starts.

Many authors have also not observed a notable rise in human capital (because of said investments) during industrialization. However, there was rise in some human capitals before the start of Industrial Revolution mainly due to slow rise in incomes (Mokyr and Voth 2010). Numeracy and literacy are two most appropriate measures that can be used for the formation of human capital in history. West (1978) observed that literacy was started to improve significantly after 1760. In England, though early improvements were observed in literacy, but formal education did not show any noticeable increase (Schofield, 1973). Moreover, numeracy also appears to be improved between late 18th and mid-19th centuries across US and much of Europe (A'Hearn et al. 2009). Resultantly, another puzzle comes up that is how early industrialization could bring improvements both in quality and quantity of people, while only little enhancement in the formal investments on children that would be case in Pakistan.

While comparing first Industrial Revolution with Second one, more surprisingly a rapid growth was observed in human capital investments only afterwards. Flora et al. (1983) documented an outburst in education from 11% during 1855 to about 74% at the end of century, whereas other European nations also experience same rise with respect to education rates (Figure 2 for detail). The story of America`s growth in 20th century reaffirms that human capital remained highly significant in late mid of 19th century. According to Goldin (1999), education played very important in economic growth of US during 20th century (Figure 3 for detail). With the initiation of 20th century, there were only few people who could afford school expenses, but when century ended only few people were there who could not afford school expanses. As a result of this transformation in education related focus of America, Goldin and Katz

(2007, 2008) dubbed 20th century as “human capital century.” In order to unify various phases of growth, any theory should consider this transformation of immaterial role of education in 18th century to noticeable indispensability in 20th century. While, A’Hearn et al. (2009) indicated that we cannot compare the required skills level of 18th, 19th century with 20th centuries because academic literacy got more importance in industrial revolution because there are advance skilled required to successfully compete in international market in this century. Therefore, the government must have to focus on the local skill development to successful compete in the global market.

3.3 FLEXIBLE PRODUCTION AND FLEXIBLE SPECIALIZATION

Flexible production thesis is an approach that is best to explicitly explain local economic development and differential local growth issue (Scott, 1988; Scott and Storper, 1992; Storper, 1995). It includes transaction costs, the components of evolutionary economics (Nelson and Winter, 1982), institutionalist economics (Hodgson, 1988; Veblen, 1904) and regulation theory (Jessop, 1990). This model derives its essential elements from capitalism best conceptualised by Scott and Storper (1992) as “Capitalism is an arrangement in which commodity producers combine the physical means of production and labour in order to bring forth sellable outputs which generate profits”. There appears variation in special social configuration of this common form, from situation to situation and time to time. Practically it emerges as a set of geographically and historically specific institutional-technological systems involving: 1) an evolving organizational and technological production structure, 2) industrial relations and labour markets including socialisation mechanisms of labour and industrial politics, 3) norms and marginal cultures, 4) types of competition and market structures, 5) regulatory institutions not only at sectoral but also at international, national and local levels. Small enterprises and mills of mid-19th century replaced early capitalism systems and gave path to the Fordist mass production. However, Fordism is now, with its large-scale urbanization characteristics and special regulatory regime, said to give the way to latest flexible production, characterised not only by significant vertical disintegration but also by incorporation of processes into tightly knitted networks in modern industrial districts (Scott and Storper, 1992).

In this regard, Scott and Storper (1992) commented as "groups of industrial establishments with especially dense interrelations tend to locate close to one another to facilitate exchanges of goods and information, and to take advantage of external economies in labor markets and infrastructure" (page 8). External economies heavily focus on reducing transaction costs (Scott, 1988). Moreover, organizations in these new industrial districts have unique characteristics. Sternberg (1996) reported that these firms (a) essentially produce for same market, (b) are related via cooperative, informal, stable connections based on reciprocity and trust, (c) are incorporated in milieu of common culture, (d) do not compete on price but on quality, (e) have constantly changing and broad product ranges, (f) are specialised in extreme labour division, (g) use modern technologies, and (h) have support from regional institutions that trigger permanent innovation.

Theoretically, new demands have been created at local level as a result of new technological system of the flexible production because new industries are creating their individual spaces far away from agglomerations of mature industries and established production centres, which then face entropic death. In this latest transition in context of capitalism, there seems to appear three kinds of deagglomeration including: design-intensive, craft-based centres (for example Third Italy), advanced financial services and producer agglomeration (e.g. London), and high technological centres (such as Silicon Valley) (Scott and Storper, 1992). Resultantly, these modern industrial districts appear to be incorporated into "global mosaic of regional economies" (Scott and Storper, 1992, page 11). Scott and Storper, (1992) described regional production systems as, "every system has its own dense system of intra-regional transactional arrangements and local labor market activities, while being entwined in a worldwide web of interindustrial linkages, investment flows, and population migrations, mediated by a number of crucial institutional arrangements involving the multinational enterprise, an emerging system of international subcontracting, interfirm strategic alliances, international agreements, and so on".

Though many scholars such as Gertler, (1992) and Sternberg, (1996) have criticised this regional development model as well as differential economic growth, but it still gets high importance due to incorporation of four dimensions broadly into far-reaching explanatory model. Similar to regional economic development model, the

technology driven flexibility model hinges on integration of organizations at local level via exchanging information and goods. This integration leads to obtain regional external scope and economies of scale and reduce transaction costs (Scott, 1988). The technological, place-based leadership in this framework is in fact driven by reciprocity and trust involved in supplier-buyer relationships, institutional support as well as potentialities of HR with respect to regional labour market. These forces collectively shape, modify and mould the Schumpeterian dynamics of local creative destruction for the rapid learning and innovation.

3.4 LEARNING, TECHNOLOGY AND INNOVATION

Majority of studies in existing literature have tried to address the question how innovation and learning can be developed and accelerated and how capabilities play an important role in the formation of structural transformation (Shen, 2018). Economic development and its dynamics remain the centre of focus of evolutionary economies (Zaring, & Eriksson, 2009). Moreover, productive transformation is a very complex, non-linear and incremental process due to having technological change, accumulation of regional capabilities and analyses learning as its central drivers (Chebbi, & Khedhiri, 2011). In this regard, economists argue that rather than “given” the comparative advantages, in fact, are made. That is why development states pay high attention to design such institutions and policies that are supportive for learning processes (Farrell, et al., 2009; Naeem, 2019b). Moreover, the developed economies have discovered the ways through which they can move their entire productive structure deliberately away from “lower quality activities” having attributes such as flat learning, diminishing returns, low wages and low productivity towards “higher quality activities” having attributes such as steep curves of learning, economies of scale, high wages, high productivity, fast technological progress and high growth rate of output (Cimoli, Dosi and Stiglitz, 2009). Regarding this framework, State should create such conditions that are conducive to the process of learning in Pakistan.

While discussing the expansion of “infant industry” or “infant economy”, Greenwald and Stiglitz (2013; 2014) argued that government should create well-designed policies on intellectual property, trade and industry in order to ensure the creation of learning society. They further argued that “creating a learning society is more likely

to increase standards of living than the small, one-time improvements in economic efficiency or those that derive from sacrifices of consumption today to deepen capital” (Greenwald and Stiglitz, 2013, p. 45). Regarding learning, knowledge and technology upgrading, their approach is not only rooted deeply in neoclassical traditions but also is based on analysis regarding the failures of markets for knowledge dissemination, information and production and failures of financial markets for innovation and finance knowledge (Holmén, 2002). According to them, understanding learning structure in any economy is very important, including how learning spreads throughout the sectors. These understandings are also very important for deriving the policy conclusions regarding how exports, manufacturing and other sectors can be best encouraged for fast productivity growth and accelerated learning.

Recently, Mazzucato (2013) provided a powerful, fresh and contrasting look at how State plays its role in promoting the need to develop technological capabilities necessary for “innovation-led growth”, particularly in middle-income and developed countries. She evidently proved that both main entrepreneurial drive as well as consequent risk-taking necessary for development of various important latest technologies (such as wind and solar energy, voice-recognition software, Internet, GPS and touch-screen displays) has been less provided as compare to what more-hyped venture capital and private sector has suggested and more as compare to what State has acknowledged. Moreover, she showed how public policies in US and other nations played an important role in creating these capabilities and innovations during highest risk period. By using structuralise–evolutionary inspiration growth model. According to Breznitz, (2007), it is the rationalization that drives the productivity growth in case of appreciated real exchange rates and weak technological and industrial policies whereas defensive responses are not associated with increasing effective demand. Resultantly, the technology-intensive sectors are more likely to lose their competitiveness, whereas employment is expected to concentrate more in activities with lower productivity. On other hand, in case of competitive exchange rate and strong technological and industrial policies in favour of diversify production, employment is expected to rise, and productivity shows significant growth.

'Innovative milieus' (Maillat, 1995; 1996; Maillat and Lecoq, 1992) and 'learning regions' (Asheim, 1997; Lundvall, 1992; Maskell et al, 1998) are the concepts that have significantly refined and extended the flexible-production and flexible specialization model. These concepts have been used to elaborate and propose the mechanism through which new place-specific economic activity can be created, which is highly determined as compare to 'arbitrary local event' due to its transformation into flexible production model (Asheim, 1997; Malmberg and Solvell, 1997; Sternberg, 1996). Through their place-based roles, learning, knowledge and information act as strong promoters of regional economic growth. This framework mainly focuses on shared psychological, political and cultural backgrounds of participants within network, intensive interconnection amongst agents and immobile human-capital (Maillat, 1996). Though leadership and technological change are central to this framework, however, are mostly viewed in context of increasing innovation accelerated by regional exchange of implicit knowledge (Asheim, 1997; Maskell and Malmberg, 1999).

The dynamic role of knowledge and information is pushed into the model through 'ubiquification' process in factor market. The core argument that is centre to ubiquification process is that slightly intensive competitive, larger and more efficient factor markets generate many geographically ubiquitous production factors. Resultantly, they have stopped to work as spatial forces of uneven development. Now, availability of tacit knowledge is viewed as strongest remaining differentiated factor of production.

As Malmberg and Solvell (1997, page 11) stated that "an innovative milieu is a segment of territory that is characterized by a certain coherence based on common behavioural practices as well as a 'technical cultural way to develop, store and disseminate knowledge, technical know-how, norms and values linked to a certain type of economic activity". They pointed out four main characteristics of these milieus: (a) group of such actors (institutions and firms) that are autonomous in strategy formulation and decision making, (b) a set of institutional, material and immaterial elements combining legal frameworks, authorities, know-how, knowledge, infrastructure and firms, (c) a self-regulatory dynamic leading towards learning and (d) interaction amongst actors on the basis of cooperation. Communities and localities act as facilitator for evolution of values, norms, social bonds, common

language and institutions and all make a collective contribution to accumulated learning process (Morgan, 1996). These localities are of considerable sectoral specialization, not only specialize in high-tech but also equally in low-tech activities (Maskell et al, 1998; Maskell and Malmberg, 1999). Success of these specialized milieus heavily relies on long-term buyer-supplier relationships (oblique and horizontal quasi-integration), trial and error-based problem solving and knowledge exchange and repeated interaction (Leborgne and Lipietz, 1992). Overall, this approach is proposed to understand spatially uneven growth of economy as firms' social bonding to generate enterprise via learning (Braczyk et al, 1998; Maskell et al, 1998).

Schumpeterian framework that flexibility model has is thus built on technological leadership, local integration processes, local human capital and institutional support. This framework is further extended through the addition of two new main dimensions including regional sectoral specialization and knowledge and information. these elements of regional economies in combination with local firms' integration foster continuous innovation, place-based learning and constant reinforcement and refreshment of regional competitive advantage.

3.5 COMPETITIVE ADVANTAGE

Though Neoclassical economic model is one of the latest growths facilitating approaches but are imperfect in saying about development and growth and policies that are helpful in managing these processes (Commission on Growth and Development, 2008). However, neoclassical framework based developed trade and traditional growth models explain the growth with respect to accumulation of the production factors such as technology, human and physical capital in particular (Solow, 1957; Lucas, 1988). According to these models, a country should have specialization in products regarding which it holds comparative advantages. Also, the policies should be centred largely on residuals derives from exercises produced by the said approach (Aghion and Durlauf, 2007; Kenny and Williams, 2001). Market failures, in principle, provide strong justification for state interference. Neoclassical economics emphasis on documenting government failure cases and argues that these failures are mainly due to factors like corruption and incompetent or myopic bureaucracies (Fraser, & Kelly, 2010). Moreover, government failure is more likely to

occur as compared to market failure (Krueger, 1990; Schleifer, 1998). Stylized-perfectly competitive norm is the factor on which this approach actually based. The resultant policy debate that compares market failure with governmental failure is unnecessarily polarized which has greatly the development policy through stopping rich analysis regarding how different learning processes and institutions can stall or promote structural transformation in specific set of historical circumstances and initial conditions. In this tradition, mainstream policy, instead of this nuanced enquiry, has promoted excessively simplest universal policy principles and rules like getting the government outside the way or getting prices right.

The competitive advantage model proposed by Porter (1990; 1998) further interpret the processes running in globalized economic, political environment and observed more success in some nations, places and regions than others. this model is highly summative eclectic with particular focus on managerial and business enterprise decision making (Jin, et al., 2017). It is a model, in which local growth and competitive success are judged to identify the processes that collectively increase the productivity, "with location affecting competitive advantage through its influence on productivity and especially on productivity growth" (Porter, 1998,209). Instead of focusing on cultural, political and institutional elements of business environment, this approach places high emphasis on demand conditions, factor conditions, firm structure, rivalry, and strategy and supporting and related industries. Recently, this model is elaborated with respect to `clustering' processes (Leoncini, et al., 2019). Porter (1998) superficially and quite explicitly draws on the concepts particularly from learning regions and flexibility models and generally from work related to an agglomeration in context of economic geography. As Porter argue that firm rivalry, structure and strategy can lead to generate local competitive advantage thus it is important to reinforce the nature and internal workings of business enterprises (managerial attitudes, commitment and motivation) as an important source of the differential local growth. While analysing "clustering", discussed above that Porter argue that competitive advantage model can enhance the productivity through:

1. Strengthening the local demand as it brings competitive advantages in terms of international trade
2. Local specialization as it reduces transaction costs both in terms of human resources and assembling inputs

3. Increasing the access to related information
4. Complementarities amongst firms through local integration
5. Both private and public institutional support in turning expensive inputs into quasi-public and public goods
6. Technological leadership that facilitates the identification of local opportunities

3.6 DEVELOPMENT: MARKET-LED OR STATE-LED?

Theoretically state-led and market-led development strategies are generally viewed as two different options of growth, and any one can be selected from both. It is however unclear as whether majority of developing nations have had yet any freedom to explicitly exercises or choose these options, expect for few that are “oft-touted examples” in this respect.

3.6.1 Developing through market or state

Through reviewing literature on development, it is revealed that market-led development, a paradigm simplistically draws from neoclassical economic principles, is argued to allow the market for allocation of resources, thus reduces the role and authority of state. This paradigm refers market as to best mechanism regarding resource allocation and time reinforcement through different international agencies, such as World Bank (e.g. Stein, and various other authors) (Liang, & Goetz, 2018). According to market proponents, economic crises (of 1970s in particular), and their resultant impact on universal trade, inflation and unemployment lead to the development of market-led solutions, which relied heavily on competitive industrial development and markets deregulations as long-term solutions to finance and labour (Chang 2002). In addition to that, the other shortcomings associated with state include rent-seeking via state actors, creating undue expectations about employment conditions, difficulties regarding to engage private sector, information asymmetries, high transaction expenses and undue coordination costs (Olowu 2003). World Bank and other donor agencies have adopted market-led development approach across Africa and promote those approaches that devoid of and “hand off” the involvement of state. Regardless of this, increasing emphasis has been observed on interventions from state, particularly via industrial policy. “Boom & Bust” patterns of macroeconomic growth characterised by unexpected implications for developing economies has strongly reinforced the paradigm of state-led development (North 1990). As a result of such recurring phenomenon, market relevancy has been

undermined as a single force for constant development with passage of time, which in turns increasingly calls for role of state. These approaches firmly build on those economic theories that clearly steer away from expression of market-driven strategies (North 1990). For example, institutional economics is escapes from theoretical assumptions of welfare maximising, rational people, operating in unnatural world where all selections can be accurately predetermined, to relatively more realistic environment where institutions essentially have to minimise the transaction cost (Coase 1937, 1960, 1988; Williamson 2005; 2010). Institutional economics is mainly characterised by inherent risk in decision making under uncertain condition, bounded rationality and relevance of societal norms (North 1990). Other studies in field of economic sociology, economics and political economy further support these insights (Polanyi 1944, 1957). The studies on embedded institutions and relevance of social norms (Evans 1995), state-led development theories (Amsden 1999, Amsden and Chu 2003, Johnson 1986 and 2000), innovation studies and other latest studies on economic catch-up and industrial policy (Cimoli et al 2009, Naude 2011), are all developed on the base of these insights.

Based on these perspectives, it is argued that importance of state as the source of resource mobilization remains paramount, specifically to ensure employment creation, equal distribution of employment opportunities and overall development. However, state shows variation in articulation of these roles. According to institutional economics, state is an actor that requires resistant whereas newer approaches refer the state to such an actor that acts as very much positive driver of development. Literature on innovation studies, for example, describes state as main force that coordinates all non-economic and economic actors builds up the capabilities through a meaningful policy of learning and coordination.

3.6.2 State-led and market-led: a misleading dichotomy?

The current policy framework in developing nations reveals a combination of market-led and state-led approaches. On one end, state-led developmentalism is being touted by giving the examples of India, China and East Asian countries as success stories. Based on the experiences of these countries it is argued that role of social capital in terms of technological change is very important (Gerschenkron 1962, and later Chang 2004, 2006a, 2006b). these are the state-led actions that initially

triggered the technological change, in which role of public sector organizations was very important both in emphasising on process and product development and also as a hub of creativity. In above mentioned examples of India, China and many East Asian nations, state-led organizations raised entrepreneurial spin-off that in turn led to produce skilled manpower, facilitated the creation of employment opportunities for numbers of people and encouraged closer university-industry alliances (Moudud & Botchway 2009). Many scholars argued that there is need to strengthen the role of state, for which they emphasised on job growth, particularly in term of facilitating the recovery from latest financial and economic crisis (Moudud & Botchway 2009). Moreover, job growth is also suggested to be based upon technological development so that sustainable, high quality jobs can be created. Since long, scholars have been debated on how to create these jobs and what kinds of options is available regarding this (Moudud & Botchway 2009). Moreover, extrapolating the role of state regarding to promote technological development across East Asian countries and how to apply it in Africa is also an important question. Some studies, in context of Africa, have emphasised on comparative advantages as best way to generate job growth in African countries. This approach fundamentally recommends that rather than moving towards other sectors, they should engage in such development strategy through which expansion in current resource intensive and labour-intensive industries can be promoted, so that no more skills and capital can be called for (Lin 2012).

Problematically, though these arguments seem as supporter of state-led development, but they misleadingly marked current development patterns (specifically those relevant with growth of resource-led commodities) as the development strategies (Lin 2012). It is fact that natural resources simply cannot act as backbone of industrial efforts of a country but should be augmented via intellectual capital (knowledge accumulation, learning and skills) and material growth (industry and machinery). Whenever state`s role in terms of technologically-based job growth is propounded, the debate often obfuscate the issue that promotion of skilled-intensive jobs usually comes at expense of ignoring the generation of employment for other unskilled and semi-skilled jobs, particularly that are traditionally linked with rising productivity of manufacturing sector (Jomo 2002, Jomo and Ocampo 2003). For example, this can be demonstrated through current Indian experience which has totally different economical structural transformation as

compare to China. Most recent analyses reported that during transition of India from agriculture sector to services, its manufacturing sector grows a little bit which acts as major cause to make overall economy unable to bring significant job growth throughout the country (Kotwal and Ramaswami 2011). Resultantly, the available employment for skilled-intensive jobs has stunted the possibility to bring large proportion of population out of severe poverty, as compare to what Pakistani economy has achieved over last three decades.

3.7 CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

This chapter restates the industrial policy through (1) investigating the relationship between job creation, employment growth and productive transformation – this relationship found weak in present literature (2) highlighting the importance of various economic traditions that can be considered while analysing and developing industrial policy, also recognizing that there is certain rapprochement among these traditions, partly based on understanding of failure and success record of the industrial policy, and (3) making a set of different important principles and lessons that are valuable in supporting productive transformation (setting the target appropriately, pursuing better match between industrial, macroeconomic and trade policies, promoting productive transformation and learning as interrelated procedures and need for integrated , coherent, multi-sectoral frameworks).

This chapter has provided a comprehensive overview of major frameworks along with issues arise out of case-studies included in this framework and has distilled some common principles and lessons about how to develop a right policy. This requires to seriously considering measuring performance and institutional design to ensure discipline and learning from experience, being flexible and pragmatic with passage of time; and seriously raises the voice by promoting social dialogue, participation and consultation at each level and keeping the industrial policy pure and honest. These are excellent principles not only for the industrial policy but also for all policy domains.

The countries that had already applied existing market orthodoxy and had successfully passed through the catching-up process, may not be considered as success stories nowadays. The governments of these countries were both pragmatic and unorthodox in their policy approaches, which is the main reason

behind their success. Moreover, these countries experimented with variety of different sectoral, education, technology, macroeconomic and trade policies that enable them to introduce and manage capability building and structural transformation process in sustainable manner. These policies also allowed these countries to learn from their errors and then adopt policies accordingly. The principle these countries used to apply is “the market is a good servant but a bad master”.

Figure 3.10 Conceptual framework

The technological, place-based leadership in this framework (see figure 3.1) is in fact driven by reciprocity and trust involved in supplier-buyer relationships, institutional support as well as potentialities of HR with respect to regional labour market. These forces collectively shape, modify and mould the Schumpeterian dynamics of local creative destruction. There is major four main characteristics have been identified of these milieus: (a) group of such actors (institutions and firms) that are autonomous in strategy formulation and decision making, (b) a set of institutional, material and immaterial elements combining legal frameworks, authorities, know-how, knowledge, infrastructure and firms, (c) a self-regulatory dynamic leading towards learning and

(d) interaction amongst actors on the basis of cooperation. Communities and localities act as facilitator for evolution of values, norms, social bonds, common language and institutions and all make a collective contribution to accumulated learning process (Morgan, 1996). In this regard, the literature has recently provided evidence about the relationship between growth rates and diversification patterns (Hausmann, Hwang and Rodrik, 2007; Ocampo, Rada and Taylor, 2009; Lederman and Maloney, 2012) see figure 3.1 for the detail of industrial policies impact on productivity. The figure 3.1 highlighted that what are the important industrial elements such as education, skills, and innovation technology that can enhance the capacity development as well as increase management of productive industrial transformation in the country like Pakistan.

Schumpeterian framework that flexibility model has is thus built on technological leadership, local integration processes, local human capital and institutional support. This framework is further extended through the addition of two new main dimensions including regional sectoral specialization and knowledge and information. These elements of regional economies in combination with local firms' integration foster continuous innovation, place-based learning and constant reinforcement and refreshment of regional competitive advantage. The resultant policy debate that compares market failure with governmental failure is unnecessarily polarized which has greatly the development policy through stopping rich analysis regarding how different learning processes and institutions can stall or promote structural transformation in specific set of historical circumstances and initial conditions. In this tradition, mainstream policy, instead of this nuanced enquiry, has promoted excessively simplest universal policy principles and rules like getting the government outside the way or getting prices right.

Rather than viewing factor conditions as only physical resources, they are more broadly seen as knowledge resources (market, scientific and technical knowledge), human resources (skills, cost and quantity), infrastructure (social and physical) and capital resources (deployment, types, access). Production factors can also be created which is their most important aspect. So, it isn't stock of the factors that helps to better understand differential local growth, however with which rate they are usually created is also important. Home demand, by nature, is a place endows with dynamic advantages. Through sophistication and needs of domestic buyers, local

producers can be sensitized along with instillation of confidence. Moreover, dynamic local markets facilitate the firms to foresee the international demands whereas size of regional demand acts as reinforcing advantage. It is generally recognized that specialization is a potential source of competitive advantage. According to complementing ideas about learning regions, innovative milieus and flexible production, the supporting and related industries provide competitive advantage by recognizing agglomeration in external economies. 'Regional integration' provides few tangible benefits regarding innovation, technology, knowledge and learning. These processes then, through the creation of social capital, trigger the productivity growth within economic or locality cluster. Based on these perspectives, it is argued that importance of state as the source of resource mobilization remains paramount, specifically to ensure employment creation, equal distribution of employment opportunities and overall development. However, state shows variation in articulation of these roles. According to institutional economics, state is an actor that requires resistant whereas newer approaches refer the state to such an actor that acts as very much positive driver of development. Literature on innovation studies, for example, describes state as main force that coordinates all non-economic and economic actors builds up the capabilities through a meaningful policy of learning and coordination.

Although the extent of literature is available with respect to find the decline causes of textile sector in Pakistan (Abbas et al., 2012; Shah et al., 2013; Afzal, 2012; Kanat, et al., 2018; Cororaton, et al., 2008; Khan, et al., 2010; Shah, et al., 2012) however these studies are produced different results from each other. Abbas et al. (2012) argued financial crises decreased textile sector growth; Afzal (2012) found that rise in interest and electricity rates made textile sector less attractive; Haq 2019) highlighted external debt increased has negatively influence on currency as well as machinery import for textile sector; and Kanat et al. (2018) have found that energy crises, high cost of production, and political instability are the main reasons of decline . Here it has become important to explore the overall challenges of textile sector which have decreased the level of productivity, exports, growth, and attraction for investors. Furthermore, none of these studies (Abbas et al., 2012; Shah et al., 2013; Afzal, 2012; Kanat, et al., 2018; Cororaton, et al., 2008; Khan, et al., 2010; Shah, et al., 2012) which are conducted in Pakistani textile sector used any

particular theories because it is impossible to use too many theories for human, government, technology, financial, structural, government, security, energy, and other challenges for textile sector which are vary between country to country.

CHAPTER 4: RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

4.1 INTRODUCTION

This chapter is going to discuss and justify the research philosophies and research methods for this research. As the research paradigm is the starting point of the research methodology, as Guba & Lincoln (1994) have defined paradigm as, a basic belief system or world view that guides the investigation. There are various taxonomies that are used to differentiate the paradigms but collectively these taxonomies share three basic elements including ontological assumption, methodological assumption and epistemological assumption (Guba & Lincoln 1994).

- The Philosophy that deals with reality, its form and nature is called ontology. It helps to constitute legal researchable questions (Guba & Lincoln 1994).
- The philosophy that deals with knowledge i.e. what considers as knowledge and how someone comes to know is called epistemology (Guba & Lincoln 1994 cited Crowther, & Lancaster, 2012).
- Methodological assumption is a procedure that is used by researchers to investigate the rationale lies behind the procedure and to know what they actually believe (Sarantakos 1998).

Figure 4.11 Methodology elements (source: Howit, & Cramer, 2017).

When researchers make claims about the reality, it is called ontology, how they know what the reality is, is called epistemology and procedure they use to study it is called methodology. All of these philosophical assumptions are interrelated with each other and their distinctive relationship helps to understand different research approaches (Walliman, 2010). There are number of diverse paradigms that can be differentiated through a wide range of different taxonomies. In social sciences, interpretive, critical and positivists are three dominant paradigms (Cohen, et al., 2017). Following figure shows the major elements of methodology

4.2 ONTOLOGY

Figure 4.12 Research methodology alignment

4.3 SUBJECTIVISM

Subjectivism views the creation of social phenomena as a result of perceptions and resultant actions of concerned social actors. According to this view, creation of social phenomena is a continuous process in sense that social interactions keep these phenomena in a state of constant revision (Newby, 2014). According to Remenyi et al. (1998:35) cited in Quinlan, et al., (2019), “there is need to study the details of the situation to understand the reality or perhaps a reality working behind them”. This

view connects the subjectivism with social constructionism or simply constructionism that follows interpretivist position which emphasis on exploring what subjective meanings tend to motivate the social actors to act so that researcher can better understand their actions (Cohen, et al. 2011). According to social constructionism, reality is socially constructed which deeply rooted with subjectivism which why subjectivism ontological position is taken for this research.

This debate on subjectivism vs. objectivism is to some extent similar to various ways through which practical and theoretical approaches to organizational culture have recently developed (Saunders, et al., 2009). Hammond, & Wellington, (2013) argued that objectivists view the organizational culture as something organization “has” therefore, the subjectivism ontological position will be helpful to explore the political and cultural meaning attachment. Subjectivists, in other pool, view the industrial polies as something construction of political, economic and legal outcome of continual social enactment process (Rodrik et al., 2004). However, industrial theories as well as practice lean more towards viewing local political, economic and legal culture as something as whole of industrial policies “has”, a variable which can be changed, manipulated so that industrial policy makers desired state can be produced. Subjectivists reject this view by arguing that industrial polices is produced and reproduced through complex phenomena that involve social interactions, rituals, politics, myths and physical factors like office setup to which policy makers attach some meanings. Understanding meanings attached by the social actors to these complex phenomena in industrial policy making is necessary to understand the transformation of the industrial policies and the effectiveness of industrial policies. As organizational culture is a continual process therefore isolating, understanding and manipulating it is quite difficult.

4.4 AXIOLOGY

The philosophy of judging the value is called axiology. This may also include researcher`s own values in areas of ethics and aesthetics. Here we consider the axiology as process of the social enquiry. Researcher own values play very important role throughout research process and makes strong contribution in generating credible research outcomes. According to Heron (1996), values of human beings are guiding reasons of their actions. Researchers` axiological skill enables

them to express their values based on which they make judgements about which they have to conduct research and how to do it. However, researchers should demonstrate their values at all steps throughout research process. While discussing axiology, Heron (1996) presented very interesting idea that researchers can write own statements of their personal values with respect to topic they are studying. However, this may evidently more applicable to certain research topics but not others.

4.5 EPISTEMOLOGY

Table 4.3 Positivism versus interpretivism

Assumptions	Positivism	Interpretivism	Authors
Nature of the reality	Tangible, Single, Objective,	Multiple, socially constructed	Donley, (2012).
Research Goal	Strong prediction, Explanation	Weak prediction, Understanding	Crowther, & Lancaster, (2012)
Focus of the interest	What is average, representative and general	What is unique, deviant and specific	Walliman, (2010).
Knowledge generation	Absolute Laws (value, time and context free)	Relative Meanings (value, time, context and culture bound)	Cohen, et al., (2017)
Researcher-Subject relationship	Severe separation	Cooperative, Participative, Interactive	Howitt, & Cramer, (2017)
Required information	How many individuals have specific problem or do and think specific think	What people do and think, what problems they generally encounter and how people deal with these problems.	Tracy, (2013)

The major concern of epistemology is what makes up acceptable knowledge within area of research (Tracy, 2013). The major distinction is hinted in our above-

mentioned example of different researchers' view about what is important while studying manufacturing process. Position of "resources" researchers is more parallel to that of natural scientists as they consider data related to resources (Tracy, 2013). This position may also be of operation management specialists who are comfortable with collecting and analysing the facts (Howitt, & Cramer, 2017).

Figure 4.13 Positivism versus interpretivism

4.5.1 Positivism

When research philosophy represents the views of positivism, researcher will likely to adopt philosophical position of natural scientists (Saunders, et al., 2016). Therefore, positivists tend to prefer 'working with an observable social reality and that the end product of such research can be law-like generalisations similar to those produced by the physical and natural scientists' (Newby, 2014). Similar to 'resources' researcher, only the phenomena that can be observed by the researcher will produce credible data. By using existing theory, researcher can develop research strategy, collect data and develop hypotheses (Hammond, & Wellington, 2013).

Table 4.4 Characteristics of positivism and interpretivism (McNeill, & Chapman, 2005).

	Positivist paradigm	Interpretivist paradigm
Primary beliefs	World is objective and external, science is context and value free, researcher is independent.	World is subjective and socially constructed, observer and thing to be observed are not separated from each

		other, science is all about human interest
Responsibility of Researcher	Research should look for fundamental laws and causality, emphasis on facts, reduce the phenomena by fragmenting into simplest components, formulate and test the hypotheses	Researcher should emphasis on meanings, focus on understanding what is actually happening, develop ideas from data through induction, look at situation in totality
Preferred methods	Operationalise the concepts in order to measure them. Draw samples of large size	Develop different views by using various methods Draw small samples to investigate over time or in-depth

Even if institutions are quite decent, the problem will remain same. Moreover, “Good governance” refers to the ability of generating and implementing policy initiatives require to minimise the effects of market shortcomings and imperfections (Danhui, 2014). The developing countries like China, Taiwan and South Korea did not make their institutions suddenly perfect, but gradually developed through the implementation of policies to cope with market hindrances that their investors encountered in new tradable industries (Danhui, 2014). But polices in all of these countries are quite different than other therefore, researcher cannot test or apply any single theory to develop better textile industrial policy for Pakistan which is why positivism epistemological position is not being taken for this research. Positivist philosophical position carries pejorative connotations in social research. As this paradigm relies on model of natural science, therefore many social critics and philosophers characterised it as scarce in science (Saunders, et al., 2007). Positivism has been highly criticised because its emphasis more on the direct

observations thus disregard values, beliefs, moral judgments and informed opinions (Cohen, et al., 2011).

Figure 4.14 Characteristics of positivism and social constructionism (Naeem and Khan, 2019)

The positivists represent the reality through objects that consider “real”, for example trucks, machines and computers. These objects separately exist from researcher that is why collected data is less or even not open to the bias, hence more “objective” see figure above (McNeill, P., & Chapman, 2005). Resource researchers have little control over collected data as compare to “feelings” researcher who concern with attitudes and behaviour of industrial policy makers towards overall industry transformation. Moreover, the objects that are studied by “feelings” researchers – attitudes and feelings – would be viewed by “resources” researchers as the social phenomenon with no exterior reality (Quinlan, & Zikmund, 2015). ‘The

textile industrial policies are situational, social, cultural and political constructed therefore the industrial policies cannot be treated by a universal theory and laws additionally these laws cannot be work well for the all the time. Consequently, the positivism epistemological position cannot be taken for this research because positivism believe that world is based on static laws and regulation which is call universal truth for all.

Figure 4.15 Ontology influence on the epistemology

Generalizability is another issue for positivist as they argue that quantitative inquiry is context and time free. Industrial policy sceptics, in reaction to above listed market failures, often realise that policy intervention should be there, but highlight that horizontal policies are needed instead of preferential policies that discriminate the activities (Ember, & Ember, 2009). Learning human-capital externalities and financial market failures are perfect remedies, uniform measures directly targeting the education, R&D and financial markets remove the counter arguments (Gulin, & Ermolov, 2015). However, horizontal interventions should be considered for limited cases without thinking it as definite alternative of vertical policies. Practically, most

interventions (both horizontal and vertical) favour few activities and not others (Lester, et al., 2013). For instance, the policies that tend to improve financial intermediations through conventional banks partially target the enterprises in formal sectors having access to outer finance, while discriminate against informal and small enterprises (Maskus, et al., 2013). The pollicise targeting the microfinance have entirely opposite effect. Moreover, accelerated depreciation not only facilitates capital-intensive activities but also discriminate against the labour-intensive activities (Weiss, 2018). Intellectual-property protection and R&D subsidies helps the firms in undertaking patentable innovations, however, not support the firms that produce “cost-discovery” externalities (knowing what could be profitably manufactured at home) (Morris, et al., 2012). Exchange-rate policies – typical horizontal policies – support tradable activities but at expense of the non-tradable activities. Therefore, policy makers should not ignore the asymmetric impacts of horizontal interventions and should ensure that they ultimately favour the activities that suffer disproportionately from market failures in question (Thrasher, 2013). At the same time there are many other factors like get fruitful results from the policies.

If we consider the research aim is to develop textile industry development framework for Pakistan which required interpretation of the overall circumstance of the industry which is not align with positivism which is why positivism epistemological position is not being taken for this research.

4.5.2 Interpretivism

The opponents of positivist tradition claim that the complex social world including management and business cannot lend itself over to definite laws and theorising as physical sciences do (Hesse., 2010). The researchers who criticise positivism claim that deep insights into complex social world would be lost if this complexity is entirely reduced to a set of the law-like generalisations (Guthrie, 2010). In case of such views, research philosophy tends to be closer to interpretivism, an epistemology which advocates that researchers should differentiate the humans in terms of their roles as the social actors (Walliman, 2006). Here, ‘social actors’ is most significant term to understand the institutional coordination and attitude toward the textile industry development policies. According to metaphor of theatre, human life is the stage where we as humans have to play our role. In theatres, actors interpret their part of play in a specific way and then act according to this interpretation (Matthews,

& Ross, 2010). Likewise, researchers interpret social roles of humans with respect to meanings researchers attached with these roles. Moreover, researchers also interpret these human roles with respect to their own bunch of meanings (Bode, & Arthur, 2014).

The interpretivism epistemological position is being taken for his research because interpretivist research help to interpret and understand meanings attached with human behaviour instead of generalising and predicting cause & effect relationships in textile industrial development in Pakistan. The interpretivism epistemological position helps to find technological, government, financial, human capital, market, legal and other issues that can influence the growth of textile sector, therefore, by selecting interpretivism epistemological position the researcher can find thick interpretation and rich understanding about the issues of textile sector for suggesting the practical recommendations. It is necessary to understand context and time bound motives, reasons, meanings and other kind of subjective experiences of outcome and failure of the textile industrial polices in Pakistan. The subjective experiences and meanings assigned by different 'social actors' is most important to understand the institutional coordination and attitude toward the textile industry development policies.

According to Ocampo "the strategy of industrialization and export promotion advocated by ECLAC was also tied in with short-term macroeconomic policy because of the institution's obsession with maintaining competitive exchange rates, which were viewed as an essential ingredient of proactive policies to foster production sector diversification" (Rodrik et al., 2004). A recent research has justified the ECLAC's "obsession" to maintain competitive exchange rate by proving that real exchange rates act as main determinant of the economic growth. In 1970s, Southern Cone countries` experience showed that when move towards the liberalize trade is combined with opening balance of capital account; it may lead to non-occurrence of possible real depreciation (Blackie, & Turner, 2018). However, this combination may also yield totally opposite outcome: real appreciation that may be disincentive for industrialization and exports. For productive transformation strategies, it is important to wisely manage exchange rate across entire business cycle. Based on this need to develop a growth strategy that couple countercyclical macroeconomic policy together

with proactive strategies for the diversification of production structure, legal, technological, educational and institutional strategies with major priority giving to industrialization it shows that there is need to interpret the links between all of the mentioned institutions for successful outcome of textile industrial policies outcomes in Pakistan which is why interpretivism epistemological position is being taken for this research.

Table 4.5 Ontology influence on the selection of epistemological position (Naeem, 2019a).

Constructionist and interpretative researchers assume that individually constructed and changing reality and access to the shared dynamics is only possible via social constructions like shared meanings and language (Naeem, M. (2019e, Naeem, 2019a). (see figure 4.3). Therefore, constructionist and interpretative research focus on both content of the empirical data and how content generates via language practices. The research that is based on these philosophical stances cannot predefine independent and dependent variables, however, focuses on full density of the human sense as situation emerges (Ali, S& Naeem, 2019). Additionally, it is

assumed that same data can be interpreted in many possible, potentially meaningful ways. Neoliberal approach towards industrial policy in developed economies is recently contrasted by numerous trends. This suggests that industrial policy should re-emerge (van Zanden, 2009). Firstly, recent financial crisis has triggered many governments to actively implement such policies that can save organizations and industries (such as through bail outs), create fiscal stimulus and combat unemployment (Mathews, & Tan, 2014). Secondly, as markets have become globalised it becomes necessary to stimulate the regional development and care for local industry (Bakker, 2013). Thirdly, structural changes within economy further extend the industrial policy to new industries (Alshumaimri, et al., 2010). However, industrial policy developed in organized and strategic manner particularly in aligns with innovation policy and technology. These policies in EU and US are particularly directed towards research-industry cooperation, private-public partnerships and regional specialization and clustering. This new industrial policy has been implemented in EU since 2005 with a sound horizontal component, however with tailored policy measures related to specific industries and sectors of strategic significance (Zourek [2007](#)). As compare to previous neoliberal approach and interventionist' approach, this approach is relatively less extreme. This approach has been labelled as 'matrix approach' by Earle, & Gehlbach, (2015) and as 'pragmatic' by Hendrickson, (2015). As the figure below shows there is need to interpret the all factors below to understand the textile industrial policies as shown in figure 4.6 below

Figure 4.16 Interpretivism of the industrial factors

4.6 RESEARCH APPROACH

One amongst these approaches is related to ways through which knowledge can be best acquired (Balnaves, & Caputi, 2001). According to one view, knowledge is primarily induction based – ‘bottom-up’ approach that derives patterns from the observations of surroundings (Rugg, & Petre, 2007). Contrary to that, those who hold the view that knowledge is deduction based argue that knowledge acquisition is ‘top-down’ process in which logically derived hypotheses or propositions are subjected to rigorous tests against observations (Williams, & Vogt, 2011). Alternatively speaking, inductive processes use evidence as origin of conclusion – firstly collect the evidence then built up theories and knowledge on the evidence (Naeem, 2019d). Whereas deductive processes involve evidence as a support for conclusion – firstly develop the hypothesis then collect the evidence to reject or accept the hypothesis (Brewerton, & Millward, 2001).

Figure 4.17 Inductive versus deductive research approach (Walliman, 2010)

Often, the Qualitative study is illustrated as inductive process – a misleading simplification (Donley, 2012). Wilkinson, et al., (2002) argue that nothing is pure ‘deductive’ or pure ‘inductive’. For instance, when inductive researchers produce and interpret the data, it is impossible to approach it with empty mind (Walliman, 2010) see figure 4.7. Though, inductive researchers do not test the hypothesis, but questions they ask, data they generate and analytical methods they employ will be definitely influenced by deductively derived assumptions from previous studies in their area of interest (Naeem, 2019c). Likewise, deductive researchers have to test the hypotheses that will have been drawn on existing theory, which has been derived inductively from previous observations (Cohen, et al., 2017).

Figure 4.18 Relation of subjectivism with inductive research approach

As constructionism is legitimate paradigm therefore it is useful to conduct qualitative research generated as a response to quantitative methodological efforts to reconcile post-positivism and positivism (Cassell, et al., 2017). Frost, (2011) world's most famous qualitative researchers mapped out the incompatibility of constructionism and positivism through series of black & white contrasts (Naeem, 2019b). From ontological perspective, actors of the research construct multiple realities therefore research is based on relativist ontology according to which no possible accurate reality actually exists (Matsumoto, et al., 2011). Whereas from interpretivism epistemological perspective, they present researcher is taking subject-subject position but there is inextricable connection between values and facts which is best align with inductive research approach (see figure above). The research is actually value-bound as known and knower are inseparable. Likewise, naturalists, they also align to belief that the research is context and time bound, so generalisation is impossible (Margolis, & Pauwels, 2011). While considering casual relationships, they argue that differentiating causes from the effects is not possible. Concerning theory-research relationship is last principle of the constructivism (Atkinson, 2011). As discussed above that constructivist research is consistent with inductive reasoning by arguing from specific to more general which is why inductive research approach is being taken for this research. However, from methodological perspectives, it hermeneutically proceeds by showing each construction as accurate as possible to

dialectically contrast and compare it with intention to reach and generate substantial consensus (Bowling, et al., 2005). As the major objective of the research is to propose as best industrial policies for textile industry of Pakistan to improve the industry performance which why there inductive research approach is being employed for this research because the inductive research approach is best to induct the qualitative data into the form final framework and proposal. The figure 4.9 below shows that major elements of the research and their qualitative interpretation and induction toward the final proposal of this research.

Figure 4.19 Industrial policies interpretation required induction and qualitative inquiry

4.7 QUALITATIVE RESEARCH METHOD

Qualitative research generally describes as interpretative, naturalistic approach that concerns with investigation the phenomena ‘from the interior’ and takes research participants’ accounts and perspectives as opening point (Cohen, et al., 2011).

According to Denzin and Lincoln (2011), though qualitative research is inherently diverse but can be defined as a series of material, interpretive practices based on which the world becomes visible and transformed. Alternatively speaking, these practices transformed the entire world into set of representations such as photographs, recordings, memos, interviews, conversations and fieldnotes. Therefore, it inquires a phenomenon in its natural settings of Pakistan textile industry, focusing on interpreting or making sense of the phenomena in relation with meanings of different institutional, political, economic and technological factors to make effective industrial policies.

Specific methods of data generation such as in-depth and semi-structured interviews, focus groups and observational methods have been pointed out for qualitative studies (Jones, I& Gratton, 2015). However, there is considerable variation among qualitative researchers regarding to what extent they use these methods (Coolican, 2018). Walker, (2010) described that qualitative study often associates with particular form of data, generally involves images or words instead of numbers (Ember, & Ember, 2009). The variation in richness and volume of the qualitative data depends on the distinct approaches used by the qualitative researchers for interpretation and analysis of the data and types of research output derive from the qualitative study. Another thing that differentiates the qualitative study is that it generates hypotheses from data analysis instead of stating it at outset (Teater, et al., 2017). Moreover, other authors focus on those characteristics of the research design which may identify the study as a “qualitative study” and concerns with ‘how’, ‘what’ and ‘why’ questions instead of ‘how many’, flexibility of research design and focus on the processes (Saunders, et al., 2007). Therefore, qualitative research proved helpful to understand what type of the crucial factors in textile industry of Pakistan, why these factors are crucial and how these issues can be sorted to improve the overall textile industry performance. Additionally, the qualitative research method is also aligning with the overall philosophical position of this research as shown in figure below.

4.8 DATA COLLECTION

4.8.1 Semi-Structured detailed Interviews

There are different data collection methods which are used in qualitative studies. These methods are group discussion, observation, document analysis, and interviews method (Gill et al., 2008; Cassell, & Symon, 2004). It has found that in qualitative studies rich insights can be obtained using narratives, stories and diaries, observation of participations (Garner, & Scott, 2013). Among these methods, semi-structured interview method is most useful for current research because it provides flexibility to modify, add, or delete questions during the interview stages so that researcher can bring relevant data about the proposed objectives of a study (Galletta, 2013). On the other hand, other open-ended method is not useful because it takes more efforts, time, and become impossible for researcher to keep the participants on track during the interview (Alshenqeeti (2014). Therefore, present study has used semi-structured interview (using face to face approach) is most suitable method because it provides edge to researcher for adding or deleting research questions as well as create frankness with participants so that they can share data without any hesitation (Galletta, 2013; Horton, et al., 2004).

The researchers get involved with respondents by using semi-structured detailed interviews that include pre-set guided questions (Walliman, 2006). According to Matthews, & Ross, (2010) the justification behind selecting this type of interview plan was that it can enable respondents to make additional conversation encouraged by a set of structured questions. A specific time duration was set for each respondent for the research interview, i.e. thirty to sixty minutes. This is consistent with the time duration that is considered ideal for interviews, which is anywhere between thirty minutes to less than an hour so as to stimulate better focus of respondents (Bode, & Arthur, 2014).

Consent form and invitation letters were sent electronically to the interviewees who met the predetermined criteria set by the researcher. Once they gave their consent to participate in the study, they were asked what location they found best for interviews. By offering the respondents a choice to pick a location lays foundation for a meaningful result of interviews. Bernard, (2011) explain that as indicated by the literature, giving the choice to respondents to pick the place they want to be

interviewed at makes them feel more comfortable with the research. Once the location was chosen, interviews were recorded digitally while researcher makes notes during the proceedings. Notes were made regarding the body language of respondents. Bradford, & Cullen, (2012) stated that a crucial part is played by vocal and non-vocal interaction to understand the perspective of respondents and the meaning that is assigned to that phenomenon. Saunders, et al., (2012) state that semi-structure interview questions were particularly constructed in congruence to answer the primary research questions. Moreover, the experiential knowledge produced was improved with the researcher's direct involvement in research. Moreover, on the basis of semi-structured interviews, the current questions were adjusted so that during the course of interview new questions were added where needed.

4.8.2 Sample Selection

Consistency is very important, just like in any research, when decision has to be made about selecting cases for sampling as it affects the research results. It is also applicable in context of high-end disruptive innovation. (Saunders, et al., 2009) According to Howitt, (2019) when sample size has to be selected the fundamental principle is to choose a sample that depends on N (number of sample) which can explain the research purpose. Robinson (2013) and Marshall (1996) asserted that literature also supports this through different academics. However, there are still limitations to this technique as it offers no guidance for deciding N. In the past, rule of thumbs was used by academics by making comparison for N for previous studies in order to get an estimated number for analysis. Martin, & Bridgmon, (2012) explains that N in a qualitative study depends on saturation point where there is no new information collection. The basis of this research was a combined or mixed sampling technique and was chosen because of the struggle faced during the process of collecting data. According to recent studies which have used the thematic analysis, researchers have highlighted that 30 or more respondents are enough to draw meaningful and precise results from qualitative studies (Naeem, 2019a; Naeem, 2019b). Therefore, current study also aims to collect data from 30 respondents as it is very hard to meet the owners, senior managers, and other stakeholders of textile industry who have lot of responsibilities as well as limited time for other than business activities.

However, in the beginning certain textile executives agreed to participate in the study, but several others refused to contribute to the process of data collection. Furthermore, sampling is particularly important for qualitative research because of the richness of information provided by it (Sloan, & Quan-Haase, 2017). As a result, snowball sampling proved to be very helpful to get cases for the research that were rich in information. The chosen strategy should be selected based on its ability to generate desired results. The following table provides a summarized description of different strategies

Table 4.6 Sampling strategies

No	Strategy	Illustration
.		
1	Combination or Mixed Sampling	A mix or combination of the following strategies is used for sampling; multiple interests are addressed by using multiple strategies
2	Convenience Sampling	This type of sampling is the most convenient but weakest (in terms of credibility) and saves money, time and effort. This may generate cases with poor information as the selection criteria was completely based on convenient accessibility. For instance, neighbors and co-workers are considered for sampling
3	Confirming & Disconfirming Sampling	This type of sampling is based on the method to select expected and exceptional cases that surpass the expectations, encompassing both disconfirmed as well as confirmed cases. For instance, if undesirable academic results were being studied by a researcher regarding environmental aspects like lack of funding or low parental involvement. The interest of the researcher would be in cases that provide proof to the undesirable effects of such aspects on academic performance, and would encompass cases which disconfirm affects like when no negative association exists
4	Homogenous Sampling	This type of sampling involves the cases that have similar experiences and

- backgrounds and is significant for a research that has the primary motivation to simplify analysis and reduce variation. Furthermore, it helps researcher in facilitating interviews of groups and is typically used for focus group interviews
- 5 Critical Case Sampling

This method is useful when exploratory qualitative research is being conducted and typically used in case of limited resources, and a decisive part is played by a small number of cases.
 - 6 Intensity Sampling

The aim is to look for rich patterns of primary phenomenon. Nevertheless, these cases aren't severe and this strategy is useful to collect limited number of cases that are rich in information. With this strategy an in-depth insight is achieved into the phenomenon that is being investigated
 - 7 Criterion Sampling

Case selection on the basis of preset criteria to obtain rich information and prevent quality assurance problems. For instance, the duration for stay for a surgical process is 3 days at a minimum. In these type of cases researchers may decide on criteria to choose the cases that were there for more than 3 days.
 - 8 Extreme Case Sampling

The key focus is on unusual or special cases. For instance, cases highlight success, failure, notable results. They offer important insight into specific phenomenon that proves to be valuable lesson
 - 9 Politically Important Sampling

This type of sampling is a variation of critical case which includes the method of choosing samples that are helpful and pertinent to information in terms of political moment. For example, if voter behavior is being investigated by a researcher, he may consider the latest election
 - 10 Snowball Sampling

This sampling uses assistance from others for identifying cases rich in information. the first step is to ask

questions that are known to the respondents. Later, the researcher collects nominations to talk to other professionals and the sample increases till the key names start to repeat meaning it is possible to make a sensible final selection

- 11 Maximum Variation Sampling
This type of sampling is a variation of heterogenous sampling which can capture widespread selection of viewpoints on subject under study. The variation viewpoints range from extreme to archetypal
- 12 Purposeful Random Sampling
This strategy makes random selections and adds credibility when the sample is too large to manage. However, the aim of the strategy is not to add generalizability but credibility. For example, a drug rehabilitation program consisting of 300 cases is studied. At random 10 cases may be selected by the researcher. The outcomes are generated in form of reduced judgment in this strategy due to random sampling
- 13 Opportunistic Sampling
During the process more samples are selected. This type of sampling uses unanticipated opportunities and follows new leads. For instance, the interest of a researcher may be to study awareness of a 6th grade student regarding a particular subject, and that it is helpful in including 5th grade students also, as this lets researchers have better understanding
- 14 Typical Case Sampling
The strategy involving typical or normal sample units like events, places, cases, people, and settings. In this study findings of the study are compared by utilizing this technique with similar samples. The purpose of sample is not to generalize populations, rather to illustrate other samples. Samples are selected through expert opinions. Data from past survey can also be used.
- 15 Theory-Based Sampling
Theory based sampling includes choosing samples that meet theory-driven criteria. However, just like

criterion sampling, this is done on the basis of a concept. This is useful for studies of grounded theory where the samples of incidents or people is drawn upon whereby a significant theoretical construct is represented by them

16 Stratified Purposeful Sampling

In this type of sampling, samples are chosen from within the samples. It is conducted based on particular features of specific subgroups of interest, which is useful to make comparisons. For instance, a researcher may be interested to study academic performance and will choose a sample that focuses on a group, such as various performance categories based on average. The aim of this strategy is to capture key variations

A mixed or combination purposeful sampling is applied in this research. The reason this strategy is chosen include: (1) Snowball sampling was found to be helpful where industry professionals were consulted for recommendations for respondents who had more information for the research. (2) Homogenous sampling was found to be helpful in choosing senior executive level managers who are experienced and knowledgeable. (3) Criterion sampling was significant in terms of textile firm to create a foundation of preset criteria. The table 4.4 below offers some criteria to select case for data rich in information (Patton, 2015).

Table 4.7 Criteria for Inclusion and Exclusion of Cases

Criteria	Exclusion	Inclusion
Complete legal capacity	Less than 18 years of age	Older than 18 years
Textile firm timeline	Participants who have been associated with textile for less than 10 years	Participants who have been associated with at least 10 years old
Only founders or professional executive level managers	Has professional experience less than 10 years and at a lower level than head of division/ department	Has professional experience more than 10 years and at least a head of department/ division

Business development enthusiasm/ management	Innovation development and associated role in of management	Enthusiastic for business development and associated role in low level of management	Enthusiastic for business development and associated role in top level decision making
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Numerous considerations made the basis for the criteria that was useful for selecting sample cases. Typically, the only participants included in the research were the ones who had full capacity of making contract. In Pakistan the full capacity to contract is 18 years as minimum age. As a result, the process of selecting samples excluded cases less than 18 years of age.

Furthermore, the study included participants who were either executive level managers or founders of textile firm. These participants needed to be at least head of divisions or department. Data richness was improved by including participants who had more than 10 years' experience at a senior level position. This study did not consider managers who had less than 10 years' experience.

Next criterion for the research was that all firms must have been in business for 10 years minimum. This is essential due to the evolutionary concept of disruptive innovation, and disruption happens over time. When firms with more than 10 years of business are included, it can establish certainty to some extent that they have the capacity to compete in the market. Data reputation is thus enhanced through this inclusion in the sampling criteria.

Lastly, including enthusiasm and pertinent experience in innovation management as well as business expansion is valued as they can be consulted for opinions. It is important that participants had used innovation for the development of business in order to offer pertinent testimonies. The study excluded less enthusiastic participants as it was probable that they would deviate from the original subject under study.

4.9 DATA ANALYSIS METHOD

Thematic analysis is very famous and recognized method that draws meaningful outcomes in qualitative studies (Braun et al., 2018). Themes are referred to as a type of agreement with text, yet concise, simple, short and accurate. Themes are often repeated due to their efforts in answering research questions (Alhojailan, 2012;

Braun et al., 2018; Clarke, & Braun, 2013; Javadi and Zarea, 2016). These studies also highlighted that thematic analysis can be done manually as research is involved in through the process of data collections therefore the understanding of researcher is helpful to provide further rich insights (Alhojailan, 2012; Braun et al., 2018; Clarke, & Braun, 2013; Javadi and Zarea, 2016) therefore present study has used the manual thematic analysis by following the given guidelines of Braun and Clarke (2006) for manual coding process. According to Terry et al., (2017), when researcher involved in manual coding then they can easily ensure that the repetition of ideas should not occur, and they can select only include those ideas/responses which are unique and helps to build theoretical framework. Therefore, present study did not add those responses of participants that are providing the similar ideas.

Rubin and Rubin (2011) presented arguments for thematic analysis that it is an exciting and interesting phenomenon as it helps in identifying themes with the help of data collected from interview. This type of analysis could be used for pinpointing, recording, and evaluating data so that meaningful concepts and extracts can be attained. Data in thematic analysis could be obtained by transcription of documents, interviews, videos, pictures and field notes. The assumptions of essentialist and constructionist paradigm are followed by thematic analysis. There are two major groups of data analysis, which are conventional analysis and interpretative phenomenological analysis. This study follows assumptions that are linked to interpretative phenomenological analysis which is also referred to as thematic analysis with no limitations to any kind of theory. Rayan et al (2003) believe that inductive approach derives themes, or they could be because of using the theoretical understanding like literature review professional definitions, theoretical orientations, and personal experiences. Thematic analysis and assumptions related to it in the study of Rayan et al (2003) are followed in this study. Further, qualitative analysis steps that are mentioned by Braun and Clarke (2006) are also followed in this study, from which it is concluded that constant comparative thematic analysis is best suited. Present study aims to understand subjective realities about the decline of textile industry therefore thematic analysis support to identify which are common patterns/causes of decline for Pakistani textile industry.

4.10 INVESTIGATING INTEGRITY OF RESEARCH FINDINGS

Matsumoto, et al., (2011) were the first to raise the concept of integrity of findings of research and debated that the challenge that qualitative researchers face is to determine how to make sure that respondents didn't fabricate their responses. As the aim of qualitative research is to examine the world view of respondents, they may not be willing to deliver information or may not like the researcher, and thus end up providing false information. The best strategy for qualitative researchers to deal with fabricated information, lies and evasion is to not accept information at face value and be skeptical of the information. There are other ways to deal with it that include triangulation (across researchers, methods and sources), building trust and rapport, protecting identities of respondents, effective interview techniques, navel-gazing and self-analysing researchers (Cassell, et al., 2017).

Prior studies have indicated that transferability can be used in the place of external validity, confirmability in the place of objectivity, dependability in the place of reliability, and creditability in place of internal validity (Lavrakas, 2008; Guba, & Lincoln, 1982) The transferability judgment by a prospective user is facilitated by the researcher through purposeful sampling and thick description (Bitsch, 2005). Current study results are transferable in especially in the context of developing countries where there is political instability, devaluation currency, energy crises, and inflation are same as in Pakistan. Furthermore, data obtained from Textile mills and SMEs owners and managers which allow this study to get thick description of data by choosing those participants who have rich experience and knowledge. According to researcher, confirmability means findings of this study also somewhat consistent with previous studies (Lavrakas, 2008), while dependability means how much findings are stable over the period of time (Bitsch, 2005). Current study provides more rich insights by gathering data from both SMEs and textile mills which are useful to highlight the overall decline issues of textile industry in Pakistan. Furthermore, the results of current study also offered useful insights with respect to how all the challenges are interlinked and what policies are required to address these challenges. In the context of this study, the data is collected first from textile mills owners and managers then from SME owners with the purpose to compare the results with the purpose to ensure the validity as guided in relevant studies (Abbas,

et al., 2012 Afzal, 2012; Cororaton, et al., 2008; Khan, et al., 2010; Khattak, et al., 2011; Shah, et al., 2012).

4.11 LIMITATIONS OF PROPOSED RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Interpretive or qualitative methods are usually employed when the level of information and knowledge is available in the form of subjective realities which have rich insights and useful information (Cassell, et al., 2017; Saunders, et al., 2012). However, there are some limitations of proposed research methodology for this study. Although this study is able to provide rich and useful knowledge about the selected topic, but the results of this study are verified with the help of statistical data analysis techniques. The results of qualitative studies are usually unique and not fully replicated with each other (Cassell, et al., 2017; Saunders, et al., 2012), therefore it is difficult to determine the causality in the data of this study. Qualitative studies are required labour intensive work therefore it is very important that researcher must be expert in communication as well as in qualitative data analysis techniques (Cassell, et al., 2017). Finally, there is no predetermined method to estimate about the biasness from researcher as well as participants sides (Cassell, et al., 2017).

4.12 ETHICAL CONSIDERATION

There are two distinctive steps to ethical considerations in qualitative research. The foremost step is applying research ethics in the university. Denzin and Lincoln (2005) explain that the next steps address the attention captured by the values that support the research in creating knowledge. With reference to the first concern, the standards and regulation of University of the West of Scotland (UWS) were followed by this research. According to UWS (2019) the research charted the guidelines issued by Ethics Committee to engage in Ethical Practice in Research and Scholarship. The research under study is focused on high-end disruptive innovation in terms of textile firm in Pakistan. All the information gained during the course of interviews has been utilized for informing the practices and ideas of executive managers at senior positions regarding high-end disruptive innovation. The research encompasses asking founders or executive managers of textile firm in Pakistan to contribute their knowledge. According to the present criteria for sample inclusion, it was necessary that these founders and executive managers had sufficient

experience in professional capacity. Where they were willing to contribute, matching the benchmarks, information regarding aims, data engagement, nature and scope of research interviews was given. A consent was signed by all participants before interviews were conducted.

For this study the participants were selected as per the aforementioned criteria in a private setting. Hence, it was necessary that pertinent ethical standards were discussed in general and for avoiding any conflict in interest. During the course of this study, the below mentioned ethical concerns were handled:

1. There must be no compromise of respondents' privacy and their identities were to be protected. No access to interview materials was provided to managers of the organizations, and the data was to be used only for this study. No third party was given access to data collected and the interviewees' identities were not revealed.
2. Participants were involved in this research according to their voluntary willingness and carried out without any obligation. At any point of the study participants can retract without worrying about anything. In the event that a participant withdraws, all information regarding the participants is destroyed completely.
3. Participants were clearly explained about the dual nature of the role of researcher in acting as an interviewer and researcher both
4. Participants were informed about all expected publications in future regarding this study
5. Lastly, before interviews were conducted anyone involved in this study was informed about the relevant ethical standards.

CHAPTER 5: RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

5.1 INTRODUCTION

The manual thematic analysis has been conducted in this study. According to Boyatzis (1998), manual thematic analysis is best method when researcher fully involved in data collection and fully familiar with the research data. Researchers have recommended the steps in order to follow the thematic analysis process which is also used for this study (Aronson, 1995; Boyatzis, 1998). These steps are, transcribe the data which is either written or recorded, create notes for important things related to your objectives, assign code for data set, try to search the suitable themes, try to review major themes & sub-themes and its connections, assign the name to themes and sub-themes, report and finalize the data. The study has created a major theme: current position and causes of delineation in textile industry in Pakistan while sub-themes are existing Infrastructure, government planning and support, and national and textile industry culture. The study has created a major theme: enablers and recommendation for textile industry in Pakistan while sub-themes are advance technology, role of government, and advanced practices. The study has collected data from textile mills owners, general managers, senior managers, SME owners and managers who have plenty of experience in textile industry as well as monitoring the policies of government as well as international market in order to keep their business alive. The details of these participants have been given in below table.

Table 5.8 Participants detail

Participant's code	Company type	Position within the company	Years within the industry	Age
A1	Textile mill	Owner	18 years	47 years
A2	SME	Owner	15 years	49 years
A3	Textile mill	General manager	21 years	53 years

A4	SME	Deputy General manager	17 years	52 years
A5	Textile mill	Senior Manager	7 years	35 years
A6	textile mill	Deputy General manager	10 years	42 years
A7	SME	Manager	16 years	51 years
A8	Textile mill	Senior Manager	5 years	34 years
A9	SME	Owner	13 years	47 years
A10	Textile mill	Owner	15 years	49 years
A11	SME	Owner	15 years	43 years
A12	Textile mill	Manager	12 years	54 Years
A13	Textile mill	Manager	4 years	35 years
A14	Textile mill	Senior manager	9 years	42 years
A15	Textile mill	Owner	21 years	52 years
A16	Textile mill	Manager	12 years	44 years
A17	Textile mill	Assistant manager	4 years	35 Years
A18	SME	Owner	16 years	47 years
A19	textile mill	Owner	13 years	45 years
A20	textile mill	Manager	3 year	31 years
A21	SME	Owner	11 years	42 years
A22	SME	Owner	14 years	51 years
A23	textile mill	Owner	9 years	43 years
A24	SME	Owner	8 years	41 years
A25	SME	Owner	12 years	44 years

Table 5.9 Current position and causes of delinaton in textle industry in Pakistan

Theme	Definition	Codes	Keywords
Current position of textile industry in Pakistan	Find out the current position of textile industry in Pakistan as it highlights what are the opportunities and improvements area for further development.	1. Existing Infrastructure	High number of SMEs Main source of revenue High exports Best cotton producer Limited capital for SMEs

- High cost of production
 - Low research and development
 - Low use of latest technology
 - Limited production
 - Low performance
 - High exports of raw material
 - Traditional ways of work
 - More labour and low wages
 - Weak international relations
 - Limited focus on textile related education
 - Environmental and climate change
2. Government planning and Support
- Economic crises
 - Political instability
 - High taxes
 - High corruption
 - Limited support
 - Lack of investors
 - More strikes
 - More child labour
 - Energy crises
 - Devaluation of currency
 - Terrorism attacks
3. National and textile industry culture
- High uncertainty avoidance
 - More politics and influence
 - Lack of future planning
 - Low openness to change
 - More conflicts
 - Culture inertia
 - More power-distance

Low use of technology
Low awareness about ICT
Low level of education
Under-developed ICT
Infrastructure

Theme 1:

5.2 CURRENT POSITION AND CAUSES OF DELINEATION IN TEXTILE INDUSTRY IN PAKISTAN

It is very important to analyse the internal and external factors which positively and negatively influence the current position of textile industry in Pakistan. The infrastructure of textile, education, government support, national and organizational culture, use of technology, cost of production, and level of skills may vary among developing countries, emerging economies, and developed countries. These factors directly or indirectly influence the current position of textile industry in Pakistan. Without analysing the importance and intensity of these factors influence on textile industry, we cannot determine what are strengths and weaknesses and how these weaknesses or challenges may be addressed in the specific context of Pakistani culture. Researcher has gathered data from the owners of SMEs as well as the management and owners of textile mills in Pakistan. Then present study has thematic analysis in which they found current position of textile industry through three different codes such as existing infrastructure in which participants have discussed all the strengths and barriers that can positively or negatively influencing the performance of textile industry in Pakistan. In the code of government planning and support, participants have discussed all those factors that create barriers to get the maximum output with cooperation of government planning and support. Finally, participants have also discussed regarding how these national culture as well as textile culture are interlinked and how the features of culture are influencing the levels of performance and output.

Sub Theme 1:

5.2.1 Existing Infrastructure and current position of textile industry

Participant A1 has discussed about current infrastructure of textile industry:

Although textile industry is known as main contributor of GDP in Pakistan economy. But we are facing many challenges with respect to technology upgradation, infrastructure development, as well as low level of government support and political instability. For example, currently most of the textile mills have traditional working procedures such as manual procurement, more paperwork, cash handling manually as well as through bank, and low level of advance technologies for ginning and spinning. Due to these challenges, employees are spending greater time to complete their work which increase the cost of production and decrease the level of competitive advantages for us. I think.... we need to develop the education system that can deliver those competent persons which can bring organizational changes through the implementation of industry 4 technology in Pakistan.

Participant A4 has shared fruitful views regarding the current infrastructure of textile industry

Currently we are producing high quality cotton fabrics that increased our profitability. We are exporting cotton to international market which increase our profit margin compared to local market. Our government has weak relationship with many neighbour countries which has limited our market because we are unable to sell our products in few neighbour countries. Further, due to obsolete technology and energy crises we have close our SME for two years because if we produced by spending huge budget on electricity and gas supplies then It could bring huge financial losses. The one of the reasons is that other neighbour countries are producing yarn and fabrics on low cost such as China and India. Further, climate and environmental changes reduce the cotton production in Pakistan as most of time heavy rain negatively influence the production target of target.

Participant A5 shared thoughts about the current infrastructure and its challenges

“Textile sector has too many opportunities for growth as it is one of the largest contributors of our economy as well as has attraction of international investors. However, there are many challenges which negatively influenced the production and performance of textile industry in Pakistan. For instance, currently we are producing high quality cotton but by spending greater cost on energy, labour, as well as high financial debts and taxes. These factors have increased our cost of production and decreased the level of profit margin. Further, our education sector is unable to produce those people who can bring new ideas and advance use of technology. I think.... education sector is more focused on business administration subjects as well as theoretical work. Further, more than 90-percent textile industry has not research department that’s why we are still using traditional way which increase our time as well as cost of production.”

Participant A2 has shared experiences about current infrastructure of textile industry

There are huge number of SMEs which are currently producing major part of yarn or fabric in textile industry. Therefore, we have known as top ten cotton producing country as well as standing at eight position with respect to exporting the textile production in Asia. Even as an owner, I cannot count the number of small units, large spinning units, and ginning units. We have known as best cotton producer in Asia and textile manufacturing industry is known as largest source of revenue generator for Pakistani economy. However, still we are facing number of challenges that currently negatively impact especially the performance of SMEs. In textile industry, SMEs have challenges such as limited capital, unskilled labour, traditional technology models, and limited focus on research and new ways. The government is unable to provide a support which must be required to get maximum output standards.

Participant A3 shared the information about current infrastructure

In textile sector, we are using obsolete technology because we have not specific research and development department that can bring new ways to reduce the cost of production. Therefore, we have more challenges with respect to the maintain the cost of production especially when we are competing in international markets. Even we have seen worst conditions where our mill has sent the raw material to other countries for printing the high-quality fabrics because we are preparing the final output by spending more cost and average level of quality. Now we have upgrading our technology so that we can increase the production by maintaining the level of quality.

The first sub-theme (i.e. existing Infrastructure and current position of textile industry) has discussed what are the strengths and weakness which are influencing on the cost of production, competitive advantage, production and performance of textile industry in Pakistan. Participants have discussed there are hundreds of small units, large spinning units, and ginning units in one province of Pakistan. Therefore, textile industry is major contributor in GDP and recognized as a main source of income for Pakistani economy. It is also revealed that textile industry is in top ten ranking in the context of largest exporting products of textile as well as best cotton producer. Some participants have revealed that the Pakistani textile sector has too many opportunities for growth as it is one of the largest contributors of our economy as well as has attraction of international investors.

There are many challenges or weaknesses in current infrastructure which limited the growth opportunities in textile industry. First, there are hundreds of SMEs which have many challenges compared to big organizations such as textile mills. For example, SMEs owners have revealed that there have limited financial capital because they

are not publishing their financial reports therefore there are limited opportunities with respect to private investors as well as banks. It is also found that these lenders are offering loans at high interest rate which may increase the cost of production especially for those SMEs which are focused in local market. Most of participants have revealed that they are using obsolete technologies which requires more repair, maintenance, and monitoring of units and these factors have increased the cost of production. Some respondents have highlighted that how they are enforced to sell raw material to other countries when they faced energy crises, strikes, and high cost of production. It is also found that more than 90-percent textile mills and SMEs have not research and development department therefore they are using traditional way to produce yarn and fabric. Finally, the education sector has many challenges therefore textile industry unable to find out those talent people who can formulate new changes by adopting and implementation of advanced technologies. They have suggested that education sector should specify subjects on textile sector as most of students are following the studies of business administration which are known as more generic and limited to theoretical concepts.

Sub Theme 2:

5.2.2 Government planning and support and its impact on textile industry

Participant A6 shared experiences regarding government planning and support for textile industry:

“Pakistan economy is current facing economic crises because the amount of national debts has been exceeded from US\$92 billion. As a result, there are more taxes and conditions by those international funders for different industries. For example, International monetary fund (IMF) has imposed more conditions regarding devaluation of currency. As a result, we are paying very higher cost to import latest technologies and other machinery from foreign countries. These conditions have created challenges as government has unable to give any relief to textile industry and additional taxes have increased the cost of production for big organizations as well as SMEs. Therefore, they are more shutdowns and trade unions with the purpose to resolve these types of issues.”

Participant A4 offered fruitful views about government planning and support for textile industry:

Here I want to say that there is no government planning and support for textile industry as the government has increased taxes and tariffs on exports and imports. The government

has borrowed so much money from USA, china, and IMF. Due to high level of corruption and consistent devaluation of currency, now we are unable to import high technology and other machinery as it can increase our cost of production easily. Furthermore, due to high taxes, most of SMEs have shut down because they cannot get any support and suffered due to huge financial losses.

Participant A9 highlighted about government planning and support for textile industry:

The lack of planning about electric short fall as well as gas shortage created worst situation for textile industry. Many small and large units could not maximize the production and saw very worst conations. All this happened because the selected politicians were corrupt, and they did money laundering at very high level. These types of challenges have negatively impacted on our currency and increased the taxes, tariffs, and heavy duties on textile industry. These tensions have created more uncertainty for the survival of SMEs which are making low level of profits.

Participant A7 discussed thoughts about government planning and support for textile industry:

“Unfortunately, I could not remember any serious efforts which has shown the democratic governments for the development and growth of textile industry in Pakistan. Even textile industry is one of the major contributors in GDP still we have seen energy crises from previous two decades and as a result most of small textile units have shut down because they are unable to afford energy back due to limited financial capital. The political instability and weak relationship with neighbour countries also limited the growth opportunities because there are limited private investors as well as limited sellers and buyers from other countries. I believe.....most of Pakistani governments have brought more challenges for us which negatively influence our growth as well as profitability rates.”

Participant A8 told about government planning and support for textile industry:

We have seen many terrorism attacks, political instability, and high level of corrupt politicians in our country. Therefore, we are paying high taxes and bearing high cost of production as well as low level of competitive advantages compared to other Asian countries such as China and India. Due to terrorism attacks, the textile industry is also negatively influenced as buyers and employees are feeling insecure and unsafe. The government has not enough financial support as they must pay high instalments of interest on national debt and facing budget deficit from many decades. Due to deviation currency and high level of

poverty, there is high unskilled labour such as children who have age of 15 years to 18 years.

The second theme (i.e. government planning and support and its impact on textile industry) has described various situations which has increased the challenges for textile industry. For instance, it has found that Pakistan has borrowed more than US\$92 billion dollars from USA, China, and IMF. Consequently, it has brought more pressures on currency by devaluation as well as by paying higher rate of interest instalments. Unfortunately, this borrowed money is used by corrupt politicians by making personal assets. However, participants have told that they are bearing the burden of that corruption in terms of heavy taxes, tariffs, and duties on imports and exports. Furthermore, they are unable to import heavy machinery and updated technology because of high devaluation of currency as well imports can increase the cost of production. Due to high taxes and more financial burden, many SMEs from textile sector has completely shut down because these SMEs have limited financial funds, limited to local markets, and limited competitive advantage as well as government support.

Participants have also discussed how the government could not plan regarding the energy supply and as a result there is high load shedding for electricity and gas in Pakistan. Most of the corrupt practices in society such as stealing of energy sources and ultimately it increased the unit price for textile industry. These types of challenges have increased challenges such as high cost of production, more strikes, lower wage rate, and high involvement of cheap labour (i.e. child labour). The high duration of electricity is one of the reasons that create more challenges for the survival of industries and SMEs. Although SMEs and Textile mills have backup in the shape of UPS, power generators, and solar plats but it is very expensive to operate, maintain, and keep in workable conditions especially when they are dealing with heavy machinery. These type of temporary energy sources are one of the reasons that the quality, quantity, as well as the timely completion of textile orders is not possible, and it is bringing more losses and lower level of buyer's interest to place orders. The duration of electric shortage is also very long, and government of Pakistan has increased the rate of electricity and defined more strict punishment for those who are stealing electricity. However, the increase of electricity rates has

decreased the textile profit rates, labour wages and shifts, and opportunities for more production.

Due to lower level of profitability and high level of debt-to-equity ratio as well as lack of trend in publishing the financial reports, textile industry is struggling to achieve the high level of financial support or investor confidence. Due to the low income of families, most people are unable to find out employment opportunities and as a result more child labour and limited skills. Furthermore, due to the government policies and involvement in other fights brought many security and safety challenges such as suicide bombers and terrorist attacks. These attacks negatively influenced the performance of textile industry as there are limited number of buyers and sells. Participants also discussed that insecurity and unsafety brought many other challenges such as low level of investors and many small units are closed because they cannot survive in temporary shutdowns.

Sub Theme 3:

5.2.3 National and organizational culture and their influence on the performance of textile industry

Participant A10 has discussed about national and organizational culture and their impact on textile industry:

"I think... the national culture has brought many challenges such as people are not use to for advance technology and new skills. The national culture is based on collectivism therefore this high-power distance and high number of unions for organizational politics. As a result, there are more strikes, call for shutdowns, and protests for saving the interests of few individuals. These types of factors always brought challenges such as we are unable to complete the orders on time and we have to bear more losses due to unnecessary delay to our clients.

Participant A13 discussed about national and organizational culture and their impact on textile industry:

The buyers, suppliers, sellers, and investors of local textile industry is not very use to for using high level of technology such as e-procurement, brick and click business models, and e-banking. As a result, most of the employees are doing paper-based work and spending most of their time on completing the manual procedures. These manual procedures have

increased the costs as well as employee efforts. I have seen always resistance in employees whenever we tried to change their working procedures. This may be happened because people are more comfortable in repetition of work or felt uncomfortable to do accept new technologies and new practices for improve the work.

Participant A12 about national and organizational culture and their impact on textile industry:

The ICT infrastructure is not fully developed, and we are not using e-procurement, brick and click business or e-commerce business models. The one of the reasons is that we are focused in present and we are not focusing on how we can create competitive advantage by adopting new technologies and new brains. The culture inertia is one of the main reasons to enhance challenges as most of the people are not comfortable to accept new challenges and working procedures. Most people who are working in shifts are those who have low level of qualification because most them belongs to those families who are living below the poverty line. As a result, we are unable to create improvement in the processes and procedures as most people are only focused to complete their duty hours on repetitive work.

Participant A14 said about how about national and organizational culture and their impact on textile industry:

In the 15-years of my experience in textile industry, I found most of employees are not very motivational to accept new workplace changes such as e-procurement, e-banking, e-commerce model, BPR, and lean manufacturing practices. Therefore, there is high repetition of work and the productivity of employees is very limited. The one of the reasons is that our educational system obsolete as it is not following the advanced practical knowledge especially in the context of textile industry. Therefore, our employees are unable to accept the advanced level of technologies (i.e. laser printing, digital printing, and 3D Printers).

Participant A11 stated about national and organizational culture and their impact on textile industry:

Most of time we are using traditional technologies such as manual procurement procedures, manual cash handling, and paper-based work environment. Most of experienced people are not able to learn new skills and adopt new technology. On the other hand, competent persons are asking hire salary packages which are not affordable for SMEs. I have seen that our education system is unable to produce those people who have practical as well as advance knowledge about the advance procedures and technologies of textile industry compared to India and China. Therefore, we are unable to accept new changes and technologies at fast rate and constantly.

The third theme (i.e. national and organizational culture and their influence on the performance of textile industry) revealed that the Pakistani culture has higher level of collectivism, uncertainty avoidance, resistance to change, and limited planning. High collectivism and power distance always increase organizational politics in which few powerful people gain power while other persons cannot protect their personal interests. Due to these factors, there are more common that people do protests, strikes, and shutdown the production. Another example is government and textile industry could not determine the nature of challenges such as energy crisis, results of increasing national debts, high taxes, and devaluation of current impact on textile industry. Furthermore, the level of technology is obsolete such as limited awareness about laser printing, digital printing, and 3D Printers. Therefore, these textile mills have traditional working procedures such as manual procurement in which most of orders placing, suppliers record, and inventory is recorded manually of simple software's. Furthermore, due to high cybercrime attacks, these textile mills cannot adopt the e-banking system because buyers and suppliers are more comfortable to complete transaction manually. The other reason maybe they have not trust on banking system because there are some stories about how hackers have taken millions from online accounts of an Islamic bank. Therefore, these types of challenges must be addressed if government, owners, and other stakeholders want to bring significant changes in textile industry in Pakistan.

Main theme:

5.3 ENABLERS AND RECOMMENDATION FOR TEXTILE INDUSTRY IN PAKISTAN

Table 5.10 Enablers and recommendaton for textle industry in Pakistan

Theme	Definition	Codes	Keywords
Current position of textile industry in Pakistan	Find out the current position of textile industry in Pakistan as it highlights what are the opportunities and improvements area for further development.	1. Advance technology	Use industry 4 practices E-procurement Brick and click Training and Skill Development Research and development Robotic in industry Online banking system Laser printing Digital printing 3D Printers
		2. Role of Government	E-government Digital open government

			Political stability Economic stability Stabilize currency Low taxes Investment in energy More loans for SMEs Safety and Security Improve education sector Transparency and accountability Investment in ICT infrastructure Fair justice practices Invest to bring industry 4
		3. Advanced practises	HPWS practices Lean manufacturing Cyber sharing Publication of financial reports Conduct international seminars and conferences Create own energy sources Developed ICT Infrastructure Data Exchange with Partners

In previous chapter, current study has explored the importance and position of textile industry in Pakistan. Participants have reported the textile sector as main source of income generation, best yarn and cotton producer, and high demand and value in international Asian markets. However, they have discussed many challenges which negatively influenced the profits, performance, survival, and growth of textile industry in Pakistan. For example, traditional working practices, limited use of technology, under-developed ICT infrastructure, energy crises, devaluation of currency, national debts and budget deficit decreased the profits, performance, survival, and growth of textile industry in Pakistan. In the presence of these challenges, current study has brought which enablers can improve the current recession of textile industry. In the light of main theme, the study has brought three main codes: advanced technology, role of government, and advanced practices. In advanced technology, respondents have suggested which automatic systems must be adopted with the purpose to improve the level of performance and current position in textile industry. In role of government, respondents suggested the government must facilitate the textile

industry by investing in energy sources, ICT infrastructure such as e-government and digital open government. In advanced practices, respondents have mentioned all those practices that can improve the level of employees and textile industry performance. The detail of respondent's ideas has been given below for further understanding.

Sub-theme 1:

5.3.1 Advanced technology can improve the current position of textile industry in Pakistan

Participant A15 shared about how advanced technology can bring improvements in current position of textile sector:

"I think.....adoption and implementation of industry 4 has become necessary especially if our textile industry want to decrease the cost of production as well as decision making. By adopting the industry 4, we can decrease the number of employees in operation department as system are more capable to control the production and taking accurate decisions. It can systematize the data which may be easier to share with marketers, buyers, and international investors. Ultimately, the adoption of industry 4 technologies can easily improve the level of performance, online record, online data sharing, decision making, and quality of textile commodities.

Participant A19 advanced technology can bring improvements in current position of textile sector:

It has become important that we should adopt recent technologies such as laser printing, digital printing, and 3D Printers. Our textile industry is suffering because we have no research and development department that can motivate and bring improvements in ginning and spinning units. Therefore, we are spending high cost on those manufacturing processes which have become obsolete in advanced nations. Most of these countries have adopted robotic system for handling material related to textile. In future, we are unable to sell our products in international market especially in the presence of China and India if we will not adopt these automatic systems for fabrics and yarn production.

Participant A16 discussed about how advanced technology can bring improvements in current position of textile sector:

Currently our mill and other small textile units are using manual procurement where we must maintain ledgers, supplier invoices, transactions, and other information related to contracts. It increases the time, cost, and efforts of employees. By implementation of e-procurement

system, it can add value in supply chain management by bringing online record related to e-informing, e-auctioning, vendor management, order status, e-tendering, and optimal stock decisions. We are strong thinking to bring this system at the end of this year because it can improve the transparency and accountability as well as performance level of employees.

Participant A18 shared experiences discussed about the use of advance technologies in the context of textile industry:

We are using manual and traditional practices in SME therefore we are unable to gain maximum production, transparency, and high level of employees and SME performance. Recently we are focusing to bring e-procurement and online banking system in our SME. By adopting these systems, we can produce most of the data online and it can save our resources as we are paying high salaries for most of the unproductive working procedures and practices. We have capital and good reputation in market; therefore, we believe that we can make the difference by digitalize our SME.

Participant A17 shared views about how advanced technology can bring improvements in current position of textile sector:

The adoption of brick and click business model can create online record and information about our commodities. We are interested to adopt this system and we are conducted several meetings in which we have discussed the feasibility report as well as cost and benefits analysis. Therefore, I strongly recommend that this system must be adopted by in every textile mill because it can create online data about the products as well as it increases the enquires and purchasing orders from those persons who cannot travel. It can bring customer record, online reviews, and the interest of both national and international buyers. We are focusing on training and development of employees so that they should not feel any worry in the adoption of e-commerce technologies.

The first theme (i.e. advanced technology can improve the current position of textile industry in Pakistan) has discussed all those factors that can improve the current infrastructure as well as level of performance in textile industry in Pakistan. For example, most of participants reported how the automatic machines (i.e. cloud computing, artificial intelligence, smart manufacturing, and smart internet) can improve the current infrastructure and performance of textile industry. They have argued that most of current technology is useless as it is bringing more cost of productions in terms of employee salaries, supplier and buyer manual records, more depreciation and high salaries for technical experts. Therefore, they have recommended adoption of industry 4 technologies can create automatic production

control and optimal decision making. Industry 4 can reduce the salaries cost as well as employee efforts and resources on manual procedures. Other respondents have reported how improvements in supply chain management can create competitive advantages. For example, by adopting e-procurement technology, textile mills can create online record about e-informing, e-auctioning, vendor management, order status, e-tendering, and optimal stock decisions. Furthermore, e-procurement can bring more transparency and accountability in terms of inventory management and performance of employees in operations department.

Other respondents have revealed that there are unable to get competitive advantages because more than 80-percent small and large textile units have no research and development department. Therefore, these textile units have limited information regarding how advanced technologies are able to create high production, high quality, better decision making, online record and data sharing with partners. Some respondents have suggested how China and Indian textile industry is more advance because there are producing fabrics with the help of laser printing, digital printing, and 3D Printers. On the other hand, Pakistani textile industry is still producing fabrics through technology which needs more technical staff, repairing, monitoring, and other expenses. They have suggested that e-banking system must be adopted by every stakeholder so that we can bring more transparency and accountability in system.

Sub-theme 2:

5.3.2 Government support can improve the current position of textile industry in Pakistan

Participant A2 highlighted about the required support of government:

The government of Pakistan should make arrangement for uplifting the current position of SMEs. As we are using obsolete technologies, unskilled labour, traditional working procedures, and high load of taxes. Therefore, many units are closed presently in this decade. The government has to offer interest free loans and long-term loans, support to purchase and successful adopt latest technologies such as e-procurement, and importing new technologies such as laser printing, digital printing, 3D Printers. These digital printing technologies can enhance the quality of fabrics as well as supportive to implement lean manufacturing practices in micro level.

Participant A23 discussed about the required support of government:

I am happy about the new government and their efforts to bring transparency, accountability, improvements in energy resources, and support for textile sector. Although it is not easy to solve the problems of previous twenty years in five years. However, the support and planning of government can give us new hope regarding we will see good time in textile sector with respect to adopting advanced technologies and low taxes.

Participant A21 has discussed about the required support of government:

The government should publish online data in which all the details about investment in energy, ICT infrastructure, loans for advance technologies, and improvements plans regarding textile sector must be mentioned. By publishing all the data related to government planning and milestone of textile industry, we can attract the international investors, suppliers, buyers, and high skilled labour. The sharing and publishing online data can increase trust in government and textile industry is ready to give taxes if it creates positive changes with respect to profit, growth, performance, and development of textile industry.

Participant A20 argued about the required support of government:

There are many challenges which raised problems from government side such as high level of corruption, high taxes, lack of investment in energy sources and industrial infrastructure, and increase in national debts. These challenges have increased cost of production textile for textile industry. Therefore, I recommend we must adopt e-government and digital open government system in which all the data regarding investment in energies, ICT infrastructure, and relief in taxes must be online. It can bring more transparency and accountability in government department and ultimately create positive support for us. It can enhance the justice practices as well as services delivery in private and public sectors.

Participant A22 shared thinking about the required support of government:

The inability of previous governments to offer safety and security, economic crises, instability in currency value, and limited support raise more challenges for SMEs. Many SMEs have closed because they could not bear the huge financial losses due to heavy taxes and complex loan procedures. I think.....government should adopt new digital system that can evaluate the performance of government. Furthermore, government should create more support for SMEs by giving loans at low interest rates and provide support to purchase advanced technologies such as e-procurement and e-commerce models.

The second theme (i.e. government support can improve the current position of textile industry in Pakistan) discussed all the factors that can bring the improvement in current infrastructure of textile industry. For example, respondents have suggested

that adoption of e-government and digital open government can create online record about what budget, planning and support, and strategies are specified by the government for bringing improvements in textile sector. The online data sharing can create trust in owners, investors, and international market about what are milestones of textile industry and how government is planning to support industry for enhancing the GDP contribution. Findings reveal government must bring new subjects and focus on the improvements of education sector with respect to textile industry. Otherwise we are unable to find those people who can create their role in the adoption and implementation of advanced technologies and practices. Other respondents have recommended to bring political stability, more safety and security so that more international buyers, suppliers, and marketers visit without fear.

The government should take step to invest in energy resources, ICT infrastructure, and industry 4.0. The investment and advancement of technologies can provide platform for textile industry to import and install latest technologies for achieving maximum production within limited time. Most of SMEs owners and employees have suggested that they need immediate support from government because they have limited capital, human capital, advanced technologies, growth and profit rates, and access to international market. Furthermore, government should stabilize the currency because SMEs are unable to import machine and tools by paying higher cost and taxes. During these challenges, SMEs can unable to create maximum output, performance, growth, and development opportunities. They are hopeful that new government will take more immediate step to support small units as textile industry is largest revenue producer and contributor in economic development of Pakistan.

Sub-theme 3:

5.3.3 Adoption and implementation of advanced practices can improve the current position of textile sector

Participant A24 discussed about enablers and recommendation for textile industry:

These large and small textile units must adopt high-performance work system (HPWS) that can improve the performance by giving rules of thumb about recruitment, training and motivation, skills development, performance appraisal, and compensation to employees. The HPWS can easily evaluate and improve the individual and overall performance as well as effectiveness. If employees are talented, capable, then they can bring process and

qualify improvements in both yarn and fabrics. These practices must be adopted in whole textile sector so that we can create more openness towards adoption of technology and other workplace changes.

Participant A20 talked about the required support of government:

Advanced countries are generating energy for textile machines through sun and wind. However, we are still seeing towards how government should support and give relief on electricity and gas. I think.... we must develop an attractive investment plan in which we include national and international investors with the purpose to produce cheapest energy sources which can decrease the cost of production. As a result, we can sell high textile commodities at lower price, and we can share the portion of profit with investors.

Participant A12 discussed about the required support of government:

Currently government is adopting e-government system and other good practices in Pakistan. This system will generate transparency and accountability as all the information will be online. These cyber sharing systems may create high amount of information related to textile sector and it can be accessible for everyone around the world. The government and textile sector should organize international seminar and conferences in which all the stakeholders participate and share their ideas to bring improvement in textile sector.

Participant A25 shared experiences discussed about enablers and recommendation for textile industry:

SMEs are one of the main victims and trying to stay alive in textile industry. The one of reasons is we cannot adopt the advance performance improvements practices such as HPWS and lean manufacturing. By adopting HPWS system, we can identify who are the productive employees and who are un-productive. While by adopting lean manufacturing, we can easily remove extra processes that can increase the cost of production. Currently, it is a need of time that we should adopt those advance practices that can bring boom in textile industry.

Participant A9 shared thinking about the required support of government:

Most of the SMEs have weakest ICT infrastructure therefore they are spending greater time in producing maximum output. Further, the publication of financial reports and data sharing on website is not common therefore these SMEs cannot attract investors as well as the trust of private lenders. These practices should be changed towards producing more financial reports and online data sharing so that internet users can get gain maximum information about SMEs.

The third theme (i.e. adoption and implementation of advanced practices can improve the current position of textile sector) highlighted how the textile industry must focus on HPWS practices, lean manufacturing, cyber sharing, publication of financial reports, conduct international seminars and conferences, create own energy sources, developed ICT Infrastructure, and data exchange with partners. Participants have highlighted that the employees are not skilled, motivated, and committed to bring improvements. Therefore, by the adoption of HPWS system, textile sector can create improvements in employee recruitment, training and development, skills improvement, dedication, and performance evaluation. Other participants have argued that textile industry is far away to produce lean manufacturing therefore they are bearing high level of cost of production and low level of profit as well as competitive advantages. By adopting lean manufacturing practices, SMEs and other textile units can improve the process as well as quality of textile commodities.

Findings reveal SMEs must focus to develop and adopt ICT infrastructure so that they can create and share online data among stakeholders. It is also found that these SMEs are struggling because they are working with traditional supply chain management methods. By adoption e-procurement, e-banking, and publishing reports online can attract more investors and buyers. These financial reports can create trust among stakeholders that they are buying from those units who have reputation and good financial creditability in market. Respondent also suggested that government and textile sector should conduct international conferences and seminar in which they exchanged new ideas regarding how they create energy sources such as sun and wind are good alternates to produce electricity for textile machines. The conferences and seminars can enhance knowledge how textile industry, government, and other stakeholders can improve its current position by adopting new technologies and advance workplace practices.

CHAPTER 6: DISCUSSION

6.1 INTRODUCTION

This study is conducted as first study (i.e. existing Infrastructure and current position of textile industry) which have been identified both weaknesses and strengths that are particularly influencing the competitive advantage, production, performance and production cost of textile sector in Pakistan. The study participants highlighted numbers of small and large ginning and spinning units operating in different provinces of Pakistan. Peres ([2009](#)) argued that Mexico and Brazil have stimulated the technological development by creating technology funds along with other specific sectoral focus programmes. By emphasising on policy framework intending to trigger financial entry in Latin American countries (such as publicly provision of structured finance, market infrastructure, public lending, transactional cost subsidies and credit guarantee system) De la Torre et al. ([2007](#)) clearly differentiated laissez-faire policy, Intermediate policy and interventionist policy variation that particularly targets a specific set of the policy interventions - in highly restricted manner - that provides support to development of private sector and deals with market failures. They also observed many regional institutions that are gradually moving toward this policy. Thus, it can be argued that contribution of textile industry in GDP of Pakistan is quite significant and is also recognized as key income source for economy of Pakistan. According to factors, textile industry in Pakistan is one amongst top ten ranked industries in terms of best quality cotton producer and exporting textile products in huge amount. Some participants highlighted that there are numerous opportunities in Pakistani textile industry for growth because besides of major contributor of Pakistan economy, it has strong attraction for international investors.

6.2 CURRENT POSITION OF TEXTILE INDUSTRY

Figure 6.20 Current position of textile industry in Pakistan

In existing infrastructure of textile industry, there are numerous weaknesses and challenges that have limited its overall growth opportunities. Firstly, this industry has numbers of SMEs that face challenges more than big organizations i.e. textile mills etc. Often, the governments through their acts show that they cognize the particularity of public inputs and private needs, even while maintaining the novelty that they are not engaged in industrial policies. Many countries of Latin America, for example, officially detached from industrial policy in 1980s to 1990s while reorienting their economic strategies. Still, their policies for export processing zone and direct foreign investments focused on providing particular public inputs for these activities instead of focusing on “across board” policies (Rodrik 2004). Therefore, tax incentives were offered to foreign investors so that they can overcome their

inadequate familiarity with the host countries, get navigation through local rules and regulations, subsidies for their training employees, sites with committed infrastructure and protection against weak local legal regime (Nahtigal, 2014). Good infrastructure, fast-track custom processes, flexible labour activities and cheap inputs are basic requirements of the firms operating in the export processing areas. Whatever the case, governments are actively engaged in industrial policies by providing specific public inputs that benefited specific economic actors (Weiss, 2018). For example, due to not publishing financial reports, SMEs have less financial capital opportunities as compare to banks and other private investors. Moreover, the high interest rates at which these lenders offer loans may also increase the production cost particularly for the SMEs with entire focus on local market. Moreover, participants have also discussed that usage of obsolete technologies have also increased their production cost due to more monitoring, maintenance and repairing requirements. In addition to that, high production cost, strikes and energy crises are the major factors that enforce the SMEs to sell out their raw materials across the border or other countries. Participants have also discussed that more than 90% of SMEs and textile mills produce fabric and yarn through traditional methods mainly because of not having any specific R&D department. Finally, due to having many challenges, the education industry in Pakistan is also unable to provide talented people to textile industry who can bring about new changes through adoption and implementation of modern technologies. Therefore, it is suggested to education sector to include subject specifically on textile industry because majority of business administration students though have more general knowledge but have limited theoretical knowledge.

Generally, governments make regular intervention in their economies to pursue high growth rate. These interventions are conceptually justified by the market failures, which may exist in different aspects of an economy such as production of specific goods, provision of the infrastructure, interactions among organizations and accumulation of the human capital (Weber, et al., 2019). These policies collectively termed as “Productivity Policies,” while narrow focus on specific sectoral support is traditionally termed as “Industrial Policy” (Su, et al., 2010). According to standard-welfare theory, policy should have the capacity to redress the failures, ideally closer to distortion as much as possible (Poteralska, & Sacio-Szymańska, 2014). However,

some government interventions (such as in infrastructure and education) are large as well as uncontroversial while others (like targeting particular economic aspects for support etc.) are relatively more (Read, et al., 2016). In second sub-theme of the study (i.e. government planning and support and its impact on textile industry), various situations have been described that lead to increase challenges for Pakistani textile industry. Pakistan has, for example, borrowed US\$92 billion and above dollars from IMF, China and USA, which pressurises the Pakistani currency by paying instalments at higher interest rate and by devaluation. But unfortunately, this money is being used by corrupt administration and politicians in form of making their personal assets. Resultantly, this corruption leads to produce many burdens for businesses in form of heavy tariffs, taxes, exports and import duties etc. Moreover, participants described that they cannot afford to import updated technology and heavy machinery due to high currency devaluation as it can further increase the overall production cost. These extra financial burden and high taxes have enforced majority of SMEs in textile sector to shut down their businesses. In this regard, the other factors are limited financial capital, lack of local markets, insufficient government support and inadequate competitive advantage. Government capacity to develop and execute accurate solution of observed market failure is most important. Here, the traditional concerns are coordinative, executive and diagnostic capacity of a government along with its potential to distortionary seeks rent (Acheson, et al., 2011). Existing literature explicitly or implicitly divides space of policy into horizontal and vertical market failures as well as interventions as shown in figure 6.2 below (Nuvolari, 2018).

Figure 6.21 Market failure by government

Moreover, government has no appropriate energy plans due to which businesses have to face high gas and electricity load shedding in Pakistan. Additionally, stealing of gas, electricity and other sources is very common practice in our society that ultimately increases the per unit prices of all energy sources for textile sector. These corrupt practices raise many other challenges like more strikes, high production cost, involvement of child labour and low wage rates. Load shedding of electricity for long duration makes it tough for SMEs and other industries to survive. Though Textile mills and SMEs have solar plants, power generators and UPS as backup but operating, maintaining and keeping them in workable condition is quite expensive, particularly when these are using as backup of heavy machinery. Thus, these temporary sources of energy make it impossible for textile mills to deliver require quality and quantity of textile products on time. All this not only leads to increase losses but also reduces the buyers` interest towards placing the orders Though Pakistani government has defined strict punishments for energy stealing but the increased electricity rate and long electric shortage duration has decreased labour shifts and wages, overall growth opportunities and profit rates of textile industry. Lower profitability, higher debt to equity ratio and no tendency to publish financial reports are the main factors that make it difficult for textile industry to achieve investor confidence or get financial support. Furthermore, majority of families have

lower income level and also have lower employment opportunities due to limited skills, all these factors collectively lead to increase child labour. Various factors of production markets are characterized by long-term failures. Both infrastructure as well as services it renders are connected with number of market failures, for instance in classic form of the public goods, merit goods (externalities of positive consumption), decreasing costs (result in natural monopoly) or externalities (such as network externalities) (Tutino, & John., 2016). For primary as well as secondary education, the social rate of return is more than private rate of return (Moretti 1999; Dr Paul & Govekar., 2007). In other words, educated employees may increase overall productivity of their co-workers who are less educated or countries with relatively high human capital tend to learn more from others. Classically, inadequate collateral or information asymmetries lead the credit markets to face failure (Szostak, 1991). Additionally, involvement of government in fights with India has brought many safety and security issues such as terrorist attacks and suicide bombers. Resultantly, these attacks leave negative impact on textile industry by minimising the number of sellers and buyers. According to participants, safety and security issues raised several other challenges like decreasing the number of investors etc. These issues also enforce majority of small units to completely close their businesses because they are unable to survive in momentary shutdowns.

Previous result and analysis part of the first theme covered the discussion on current position and importance of textile sector in Pakistan. Pakistani textile industry is reported as major income generation source of our economy. Due to producing best quality cotton and yarn, Pakistani textile products are highly valued and demanded in international markets, particularly Asian markets. Through reviewing literature on development, it is revealed that market-led development, a paradigm simplistically draws from neoclassical economic principles, is argued to allow the market for allocation of resources, thus reduces the role and authority of state. This paradigm refers market as to best mechanism regarding resource allocation and time reinforcement through different international agencies, such as World Bank (e.g. Stein, and various other authors) (Liang, & Goetz, 2018). Participants have, however, identified many challenges influencing growth, survival, performance and profits of textile sector in Pakistan see figure 6.3 . Some studies, in context of Africa, have emphasised on comparative advantages as best way to generate job growth in

African countries. This approach fundamentally recommends that rather than moving towards other sectors, they should engage in such development strategy through which expansion in current resource intensive and labour-intensive industries can be promoted, so that no more skills and capital can be called for (Lin 2012).

Figure 6.22 Infrastructure channels and required actions

Problematically, though these arguments seem as supporter of state-led development, but they misleadingly marked current development patterns (specifically those relevant with growth of resource-led commodities) as the development strategies (Lin 2012). It is fact that natural resources simply cannot act as backbone of industrial efforts of a country but should be augmented via intellectual capital (knowledge accumulation, learning and skills) and material growth (industry and machinery). These challenges include limited technology usage, traditional work practices, lack of well-developed ICT infrastructure, and devaluation of local currency, energy crises, budget deficit and national debts. All these factors lead to decrease overall growth, profits, survival and performance of textile sector in Pakistan. Based on all these challenges, this study has been conducted with aim to bring about significant improvement in current recessions period of textile sector in Pakistan. This study has presented three major issues with respect to main theme

including: advance practices, government role and advanced technology. Regarding advance technology, participants suggested to adopt such automatic systems that can improve current position and performance level of textile industry. Moreover, in context of government role, participants suggested that government should facilitate the Pakistani textile industry by making investments not only in its energy sources (e.g. gas, electricity) but also in ICT infrastructure (e.g. digital open and e-government). With respect to advanced practices, participants highlighted all such practices through which performance of textile industry and its employees can be improved. Opinions of participants regarding all three aspects are given below in detail for better understanding.

The opportunities, benefits and challenges of textile industry may vary amongst developing countries, emerging economies and advanced countries. The practices that are developed and implemented in countries with high level of knowledge exchange, information sharing, stable politics, skilled employees, advance technologies and rich energy sources, cannot be implemented in Pakistan. According to previous studies, the numbers of shares that Pakistani textile industry has in international market is continuously decreasing due to many crises (such as obsolete technology, energy and economic crisis) (Ahmed & Siddiqui, 2016; Shah, et al., 2014; Mangi & Kay, 2016). These challenges are reported to increase the overall production cost, whereas reduce market and growth opportunities for textile industry in Pakistan (Shah, et al., 2014; Mangi & Kay, 2016). There are many external and internal factors (such as energy and economy crises, conventional workplace environment and obsolete technology) that have enforced many small and large textile units to shutdown their businesses and cancel many of international buyers' orders (Ahmed & Siddiqui, 2016; Jameel, et al., 2014). This study primarily aims at highlighting the current status of Pakistani textile sector and identifying the major causes behind its decline . Based on study findings, this study makes some recommendations reagrding how to improve current status of textile sector in Pakistan. This study selected owners and high ranked personnel from textile industry for data collection through semi-structured interviews.

Evaluating textile industry of pakistan is first objective of this study. since 1947, Pakistan is recognised all over the world as best cotton producer. Initially, there were

only three textile mills in Pakistan but later on this number continuously increased and reached to 600 mills by end of twentieth century. Moreover, a significant rise was also observed in number of spindles from 1,77,000 to 8,500,000 during said period. Currently, there are about 396-textile mills and 317-composite units are operating throughout Pakistan. Nowadays, there are countless large and small gining units, and spinning units in single province of our country. Pakistan is now recognised as one of the biggest high quality cotton producer Asian countries. Moreover, Pakistani textile industry is major contributor of our economy as biggest revenue generator. Participants also described that textile industry in Pakistan is one amongst top ten ranked industries in terms of best quality cotton producer and exporting textile products in huge amount. Pakistani economy depends heavily on its agricultural products (e.g. rice, wheat and cotton) (Memon, 2016; Mangi & Kay, 2016). Life of farmers and of those individuals working in textile, flour and rice mills totally based on these agricultural produces. Moreover, the contribution of industrial cities such as Sialkot, Faisalabad and Sheikhupura in total GDP is also very high. According to a study, textile industry is Pakistan's largest manufacturing industry in terms of higher contribution to GDP (Cororaton & Orden, 2008).

Based on higher contribution to GDP, textile industry has ranked our country amongst top global and Asian exporters and producers of textile products, accounting for 10% contribution to GDP of the country (White, 2015). But still there are many challenges that are negatively influencing Pakistani textile industry in terms of output and performance. Previous section discussed these challenges from cultural, governmental, infrastructural, financial and technological perspectives. Study findings highlighted that developing countries can bring about economic development through technology adoption, for which they have to improve and refine their industrial strategies and policies (Hutchinson & Dowd 2018; Hendrickson, 2015; Khan, Dongping, & Ghauri, 2014). According to Khan (2010), about 60% and above of exports in Pakistan is composed of variety of textile products.

Assessing current status of Pakistani textile industry is second objective of this study. It has been observed that education, organizational and national culture, government, infrastructure, usage of technology, skills and production cost are not supportive for Pakistani textile industry. Participants have highlighted that contrary to giant textile units, SMEs have to struggle more in order to survive and stay alive in

business world. Limited financial capital, usage of obsolete technology, not publishing financial reports, limited access to regional market and traditional working practices are the major challenges for SMEs in Pakistan. These factors, in turn, decrease the profits and increase the production cost for SMEs. Many studies revealed that traditional working practices are very common in textile sector due to which employees have to spend longer time for completion of their work. This eventually decreases the competitive advantages and increases the production cost for SMEs (Abbas et al., 2012; Shah et al., 2012). However, Pakistani textile industry has greater growth opportunities and is regarded as largest contributor of economy also it has greater attraction for foreign investors (Ahmed & Siddiqui, 2016; Shah, et al., 2014; Mangi & Kay, 2016). The interest rate at which money lenders and financial institutions offer loans is very high that further increases the insecurity for SMEs survival. The usage of printing machinery and looms requiring higher technical, monitoring, repairing and maintenance cost is very common in textile units. Higher interest rate, unfavourable government planning, energy crises and high production cost of inputs are the challenges that require high documentation while need to avail textile loans (Khan & Khan 2010; Khattak et al., 2011; Khan et al., 2014).

Moreover, high prices and shortfall of electricity and gas has further increased the existing challenges for the SMEs, particularly those earning minor profits from purchasers. Respondents have described that more than 90% of textile mills and SMEs have not proper R&D department. Thus, adoption of smart technologies is not easy for these SMEs and textile units and therefore they cannot decrease their production cost. Existing literature reveals that textile industry has paid little attention on R&D due to which quality of Pakistani cotton is becoming low. This, in turn, unable the textile industry to earn higher profits (Abbas et al., 2012; Khan & Khan 2010; Khattak et al., 2011; Khan et al., 2014). Moreover, education sector has not included any specialised program relevant with textile industry that is why majority of employees do not have much of awareness about latest textile practices. terms and conditions for competition, skills development, education, focusing on trade, competitiveness, innovation and technology are various factors through which performance and productivity of textile industry can be improved (Hendrickson, 2015; Vries, 2008). Diversification, restructuring, development planning, skills

development, education and upgrading are the key components that ensure a constant development in textile industry (Hendrickson, 2015). In countless presses and medial talks, APTMA (All Pakistan Textile Mills Association) have highlighted many issues that hamper the growth of textile industry and also discussed how environmental changes reduce the agricultural productivity. For example, rain fall and viruses have strongly and negatively influenced majority of crops.

6.3 ENABLERS OF THE TEXTILE INDUSTRY

Figure 6.23 Enablers of textile industry in Pakistan

It has been identified in second theme (see figure above) that advanced technology can improve the current position of textile industry in Pakistan), all factors has been discussed that can bring improvement in current performance level and infrastructure of textile industry of Pakistan. These factors may include automatic machines (for

example smart manufacturing, smart internet, artificial intelligence and cloud computing etc). majority of participants considered many of modern technology useless because it leads to increase production cost in form of high salaries of technical experts, high depreciation and buyer and supplier manual records. Therefore, participants have suggested adopting industry 4.0 technologies as it facilitates optimal decisions making and provide automatic production monitoring and control. Various studies attempted addressing the question of how to create and accelerate the learning and innovation and that how a significant role is played by capabilities in structural transformation (Hansen, et al. 2018). The focuses of evolutionary economics involve dynamics of analyses learning and economic development, technological change, and accumulated domestic capabilities as chief drivers of structural transformation (Bogliacino, 2012). This is the reason that evolutionary economics is regarded as incremental, non-linear, and complex process. As per economists, comparative advantage is 'made' instead of being 'given' and that developmental states tend to design such policies and institutions which support the learning process (Haeri & Arabmazar, 2019).

Moreover, industry 4.0 tends to minimise salaries cost and consumption of resources and employee efforts on manual work practices. Economists regard such economies as high performing ones which have deliberately shifted away from low quality activities to high quality activities whereby former is characterized by diminishing returns, flat learning, low productivity, and low wage whereas latter is characterized by high wages, high growth rate, high technological progress, rapid growth of productivity, and sharp learning curves (Liang, et al. 2016). Moreover, participants highlighted the importance of supply chain management in gaining competitive advantages. The adoption of e-procurement technology, for example, enables the textile mills to produce online record regarding e-auctioning, e-informing, e-tendering, order status, optimal stock decisions and vendor management. In addition to that, e-procurement has ability to bring about more accountability and transparency through inventory management as well as employee performance in operational departments. Greenwald & Stiglitz (2013) expanded the arguments related to infant industry to infant economy and discussed the helpfulness of well-designed policies in shaping the learning societies. They argued that creating a learning society is about increasing the living standards on piecemeal and

permanent basis instead of introducing one-time improvements in economic efficiency. (Greenwald and Stiglitz, 2013)

According to some participants, about 80% and above large and small textile units do not have any R&D department due to which they have no ability to gain competitive advantage. Resultantly, textile units slightly know about how to use advance technology for increasing production, quality, making better decisions, and sharing data and online records with partners. Participants also uncovered the secret behind the advancement of Indian and Chinese textile industries that are using 3D printers, digital printing and laser printing technologies for the production of fabric. Contrary to that, textile industry in Pakistan is still using traditional technology to produce fabrics, for which more repairing, monitoring, staff is required. Participants suggested adopting e-banking in order to bring more accountability and transparency in system. Furthermore, their approach for technology upgrading, learning, and knowledge is originated from neoclassical tradition. This approach was developed by them on the basis of market analysis due to distribution of knowledge, production, and information and of market failures due to distribution of finance knowledge and innovation (Lauridsen, 2010). They emphasized on understanding the learning structure of economy, particularly about spreading it across sectors. Such understanding leads towards concluding the significant policies about how to encourage manufacturing, exports, and other sectors for ensuring fast growth in productivity and accelerated learning (Martin & Martin, 2017).

Mazzucato (2013) recently reviewed the role which a state can play in enhancing the technological capabilities for innovation led growth in developed countries. She argued on the basis of the evidence that primary entrepreneurial drives and resultant risk taking which lies behind modern technologies has provided less compared to what has been suggested by private sector but nevertheless more than what state acknowledges. Germuska (2013) argued that public policies of different countries played significant role in developing innovations and other relevant capabilities as well when there was risk at peak. In second theme of study (i.e. government support can improve the current position of textile industry in Pakistan), those factors have been discussed that can improve current infrastructure and position of textile sector in Pakistan. Majority of respondents have suggested adopting digital open and e-

government so that online record can be created about what strategies, support, planning and budget Pakistani government has specified to bring improvement in its textile industry. Through online sharing of data, textile industry can develop trust in international markets, investors and owners about its milestones and also what government has planned to support textile industry for increasing overall GDP contribution.

There are debates in both literature and political circles concerning the industrial policies. Each debate specifically highlights radically diverging views (Avis, 2018). The traditional liberal approach provides that liberalization of economy and market is the most suitable policy for each country and is best in all circumstances because free markets allow countries to gain competitive edge in the market (Antoniuk, et al. 2017). This rationale is chiefly based on the assumption that product markets correctly respond to the investment according to the actor (Pearson & Foxon, 2012). It is the chief responsibility of the government to ensure that suitable macroenvironment is being provided and there is stability in the market (Rodríguez, et al. 2014) where there is clear definition of rules of games. Without intervening it would change the already available resources (Li Guoping, et al. 2017). This approach tends to overlook the failures of the market which is its main disadvantage (Barca, 2011), because it centrally influences growth of productivity and income in the long run, specifically in the domain of knowledge and innovation (Mann, 2018; Hall & Jones, 1999). Based on study findings it is suggested to government to bring about new subjects with more focus on improving education sector in context of textile industry. Bringing such improvements will enable us to find out those individuals who have ability to adopt and implement new practices and technologies. In addition to that, respondents have also highlighted the need of more security, safety and political stability so that international marketers, suppliers and buyers can visit our country without any fear. Literature concerning technological capabilities regards technological change as significant for development of economy for emerging countries. However, this development process is hindered by the market failures (Etzkowitz & Viale, 2010; Howe, 2016). This approach argues that any country's industrial success depends largely on its capacity of embracing and becoming expert in existing technologies (Bogart, 2011). Due to market failures it becomes impossible for technology to be available freely. Therefore, it is imperative

for organizations to make conscious and purposive efforts for building technological competencies and invest in the technological based learning process (Prisecaru, 2017; MacNeil, 2013; Sharp & Weisdorf, 2012).

The study highlighted the situation with which textile industry in Pakistan is passing through. The study highlighted different strengths and weaknesses of the situation to indicate the steps that need be taken by the stakeholders of the textile sector for improving technology, processes, productivity, financial position, quality, performance, and timely completion of orders. The debate on the current infrastructure of textile industry showed that there are 396 textile mills, and 317 composite units hiring the maximum number of textile workers in the industry. Moreover, the textile sector has also achieved significant position in the Asian markets with textile exports about 60%. However, in past two to three decades the textile industry in Pakistan has received a blow due to various reasons such as poor infrastructure in the country, lack of advanced work practices, and new technologies. The industry is facing challenges in adopting advanced practices e.g. the textile units possess limited capital, their labour is unskilled and unprofessional, they have low level of support from employees, their infrastructure is still underdeveloped, and there is lack of support from government. Due to these reasons the textile industry is on the decline in Pakistani market. This has aggravated the situation with exports falling, units closing down, and unemployment of textile workers increasing.

Textile industry is dependent on the productivity of the agriculture as textile industry is dependent on production of cotton. The environmental and climate changes are negatively influencing the agriculture sector of Pakistan and indirectly influencing the textile industry. For example, heavy rainfall and high temperature is affecting cotton production in the country. It has also been found out that there is lack of support for textile industry in the education system as those students are not being produced who can create competitive edge for the industry. Due to this reason, much of the work in the industry is still manually done involving also manual methods of payment, paper based working, and small number of technical experts. This has affected the productivity level of the industry compared to the industries of other countries. Due to these reasons, it is hardly enviable that the SMEs in the textile industry will be able to achieve high productivity. Therefore, many small units are going in losses and are thus closing down permanently.

It is also important to note that previous governments bought heavy amount from foreign lenders and the current Pakistani government is struggling to pay back the debt with interest. The menace of corruption has further aggravated the problem as the corrupt officials utilized public money for creating offshore companies and other personal assets. Due to this reason the industries in Pakistan are suffering because of energy crisis, high tax rates, high export and import duties, and continuous currency devaluation. This has increased the cost of machinery due to which SMEs cannot import that machinery from abroad. The failures of market justified the intervention from state in the sense that neoclassical economic wisdom documented the failures of governments (Getahun & Willanger, 2019). It argues that factors such as myopic and incompetent bureaucracies and corruption by private sector have increased the probability of governmental failures more than the likelihood of market failures (Bae & Mah, 2019). This approach while based on perfectly competitive principles and unessential policy debate concerning failure of government versus failure of market is damaging the development policy by preventing rich analysis concerning different learning processes and thus is unable to promote structural transformation (Barkley & Dudensing, 2011). Contrary to such enquiry, traditional policy seen under this tradition furthers the unduly simplistic worldwide policy rules such as 'get the prices right' or 'get the government out of the way' (Choi, et al. 2011).

SMEs are also unable to tap the international markets because of increased taxation in the country. The cost of production has increased due to taxation and also because of inflation. This has increased the child labour issues in the industry for keeping the wage rate at the minimum possible level. The growth opportunities were also significantly affected due to terrorist attacks in the country. The foreign investors became reluctant due to terrorist activities in the country which have now largely been controlled. The installing of new technologies also gave rise to suspicion among labourers that they would be replaced by machines due to which resistance to change started to appear. Therefore, the working procedures are still traditional to avoid conflict with the workforce. It has also been observed that much of the labour from textile industry is not educated and thus earning bare minimum wage. The role of institutions and governance has largely been highlighted by different latest approaches in the neoclassical framework (Choi, et al. 2010). Such variables have

not been integrated yet into the models and frameworks. Consequently, there power for providing policy recommendation is low with respect to strengthening the relationship of such variables (Colette, 2015). This shortcoming is addressed by Justin Lin and Volker Treichel by utilizing the GIF approach (Growth Identification & Facilitation) and recommended 6 steps methodology for identifying and targeting the sectors for government support and investment in regional context (Pansuwan & Routrary, 2011). This approach provides that the state should proactively engage in overcoming issues concerning externality, coordination, and information which are found in the newly developed activities and sectors (Lin, 2017). However, this approach also argues that failures of existing industrial policy was chiefly due to efforts made on the basis of such strategies which did not abide by the concept of competitive edge (Lin, 2017).

The current research provides practical recommendations for improving the governmental planning, existing infrastructure, culture of textile industry, and current position of textile industry. It is important that the government invests in the energy sector so that the uninterrupted supply of energy starts taking place again to the industries including also the textile industry. Further, the government must also import machinery and give subsidy on importing machinery relevant to textile industry. It should also focus on connecting the industry with industries from developed countries. Commission on Growth & Development (2008) highlighted the constraints in neoclassical approaches with respect to development and growth and the policies which underpin such processes (Beekmans, et al. 2016). The traditional growth and trade models which were developed under neoclassical approaches highlighted growth in the context of production factors, particularly physical and human capital and technology as well (Behuria, 2019). Gereffi (2014a) observed that a country should prioritize such products which bring competitive edge to the country and the focus of policy discussions should largely be on residual derives from exercises which this approach created. (Ovadia, & Wolf, 2018)

The government should also develop infrastructure to support the evolving development of textile industry. It is also suggested that the government must facilitate the industry to adopt e-payment and e-procurement channels to ensure speedy payments in the industry and swift procurement of raw material. This will also

increase the time efficiency of the industry. Moreover, online database must be created for textile products so that the product portfolio of textile industry can be linked with international buyers and investors. It is imperative that e-commerce model is adopted, and a complete online profile of textile industry is created so that they can receive orders online from international buyers without having to resort to physical marketing. There are clear applications for it due to practical-oriented approach. Upon assessing this approach, Chang agreed that industrial policies which deviate from competitive edge concept become riskier (Kim, C. and Hong, M., 2010). However, the approach cannot recognize that such risks have already been undertaken by different countries even when their policies showed deviation from comparative advantage. A number of success stories were based on such moves which were more daring than what was suggested by their rule (Chang, 2013). Since the emphasis of this approach is on the comparative edge, therefore, it has not taken into account the dynamics of upgrading the capabilities, learning, and technology. These aspects can be studied through evolutionary economics (Feser, 2014).

It is imperative that textile industry adopts Industry 4 technologies such as 3D printing and laser printing to produce high quality fabrics. By utilizing industry 4 technologies the cost of production can also be reduced and manual processes can be minimized. This will enhance the efficiency of the industry. By using such advanced technologies, the textile sector can gain control over production cost and enhance its profitability. Without investing on such measures, the productivity cannot be increased, and the quality cannot be brought to international level. These technologies will be helpful in bringing major improvements in home products, cotton spinning, cotton yarn and cloth, fabric processing, hosiery, knitwear, and readymade textile products. By utilizing these technologies, the industry can increase its exports.

It is also suggested that significant changes must be introduced in education sector so that textile is taught as a subject at various levels to provide the industry with skilled and educated workforce. This will be helpful in overcoming the employee resistance against change. It is also suggested that government and other stakeholders of the industry must provide safe and secure environment so that international investors can be attracted to invest in the industry. In this regard seminars and conferences can be arranged with researchers, international businessmen, suppliers, buyers, and other stakeholders about the potential growth

of the industry. Instead of this, it also recommends that while developing the industrial policies the focus should be on the economic and industrial activities and that some principles must be adhered to in this regard e.g. focusing on the services/products which grew dynamically in two decades in fast paced economies where per capita GDP was two times higher. Moreover, those goods/services must be prioritized in which the private sector has already penetrated successfully (Heide, et al., 2013). However, efforts concerning the productive transformation without taking into account the boundaries of competitive edge face failures and slow down the economic performance (Thoburn & Natsuda, 2018). The literature rarely mentions the Skills Development & Partnerships, and Multiple Actors Developing Skills across value chain. But wherever these are in place there are positive results. In Bangladesh, JMS Holdings Ltd has supported the development of suppliers through the transfer of skills. The pre-selected suppliers are invited by the purchasers to the production site of JMS and they are explained the quality requirements of JMS's clients and are also introduced to quality testing procedures. Once the delivery starts, JMS continuously communicates with suppliers if the fabric is short of vital quality standards. This offers them solutions for fixing the underlying issues. The purchasers also frequently visit the production facilities of suppliers for providing them support. This ensures a systematic chain management which identifies key issues and provides them with incentives so that suppliers continue to engage in training. Systematically monitoring the results of the suppliers has been crucial for achieving the sustainable improvements (KfW DEG, 2016).

Factory owners usually think that once training is provided to employees, they might quit the job and go on to find employment in another company on the basis of their training (Fukunishi, 2014). Some organizations expect their potential employees to have gone some training before they enter the job market so that the organization does not have to bear the cost of training the workforce (USAID, 2009). However, the evidence on the contrary suggests that following the training program the turnover rate of employees is significantly reduced and the organizations which invest in the training of their employees experience better retention rate of the workforce. This means that long-term investments through leadership training and skills are likely to provide win-win situations for both the organization and its workforce (Naeem & Woodruff, 2015). Evidence from Cambodia shows that,

improving the skills of workforce is less costly as compared to dealing with turnover rate of inexperienced and unskilled workforce (USAID, 2009).

Sonobe (et al. 2011) observed that in Vietnam upon receiving a successful managerial training course, the participants became interested in paying for such course in future than they thought they would before be participating in the course. Participants had increased willingness to pay for the training which they had not experienced before. The evidence from Cambodia suggests that Cambodian factories were initially sceptical of having a Garment Industry Productivity Centre (GIPC). The factory managers were not eager in investing the time or money in unproven methods which foreign experts offered. In order to overcome this hurdle, the GIPC started its activities with a pilot program spanning over eight months in which four factories were engaged in classroom instructions followed by in-factory application. There were three manageable courses involved in the training curriculum on a part time basis so that workers did not have to compromise on their time spent in the factory. At the end of the program three out of four factories completed the program and witnessed measurable improvements i.e. 30% increase in productivity. By increasing the productivity of factories the Centre also added over \$13 million in Cambodian economy. For publicising the results the Centre attract managers from 50 factories and 30 stakeholders from donors, other organizations and governmental level officials at a conference (USAID, 2009).

Based on above discussion, it is revealed that government should invest in industry 4.0 technologies, ICT infrastructure and energy resources. Through adoption and implementation of advance technologies, textile industry can maximize the production in limited time period. Majority of SMEs employees and owners highlighted the immediate need of government support because of having limited financial capital, access to foreign market, human capital, profits rates, growth and advanced technologies. Additionally, stabilizing local currency is also very important because SMEs cannot afford to import tools and machinery at higher taxes and cost. As a result of these challenges, SMEs become unable to maximise the performance, output, development opportunities ad growth. New government is expected to take immediate steps in favour of small units because textile industry in Pakistan is considered as largest revenue contributor and producer of our economy.

In third theme of study (i.e. adoption and implementation of advanced practices can improve the current position of textile sector), it is highlighted that textile industry should focus on adopting HPWS practices, cyber sharing, lean manufacturing, conducting international conference and seminars, publishing financial reports, developing ICT infrastructure, exchanging data with partners and creating own energy sources. According to participants, employees are neither skilled nor committed and motivated towards bringing improvements. HPWS system will enable the textile industry to improve employee recruitment, development and training, performance evaluation, dedication and skills improvement. Textile industry in Pakistan is very far away from lean manufacturing that in turn increases the production cost and reduces the competitive advantages and profits. Practicing lean manufacturing will enable the textile industry to improve its quality and processes. Once the factories witnessed the effect of productivity with respect to their competitors, they became interested in investing in the skills development program of their workers. Studies in different region showed that the factories which were open to change and committed to enhancing the basic techniques of production and managerial disciplines were likely to achieve results (Hurst, 2013; USAID, 2005). For example, in Cambodia, the ones who committed to introducing the skills development programs usually experienced massive gains in their productivity and hence in their profitability (USAID, 2009).

Similarly, in Bangladesh, those factories which implemented the skills development program came out to be more successful than the factories who did not introduce such program particularly in terms of efficiency and productivity (Hurst, 2013). It is crucial to have a personally committed and engaged general manager (USAID, 2009). For example, those supervisors who are supported by their managers have better skills and confidence for carrying out their jobs effectively (ILO, 2016a). The growth in productivity is not just the result of implementing skills development program but it requires the overall overhauling of the environment starting from governmental level. For example, the Sri Lankan government introduced skills development as a key component (Lopez-Acevedo & Robertson, 2016). The main RMG industry of Sri Lanka in 2002 with the help of the government developed a 5 years strategy for facing the MFA phase-out. SL 100 million were allocated by the government for increasing the productivity in apparel sector through 5 years strategy

which also involved setting up the Joint Apparel Association Forum (JAAF). JAAF was responsible for consolidating the industry associations and enabled the response across the industry against the challenges posed by the phase out of MFA (Wijayasiri and Dissanayake 2008).

Study findings further reveal that SMEs should focus on developing and adopting ICT infrastructure for creating and sharing online data amongst stakeholders. Furthermore, SMEs are using traditional methods of supply chain management, thus have to struggle a lot. SMEs can attract large number of buyers and investors through publishing their financial reports and adopting e-banking and e-procurement. Publishing financial reports creates trust amongst stakeholders i.e. they believe that the units from which they are purchasing, hold high financial creditability and good reputation in market. Participants highlighted the need to conduct international seminars and conferences in which the textile units and government can exchange new ideas about how to use wind, sun and other energy sources for the production of electricity to run textile machines. Seminars and conferences guide the government, textile industry and various other stakeholders regarding how to improve current position and infrastructure of textile industry through the adoption of new workplace practices and advance technologies. The Indian government recently started efforts for the skills development of its workforce. For example, the Ministry of Textiles in 2010 announced a major governmental program for skills development of workers through Integrated Skills Development Scheme and resultantly a Ministry of Skills Development & Entrepreneurship was created in 2014 for consolidating all training programs. A key role was played in this regard by the pan-Indian Apparel Training & Design Centre (ATDC) to provide skills training for apparel sector and there are over 200 such training centres across the country. A flagship training centre was established by ATDC following the introduction of this scheme. The training centre was called SMART (Skills for Manufacturing of Apparels through Research & Training). The aim of the centre was to increase the skills development of workers so that skilled labour could be provided to RMG sector. Fast track vocational training courses were offered under SMART which spanned 1 to 4 months. SMART also used skill camps for enhancing the industrial employability of rural poor including women and low caste people. However, there is still limited number of people who enrolled themselves in such programs.

Finding the causes of turn down in textile sector in Pakistan is third objective of this study. Existing literature shows that government of Pakistan has borrowed about US\$92 billion and above from USA, China and IMF but cannot pay even interest instalments. Now, Pakistani government has to borrow more money to pay these interest instalments. Resultantly, these excessive borrowing lead to currency devaluation and increase the production cost and duties, taxes and tariffs on exports and imports. All these factors reduce the ability of small and medium textile units to import heavy machinery and modern technologies from other well-developed countries, thus cannot bring changes at workplace that are necessary to improve profits and productivity. Moreover, currency devaluation strongly and negatively influenced the textile industry in terms of employees' income level, imports, exports, growth, and development (Abbas et al., 2012; Afzal, 2012; Shah et al., 2012). Another major reason behind decline in profit level of textile units is high taxes over textile products. over last two decades, heavy shortfall of energy sources (gas and electricity) has enforced many small textile units to either close their businesses or increase the per unit price. Studies have revealed that previous 4 governments had not properly planned about energy supply. Resultantly, Pakistani industry has to face severe energy crisis that in turn reduced the production level and increased the poverty level amongst employees. Another study highlighted many external and internal factors that can negatively influence employment opportunities particularly in textile industry (Hussain, 2017). Moreover, many small units and mills have reduced the labour shift as they cannot sell the textile products at higher production cost. Recently, a survey has reported that textile industry in Pakistan is currently accomodating about 40% and above of total labour force(Memon, 2016; Mangi & Kay, 2016). Moreover, strikes, protests, temporary closing the units raise many challenges that lead to increase poverty level, crime rate and stress ratio because of lowering income level (Afzal, 2012; Khan et al., 2014).

Study findings also reveal that how majority of textile employees, owners and management have closed their units and protested against government for long due to its negligence as well as poor or no future planning. Some respondents further argued that besides of strikes, huge energy shortfalls or crises have also unable the textile units to complete the orders on time. Resultantly, they have to outsource raw materials to meet with requirements of their clients. Majority of personnel attached

with textile industry are in hand-to-mouth situation because of losing their jobs, thus cannot afford groceries, school fee and house rent. Moreover, terrorist attacks, war and political instability in Pakistan are other challenges that have strongly and negatively influenced the overall business growth in Pakistan. These factors have also limited the activities of farmers, buyers and many investors, who feel hesitation while investing their financial capital in textile industry. Politicians in Pakistan are very corrupt and used to spend huge proportion of foreign debt, aid and budget for making personal assets, offshore companies and illegal money. These unresolved public issues have left many challenges for present government particularly in form of payments of national debts, energy crises and high rate of taxes. Respondents further highlighted that due to poorly developed ICT infrastructure, textile industry has no potential to use e-procurement, e-commerce or brick & brick business models. Moreover, using traditional working methods do not allow the textile industry to develop its database on internet. Developing database enables the businesses to significantly increase their customers, positive WOM, recommendations and social influence for others, online orders booking and customer access. Moreover, seminal work of Irvine and Martin (1984) enables us to define and understand technology foresight (TF) as it is conceived today and also encourages the world to proliferate the TF exercises. Following Japan, France took initiative to exercise “foresight” activities in 1980s and after France, Sweden, Canada and Australia started these initiatives (UNIDO, 2005). TF, however, gained momentum during 1990s and got expended in UK, US, Germany and Netherlands. While one country was performing foresight activities, other countries planned to engage in same activities to be competitive (UNIDO, 2005). In fact, TF was highly appreciated as most valuable tool for identifying market oriented, forward looking and fast innovation policies mutually agreed by private sector and government. Recently, developing countries have widely embraced foresight activities as strategic tool so that they can get closer to technological frontier (Rothkipf, 2012). It is generally assumed that cutting edge technologies are only considered for industrialised countries which is now has been overcome. This narrow indication is often discussed in literature as “leap-frogging” (Helmedag, 2019).

In addition to that, organizational and national cultures create several challenges. The national culture of Pakistan is characterised by high political involvement, power

distance, conflicts, cultural inertia, but limited future planning. These factors have direct association with corporate culture of the textile industry. The textile owners, for example, who have strong relationships with politicians, generally enjoy special attention in context of government services. Contrary to that, those small textile units that have no such associations may face numerous difficulties in getting government services. It is generally argued that the culture that is highly supportive for power distance and collectivism always tends to maximise organizational politics i.e. only few powerful individuals get the power whereas rest of individuals cannot protect even their personal interest. The employees, for example, who are involved in buttering and flattering, usually get job, transfer, promotion and less work overload. Moreover, lower literacy rate in Pakistan cannot encourage the employees of textile mills to adopt and implement modern technologies. Resultantly, they show more resistance towards the adoption of new technologies or changes. These factors thus, enforced the SMEs and most of textile mills to use traditional working practices (e.g. manual machinery handling, manual cash handling and manual procurement), which require higher operational cost and more staff. Moreover, traditional work methods involve a higher number of staff who is engaged in repeated tasks, which is total wastage of time. As all these factors lead to increase the overall production cost thus unable the small textile units to bear low profits or break-even points.

Making recommendation for textile industry to improve its current infrastructure is fourth objective of this study. Based on study findings it is suggested to textile industry to adopt advance methods and advance technologies in order to bring improvement in its current infrastructure and increase profit and workplace productivity. Respondents have highlighted various countries that are adopting modern technologies in light of industry 4.0. Therefore, suggested to Pakistani textile industry to develop its ICT infrastructure, and enhance employees` skills and motivations so that industry 4.0 technologies can be adopted and implemented. Previous studies recognised that through adoption of industry 4.0, number of workers can be reduced and decisions making about fabric and yarn can be improved. It also helps to maintain supplier invoices, ledgers and information about contracts. Moreover, e-procurement enables the SMEs and textile mills to add value in supply chain. Additionally, it saves both time as well as administrative and operational costs. Robotic industry is viewed as a major source of bringing

improvements in decline of Pakistani textile industry. It will also create competitive advantages not only for large textile mills but also for SMEs.

Based on study findings, it is suggested to textile industry to specify reasonable amount of budget for R&D so that a platform can be created through which traditional working practices can be shifted to modern technologies (e.g. laser printing, industry 4.0, 3D printers and digital printing). Adoption of these modern technologies will enable the textile units to decrease the production cost and improve the textile products in terms of quality. Respondents suggested the government to make heavy investment for the development of ICT infrastructure, also use other energy sources (e.g. wind and sun) as alternative of electricity because these are less expense as compare to other sources. By adopting digital open and e-government system, government can generate online database about the steps through which government is facilitating textile sector. Moreover, these systems lead to increase accountability, fast service delivery and transparency. Moreover, providing online information may also attract suppliers, sellers, buyers, investors and other textile industry's stakeholders for making decisions. Respondents also highlighted that government should make proper plans to improve political stability and increase security and safety so that more and more international marketers, buyers and suppliers can be attracted towards Pakistani textile industry. This can also be done through arranging international seminars and conferences for foreign buyers and investors. Technology foresight (TF) practices have capacity to overcome these emerging complexities because TF systematically embodies the programs that help to study priorities and innovation plans to foresee, direct and shape potential future technological changes (Maw et al., 2012). For this purpose, it involves active participation of different actors like civil society, industry, experts and government that collectively define a common vision of potential future (Miles, 2010). Experts from private sector and science/academia play very crucial role among all TF participants because they better understand technological issues from policy maker perspectives and thus help to minimize the uncertainty associated with unprecedented technological changes (Schäfer, 2018). The purpose lies behind these TF exercises is that overall positive games with expected and more effective outcomes can be generated particularly with respect to effective technological

advancement and more sustainable socio-economic benefits which is not possible by isolated initiatives each actor individually take (Jacobi, & Andersen, 2016).

Study findings also reveal that high duties on imports and exports and high taxes have reduced the profit level of textile industry to greater extent, whereas some SMEs have to survive on break-even points. Moreover, government should develop positive relationships with its neighbouring countries so that exports can be increased and currency can be stabilised. Government should also get interest free loaning from Islamic states so that burden on textile industry in form of high taxes can be reduced. According to respondents, Pakistani government should focus on making appropriate plans regarding to invest heavily in wind energy, solar energy and various other economic resources. Nowadays, the high rates of gas and electricity have increased the overall production cost for industrial firms, whereas profit level is quite low. In this regard, government should immediately take necessary steps in order to ensure the survival of those SMEs that are yielding minor profit. Because if textile units get closed in large number than government revenue and employment opportunities would be decreased whereas inflation ratio, crime rate and unemployment would be increased, particularly in countries with low level of income. Limited financial capital, traditional working practices and technology models, unskilled labour, and lack of interest towards R&D are the major challenges for SMEs (Syed et al., 2012; Khattak et al., 2011; Ortolano et al., 2014). According to these studies, unproductive practices can be converted into productive ones through the adoption of modern technologies.

Now, there is intense need that textile sector, government and other related stakeholders should change the education sector particularly with respect to textile industry. It has been observed that a large proportion of our youth is interested in studying business administration, whereas strength of our economy is textile mills, flour mills and rice mills. Thus, it is important for government to introduce such subject combination that can change the education industry in context of advance methods and new technologies. Government, for example, should introduce the subjects on modern workplace methods and advance technologies that can increase information level of students. If students have knowledge about digital printing, laser printing, 3D printers and industry 4.0, they will readily embrace these technologies on joining the textile industry. The previous studies related to change management

showed that higher level of knowledge and information sharing always remains supportive for adoption of technology and other workplace related changes (Aslam, et al., 2016; Muqadas et al., 2017; Aslam et al., 2018).

Existing literature on TF refers it an exercise composed of variety of different activities such as anticipation, systematically looking forward, looking ahead activities, forecasting, technology road-mapping, prognostic amongst others, futures research and strategic intelligence (Miles, 2010 and Phaal et al. 2004). In 1970s, Japan – the country where TF was initially incepted – used to entitle its national technological planning studies as “forecast activity” that was initially performing as “technology foresight” in very refined manner (Miles, 2010). Later on, in mid of 1980s, Irvine and Martin (1984) presented their seminal work that immensely inspired old Japanese traditions in TF and S&T, based on which these “forecasting” practices are nowadays called as “foresight” activities. However, this difference is unimportant. Typically, close circles of various experts perform forecasting activities and predict future contingencies on basis of deterministic precision (Chia, et al., 2019). Resultantly, their outcomes represent a common vision of entire world with specific point of the view. TF, on other pole, reflects broader vision of entire world with strategically integration in policy strategies. The resultant outcomes represent insights for future oriented S&T policies, which not “predict” but “create” the future (Miles, 2010) with intense focus on learning process (van Dijk, 1991) and dialog amongst various actors and disciplines (Elzinga, 1983). According to respondents, majority of large textile mills and SMEs are using outdated technologies for home products, cotton spinning, cotton yarn, fabric processing, knitwear, cloth, readymade, towels and hosiery. Resultantly, we are not providing the textile products of quality as per demanded by international standards. Therefore, textile units are unable to get highest profit and maximum production. Moreover, education sector in Pakistan is not producing the students with ability to use advance technology and bring about new ideas. Existing literature reveals that e-commerce models have not been completely and successfully adopted because of poor ICT infrastructure, energy crises and less awareness about modern technologies in context of textile industry (Afzal 2012; Khattak et al., 2011; Ortolano, et al., 2014). Respondents suggested the educational institutions and governments to focus heavily on R&D so that maximum awareness about modern methods and technologies can be ensured.

Based on study findings it is argued that manufacturing practices, HR practices, efforts about providing online data on textile industry and ICT infrastructure is not well developed in textile industry of Pakistan. Adoption of HPWS system would enable the textile industry to make appropriate decisions about recruitment, motivation, training, performance appraisal, compensation to workers and skills development. It has been observed that the organizations which have adopted this most effective system become even more productive mainly because this system not only facilitates in developing human capital but also improves the level of knowledge and skills for effective completion of routine tasks. According to existing literature, Pakistani textile industry is currently not producing quality fabrics and cotton (Abbas et al., 2012; Khan 2010; Khattak et al., 2011; Khan et al., 2014). Study findings reveal that textile industry in Pakistan has not yet adopted lean manufacturing thus is bearing high production cost while getting less competitive advantages and profit. Respondents suggested the textile mills and SMEs to improve the quality of various textile products by improving their processes and reducing the required efforts and time. Moreover, adoption of HPWS practices and lean manufacturing will enable the textile units to identify unproductive employees and processes, and increase the performance, efficiency and effectiveness that are key parameters for generating competitive advantages.

Moreover, Pakistani textile industry has not well-developed cyber data sharing platform, thus cannot create financial & loss statements, balance sheets and other kinds of financial statements. As SMEs do not publish their financial reports, therefore cannot attract the investors and money lenders to invest money or offer loan for SMEs development. Thus, it is suggested to SMEs to hire financial specialists for the creation and online publication of their financial reports. This will enhance not only the opportunities for borrowing but also will attract more international and national investors. Moreover, government should also provide safe and secure environment in order to facilitate the textile industry to arrange international seminars and conferences where it can share important data with bankers, buyers, investors, researchers and other related stakeholders. By expanding “infant industry” related arguments to case study of infant economy, Greenwald and Stiglitz (2013; 2014) discussed how well-designed policies on intellectual property, industry and trade are helpful in developing learning societies.

They argued that “creating a learning society is more likely to increase standards of living than the small, one-time improvements in economic efficiency or those that derive from sacrifices of consumption today to deepen capital” (Greenwald and Stiglitz, 2013, p. 45). Moreover, their approach for learning, technology upgrading, and knowledge is originated from neoclassical tradition. They develop this approach on the basis of analysis of market failures due to production and distribution of knowledge and information and of market failures due to innovation and distribution of finance knowledge (Lauridsen, 2010).

Moreover, international seminars and conferences increase the opportunities to invite successful foreign textile employees and owners to learn from them about how to further grow and develop the textile sector. In addition to that, it is prime responsibility of textile owners as well as government to invest heavily in development of ICT infrastructure in order to make textile industry capable of adopting new technologies like e-procurement, industry 4.0, brick and brick e-commerce method, e-banking and other business models. In clusters, the industries or grouping firms may enable these complementarities to be realized (Porter 2000; Duranton and Puga 2004). Firstly, big cluster of companies will efficiently construct undividable facilities like infrastructure to pay fix cost to special input providers to enter local larger market. Secondly, larger market better match employers with employees, buyers with suppliers or financiers with entrepreneurs (Rice, 2004). Thirdly, in clusters, the direct interactions among economic agents facilitate the learning about market evolutions, new kinds of firms or new technologies. Labour pooling, knowledge spill overs at industry level and local input-output relationships are the various externalities that emerges when large clusters of companies come close in same sector or industry (Krugman 1991; Marshall 1920). Generally, more urbanized economies have many producers although in different sectors or industries but at same place. Management consulting firm, for example, can grab the benefits from nearby located manufacturers, financial service provider and business schools (Rosenthal & Strange, 2004).

6.4 RESEARCH FRAMEWORK

Figure 6.24 Proposed policy framework for the textile industry in Pakistan

The enablers, benefits, challenges, and opportunities may vary between advanced countries, emerging economies, and developing countries with respect to textile industry. Therefore, we cannot bring and implement those practices which are developed and implemented in those countries where the level of information sharing, knowledge exchange, employee skills, energy sources, advanced technologies, and politics different from Pakistan. Previous studies have documented that the international market shares of Pakistani textile sector have decreased due to various crises (i.e. economic, energy, and obsolete technology) (Ahmed & Siddiqui, 2016; Shah, et al., 2014; Mangi & Kay, 2016). The studies have also highlighted that these challenges have increased the cost of production and decrease the market opportunities for Pakistani textile sector (Shah, et al., 2014; Mangi & Kay, 2016). Other studies have indicated that internal and external factors (i.e. obsolete technology, traditional working environment, economic and energy crises) closed many textile units as well as cancel the orders of many international buyers (Ahmed & Siddiqui, 2016; Jameel, et al., 2014). The purpose of this study is to highlight the

current position of textile industry and what are causes of the decline in the textile industry in Pakistan. After identifying the causes current study has suggested enablers as well as recommendation with the purpose to bring improvement in current position of textile industry. The research data have been collected from high ranked employees and owners of textile industry with the help of semi-structure interviews.

The first objective is to discuss the evolution of the textile industry in Pakistan. Pakistani textile industry is producing cotton since the period of 1947. In the starting period, Pakistan has only 3 mills which have increased up to 600 until the end of 20th century. Furthermore, the numbers of spindles are also significantly increased (i.e.177000) to eight hundred and five million. At present, 317 composite units and 396 textile mills are operating in all over the Pakistan. Currently there are hundreds of small units, large spinning units, and ginning units in one province of Pakistan. Now-a-days, Pakistan is known as the best cotton producer in Asia and textile manufacturing industry is known as largest source of revenue generation for Pakistani economy. The respondents of this also highlighted that the textile industry is in top ten ranking in the context of largest exporting products of textile as well as best cotton producer. Most of the Pakistani economy is dependent on agriculture sector products (wheat, cotton, and rice) (Memon, 2016; Mangi & Kay, 2016). These agriculture products improve the life of individuals farmers as well as those people who are attached with rice, flour, and textile mills. It is also found that some industrial cities in Pakistan (i.e. Faisalabad, Sheikhpura, and Sialkot) are contributing on very high rate in GDP. It is also highlighted by a study that textile sector is one of largest manufacturing sector of Pakistani as it is contributing at very higher rate in GDP [CITATION Cae08 \l 2057].

Due to high contribution of textile sector in GDP, It has ranked the country among the top Asian and global producers and exporters of textile items with the statistics of ten percent contribution to the national gross domestic production (GDP) [CITATION Law15 \l 2057]. However, there are still many challenges which have negatively influenced the performance and output of textile sector in Pakistan. These challenges are discussed in the context of technology, financial, government, infrastructure, and culture perspectives. Recent studies have recommended that if developing countries are interested to bring economic development by technology

adoption then these countries must improve their industrial policies (Hutchinson & Dowd 2018; Hendrickson, 2015; Khan, Dongping, & Ghauri, 2014). Khan & Khan (2010) have noticed that more than 60-percent of Pakistani exports are included different textile products.

The second objective is to assess the current position of the textile industry in Pakistan. It has found that the infrastructure of textile, education, government support, national and organizational culture, use of technology, cost of production, and level of skills are not very supportive for textile industry in Pakistan. In textile industry, respondents have reported that SMEs are struggling to stay alive and survive as compared to large textile units. These SMEs have limited capital, obsolete technology, traditional working methods, access to local market, and could not publish online financial reports. These factors have significantly increased the cost of production and decrease the level of profits for SMEs. Studies have documented that most of textile sector is using very traditional working methods their employees are spending greater time to complete their work which increase the cost of production and decrease the level of competitive advantages for us (Abbas et al., 2012; Shah et al., 2012). These studies also suggested that Pakistani textile sector has too many opportunities for growth as it is one of the largest contributors of our economy as well as has attraction of international investors (Ahmed & Siddiqui, 2016; Shah, et al., 2014; Mangi & Kay, 2016). Most of financial institutions and money lenders are offering loans at very high interest rate that raised the uncertainty for survival of SMEs. Majority of textile units are using those looms and printing machinery which required high level of technical cost such as repair, maintenance, and employee monitoring. These challenges are high documentation requirements for textile loans, high interest rate, high cost of production inputs, unsupportive government planning and support, and energy crises (Khan & Khan 2010; Khattak et al., 2011; Khan et al., 2014).

The shortfall and high prices of gas and electricity has brought more challenges for those small units which are earning normal profit from buyers. One of the respondents has told that above 90-percent SMEs and textile mills have not invested in research and development practices. Therefore, these textile units cannot adopt the smart technologies which may decrease the cost of production in textile industry of Pakistan. The extent of literature has indicated that there is limited focus on

research and development department therefore the quality of cotton is very low and Pakistani textile industry is unable to earn high profit rate (Abbas et al., 2012; Khan & Khan 2010; Khattak et al., 2011; Khan et al., 2014). It is also found that there are limited specialized programs in education sector related to textile sector therefore most of the employees have not high level of awareness and knowledge about advanced textile practices. There are many factors that can improve the productivity and performance of textile sector such as technology and innovation, competitiveness, focus on trade, education and skills formation, rules and regulation for competition (Hendrickson, 2015; Vries, 2008). The major components of constant industrial development include industry upgrading, education, skills development, planning for SMEs development, diversification and restructuring (Hendrickson, 2015). All Pakistan Textile Mills Association (APTMA) have done many medial talks and issues many press releases in which they mentioned several challenges that hinder the textile growth. For example, they have discussed that how environmental and climate changes decreased the crop production among farmers. Most of crop is negatively influenced because of heavy rain fall as well as other viruses.

The third objective is to find out causes of the decline in the textile industry in Pakistan. Findings reveal that Pakistani governments have taken more than US\$92 billion and unable to pay the interest instalments. They borrowed money from China, IMF, and USA. Even now the situation is that the Pakistani government is borrowing money to paying the interest instalments of national debt. The excessive borrowing has brought devaluation in currency and increased the taxes, tariffs, and duties on cost of production as well as imports and exports. As a result, most of the small textile units are not financially capable to import advance technologies from developed nations. Therefore, these SMEs are unable to bring workplace changes with the purpose to improve productivity and profits. The extent of literature is indicated that how devaluation of currency impacted negatively to the textile imports, exports, income level of employees, textile development and growth (Abbas et al., 2012; Afzal, 2012; Shah et al., 2012). Furthermore, high taxes on textile commodities also brought major decrease in the level of profit. From previous two decades, the energy crises (huge short fall of electricity and gas) have closed many small units and increased the unit price and demand of energy for textile industry. It is also found that previous four governments could not plan regarding the energy supply

and as a result there is high load shedding for electricity and gas in Pakistan which decreased the level of production and poverty among employees. A study has documented that how the internal and external factors negatively influence the labour employment opportunities in textile sector therefore more people have lost their jobs and it also increased the poverty level (Hussain, 2017). It is also found that many mills and small units have decreased the shifts of labour because they are unable to sell textile commodities on higher cost of production. Recent studies told that textile sector has engaged approximately more than 40-percent of labour force (Memon, 2016; Mangi & Kay, 2016). Therefore, the temporary closure of units, strikes, protests can bring significant challenges especially it increases the level of poverty, stress and ratio for crime rate due to low-income country (Afzal, 2012; Khan et al., 2014).

The results reveal that various textile owners, management, and employees told how they have temporarily closed many units for long time as well as protested government for its negligence and limited future planning. Due to energy crises and strikes, some respondents have highlighted that how their textile units unable to fulfil the demands of orders therefore they outsource raw material for fulfilling the commitments with their clients. Furthermore, most of labour in surrounded area of textile sector have spent most of their time in the situation of hand to mouth. Because they have lost their job and unable to afford rent, children school fee, and amount for groceries. It is also found that political instability, war and terror situation in Pakistan, and terrorist attacks have negatively impacted the growth of businesses. Due to these factors, many investors, buyers, and farmers are limited their activities and more hesitant to invest their money in textile sector. Majority of politicians are corrupt in Pakistan, and they have spent most of the budget, aid, and debt amount for making the illegal money, offshore companies, and personal assets. Therefore, there are unable to solve the public issues and as a result they have left the challenges of 30 to 40 years for current government especially in the context of energy crises, national debt payments, taxes, and support for textile sector. Respondents have admitted that The ICT infrastructure is not fully developed therefore majority of textile industry is not using e-procurement, brick and click business or e-commerce business models. Due to traditional working methods, they are unable to develop their database over the internet which can significantly

increase the number of customers and their enquires, word of mouth, social influence and recommendation for others, customer access and online order booking and other benefits.

The national and organizational culture creates more challenges. For example, Pakistan national culture is popular for high power distance, political involvement and influence, limited thinking about future, more conflicts, and culture inertia. These factors are directly linked with the organizational culture of textile sector. For example, those textile owners who have relationship with politicians able to get special attention related to government services. On the other hand, those small units which have no connection with politicians may unable to take government services immediately. There is no doubt that the culture which support to high collectivism and power distance always increase organizational politics in which few powerful people gain power while other persons cannot protect their personal interests. For example, those employees can get job, promotion, transfer, and low work overload who is involved in flattering and buttering. Furthermore, the literacy rate is not very high in Pakistan therefore textile mills employees are more hesitant to adopt recent technologies. As a result, resistance to change is high towards adopting new technologies. Due to these factors, most of mills and SMEs are using traditional working methods such as manual procurement, manual cash handling, and machinery which requires more staff and high operational costs. Due to manual procurement, manual cash handling, obsolete machinery, there are high number of employees and they are wasting their time in repeated tasks. These factors also increased the cost of production and small units are unable to bear break even points or low profits.

The fourth objective is to suggest the enablers of textile industry that can improve the current infrastructure of textile industry. Findings reveal that textile sector must focus on advanced technologies and advanced methods to improve the current infrastructure as well as workplace productivity and profit. Respondents have suggested that many countries are adopting the advanced technologies with the helping of bringing industry 4. Therefore, Pakistan textile sector must develop the ICT infrastructure, employee's motivation and skills that can support the adoption and implementation of industry 4 technologies. Furthermore, findings reveal that industry 4 can minimize the number of employees and improve the decision making

for yarn and fabric. The adoption of e-procurement method can improve the decision making related to maintain ledgers, supplier invoices, transactions, and other information related to contracts. By adoption of e-procurement method, textile mills and SMEs can create value in the network of supply chain management, and it will save the time and cost of operational and administrative expenses of textile sector. It is also suggested that robotic industry can bring major improvements to improve the decline of textile industry and able to generate competitive advantages for both textile mills and SMEs.

Findings reveal that textile sector must specify budget for research and development department that can create platform to shift from traditional working style to advance level of technologies such as industry 4, laser printing, digital printing, and 3D Printers for fabrics. Respondents have suggested that they have strong intention to adopt e-procurement, laser printing, digital printing, and 3D Printers so that they can decrease the cost of production as well as increase the quality of textile sector commodities. However, respondents have suggested that government should invest maximum amount to develop ICT infrastructure and invest money to bring energy through sun and wind which is less expense than other ways. It is a need to time that government should adopt e-government and digital open government system which can create online database regarding what type of steps government is taking to facilitate textile sector and these system are also supportive to increase the transparency, accountability, and services delivery for public and private sector. Furthermore, these systems can provide online information which may attractive for investors, buyers, sellers, suppliers, and other stakeholders of textile sector for taking decisions. Majority of respondents have suggested that the current government should do planning to improve bring political stability, more safety and security so that international buyers, suppliers, and marketers can visit to textile sector as well as the textile sector can arrange international conferences and seminars for investors and buyers.

Findings reveal that due to high taxes and duties on exports and imports current textile sector is earning very normal profit and some of SMEs are surviving on break even points. It is recommended that government should improve the relationship with close neighbour countries which may increase the exports as well as stabilize the current position of currency. Furthermore, it is also suggested that government

can take interest free loans from Islamic countries which may helpful to decrease the level of taxes loads from textile sector. Respondents have suggested that Pakistani government must create a proper plan to increase the investment in solar energy, wind energy and other economical sources. Currently the unit price of electricity and gas for industrial companies is very high and due to it cost of production is very high whereas the level of profit is low. All the respondents have suggested the current government has to take immediate step so that those SMEs can survive that is earning very minimum profit. The closure of more textile units can decrease the level of government revenue, employment opportunities for labour, unemployment and inflation ratio, and crime rate in a low-income country. The extent of literature has indicated the challenges of SMEs due to limited capital, unskilled labour, traditional technology models, and limited focus on research and new ways (Syed et al., 2012; Khattak et al., 2011; Ortolano et al., 2014). Furthermore, these studies also recommended to adopt recent technologies that can convert the unproductive practices into productive practices.

It is need of time that government, textile sector, and other stakeholders must bring changes in education sector especially the point of view textile sector. For example, it is found that majority of young generation is focus on business administration subjects while the strength of Pakistan economy is the rice, flour, and textile mills. Therefore, government should introduce the combination of subjects that can bring changes in education sector with respect to new technologies and advance methods. For example, government can introduce a subject with advance technologies and workplace methods in which students can increase the level of information and knowledge. If students are aware about e-procurement, industry 4, laser printing, digital printing, and 3D Printers then they can show more positive support to introduce these technologies when they will join the textile sector. The extent of literature on change management revealed that high level of information and knowledge exchange always create positive support for technology adoption as well as other workplace changes (Aslam, et al., 2016; Muqadas et al., 2017; Aslam et al., 2018).

Respondents have mentioned that most of textile units are using obsolete technologies for cotton spinning, home products, fabric processing, cotton yarn and

cloth, knitwear, hosiery and towels, readymade. Therefore, the level of quality as well as the production level is not as per the international standards and demand. As a result, these textile units are suffering to get maximum production and profit. Findings revealed that the Pakistani education sector is completely unable to produce those students who can bring new ideas and advance use of technology. Previous studies have indicated that the adoption of e-commerce models is not fully successful because of energy crises, under-developed ICT infrastructure, as well as low level of awareness about advance technologies for textile sector in Pakistan (Afzal 2012; Khattak et al., 2011; Ortolano, et al., 2014). They have suggested that government and educational institutions to create more focus on research and development departed related to textile sector which can bring more awareness about recent technologies and methods.

The current study has found that HR practices, manufacturing practices, ICT infrastructure, and the efforts to provide online data about textile industry is very much under-developed in the textile sector in Pakistan. By adopting HPWS system, the textile sector may able to take wise decision with respect to recruitment, training and motivation, skills development, performance appraisal, and compensation to employees. By adopting this effective system, it is found that most of the organizations have become more productive because it supports to develop human capital as well as level of skills and knowledge for completing routine tasks effectively. The literature has also indicated that Pakistani textile sector is unable to produce quality cotton and fabrics (Abbas et al., 2012; Khan & Khan 2010; Khattak et al., 2011; Khan et al., 2014). Current study findings also revealed that the textile industry is far away to adopt lean manufacturing therefore they are bearing high level of cost of production and low level of profit as well as competitive advantages. Therefore, it is recommended that SMEs and other textile mills can improve the process as well as quality of textile commodities by improving the processes and minimize the required time as well as efforts. By adopting lean manufacturing and HPWS practices, textile units can easily identify the unproductive procedures and processes as well as the unproductive employees. These systems can bring the efficiency, effectiveness, and high performance that are important parameters for creating competitive advantages.

It is found that the cyber information sharing platform is not fully developed especially in the SMEs of textile industry in Pakistan. Further, most of these SMEs are unable to create balance sheet, financial and loss statement, and other financial statements. Without publishing the report and authentic data, the money lenders as well as investors are not ready to offer loan or invest money for the development of SMEs. Therefore, it is a need of time that SMEs should hire financial experts that can create and publish financial reports online so that there are more chances for borrowing money as well as attract the national and international investors. It is also suggested that government should create the environment of safety and security so that the textile sector can arrange international conferences and seminars regarding sharing the key data with researchers, investors, buyers, bankers, and other stakeholders. By conducting seminars and conferences, it is a huge possibility that we can invite successful international textile owners and employees and learn from their experiences regarding how the textile industry can be further develop and grow. The government and textile owners must invest huge amount of money with the purpose to develop ICT infrastructure otherwise they are unable to adopt the recent technologies such as industry 4, e-procurement, e-banking, brick and click and other e-commerce models.

CHAPTER 7: CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

7.1 CONCLUSION

The study has highlighted the current position of textile industry in Pakistan. The study has concluded many strengths and weakness with the purpose to create a fair discussion regarding what steps must be taken by textile sector stakeholders to improve processes, technology, financial position, productivity, performance, quality, timely completion of orders related to textile commodities. However, there are more challenges for textile industry which very negatively impacted in last 20 to 30 years in Pakistan. It has been found that existing infrastructure is not very supportive with respect to investing money in research and development activities, adopting advance workplace practices, and new technologies. There are many challenges to adopt recent practices such as these textile units have limited capital, unskilled and unprofessional labour, under-developed infrastructure, and low level of employee and organizational support. Therefore, the decline of textile industry continues in terms of closing units, importing new technologies, unemployment among labours, limited competitive advantages, low attraction in international market, and declining exports in national and international market.

7.2 ANSWERS TO THE RESEARCH QUESTIONS

Table 7.11 Answer of research questons

<u>Research questions</u>	<u>Answer based on the research findings</u>
What are the causes of the decline in Pakistan textile industry?	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• The previous and current political governments of Pakistan have borrowed US\$92 billion and above dollars from IMF, China and USA, which pressurizes the Pakistani currency by paying instalments at higher interest rate and by devaluation. But unfortunately, this money is being used by corrupt

administration and politicians in form of making their personal assets. Resultantly, this corruption leads to produce many burdens for businesses in form of heavy tariffs, taxes, exports and import duties etc.

- It is found that textile owners cannot import updated technology and heavy machinery due to high currency devaluation as it can further increase the overall production cost. These extra financial burden and high taxes have enforced majority of SMEs in textile sector to shut down their businesses.
- Load shedding of electricity for long duration makes it tough for SMEs and other industries to survive. Although Pakistani government has defined strict punishments for energy stealing but the increased electricity rate and long electric shortage duration has decreased labour shifts and wages, overall growth opportunities and profit rates of textile industry.
- It is also found that Pakistani government has no appropriate energy plans due to which textile businesses have to face high gas and electricity load shedding in Pakistan.
- Lower profitability, higher debt to equity ratio and lack of focus to publish financial reports are the main factors that make it difficult for textile industry to achieve investor confidence or get financial support.
- During the debate regarding current textile infrastructure, there are several strengths such as 317 composite units and 396 textile mills which are accommodating maximum labour and giving them earning for affording their basic needs. Furthermore, the textile sector has gotten significant position in Asian market with respect to textile cotton as well as textile exports which is approximately 60-percent or more.
- The textile industry constitutes a pivotal part of the economic and social life in Pakistan. The textile production value chain has great impact on the overall economic and social life in Pakistan. It starts with over ten million farmers solely relying on

How competitive is this industry?

the cotton crop to live and provide for their families. They are agreed that cotton has been the top strategic agricultural product of Pakistan providing source of living for a large group of farmers and ranking the country as the fourth cotton producer and third cotton consumer worldwide.

- The sector is the major buyer of the country's over-five-billion-dollar cotton production and the largest supporter of exports with over 60% of national export returns generated from textile. Textile owners are agreed that the quality of cotton is high and attractive for national and international market. therefore, still the textile industry has many opportunities even when there are more challenges for textile industry which very negatively impacted in last 20 to 30 years in Pakistan. It has been found that existing infrastructure is not very supportive with respect to investing money in research and development activities, adopting advance workplace practices, and new technologies.

What can be done to revive the industry and increase its global competitiveness?

It is suggested that textile sector owners and political government must create a plan to invest money in cheap energy sources, development of ICT infrastructure, and loans for small units so that SMEs can survive in industry.

- It is also recommended that government and security agencies of Pakistan must provide safe and secure environment which can create trust among international investors regarding the investment and higher rate. They cannot invest money in uncertain situation where the probability of risk and loss is high.
- The government of Pakistan should offer the loan to these SMEs and ensure that these loans are only utilized with the purpose to improve the overall technological infrastructure of SME so that these SMEs can decrease the overall cost of production.
- It is recommended that textile sector should invest in technology 4 because it can reduce the salaries cost as well as employee efforts and resources on manual procedures. These advance textile technologies can bring major improvements in cotton

spinning, home products, fabric processing, cotton yarn and cloth, knitwear, hosiery and towels, readymade textile products. With the help of these advanced technologies, textile sector can easily control the cost of production and increase the level of profit rate.

- The textile owners, management, and government have to ensure that all the financial reports and other textile records should be online records because it can offer strategic confidence to national and international investors to invest money in the development of the textile sector.
- The government has to prepare an immediate plan with respect to producing energy from waste or trash, sun and wind, and other renewable energy resources.

The climate and environmental changes always negatively hit the agriculture sector of Pakistan. For example, high temperature and heavy rain fall are very common in those areas which are familiar to produce maximum cotton. Therefore, farmers are unable to control these factors and it decreases the production of cotton. It is also found that the educational system is not very supportive, and it is producing those students who are not able to create competitive advantages for the textile industry. Due to this, most of the practices are manual such as manual procurement method, paper-based working environment, and low level of technical experts. As a result, most of the employees are spending their energies and time without producing a high level of productivity and performance. During the presence of these traditional working procedures, it is not possible that SMEs and other textile units can achieve the high productivity and profit. Therefore, most of the small units have suffered with huge financial losses and these units have closed palmately.

Previous Pakistani governments have borrowed a very heavy amount and now Pakistan is borrowing more money to pay the instalments of interests and principal amounts. The high political corruption has increased further challenges because they utilized the borrowed money for making offshore companies and other personal assets within and outside the country. The borrowed amount cannot be invested in the textile industry due to corrupt politicians. As a result, the textile industry is suffering due to

energy crises, high taxes on profits, high duties on imports and exports, as well as the continuous devaluation of currency. Currently textile sector especially the SMEs are unable to pay taxes on the importing of advance machineries from other countries. Due to these taxes, SMEs are also limited to sell their textile commodities in international market. The high cost of production, inflation, and low employment opportunities brought more child labour and strikes in textile sector. It is also found that terrorism attacks negatively influenced the growth opportunities as buyers and employees are feeling insecure and unsafe during travelling and moving. The culture inertia has significantly enhanced many challenges as most of the existing labour and other employees are not very comfortable to accept, learn, and adopt workplace change in the form of new technologies. Therefore, most of the working procedures are very traditional because employees have low intention to accept new change. It is also found that most of the labour is not very well qualified and earning their wages on per hour base or minimum monthly salaries.

Current study has given some practical recommendations with the purpose to improve existing infrastructure, government planning, textile industry culture, and current position of textile industry. First textile sector owners and government must invest money in cheap energy sources, development of ICT infrastructure, and loans for small units. The government and textile industry must produce energy through wind, waste, and solar system. They must import that machinery which use lowest energy and connect the whole system through wireless internet. The government of Pakistan must invest money in developing ICT infrastructure especially in SMEs which are unable to create big changes due to limited employees, vision and mission, and capital. It is also recommended that all the textile units must adopt and implement e-procurement and e-banking method so that they can decrease the number of employees, salaries cost, as well as time for repetitive work. Furthermore, they must create online database for all textile products otherwise they cannot create link with international buyers and investors. By adoption e-commerce model such as brick and click, textile sector can create online information as well as take order online without wasting time in meetings and handling the customers physically.

It is the need of time that textile sector should adopt industry 4 technologies, laser printing, and 3D technologies for producing quality fabrics. There is no doubt that Industry 4 can reduce the salaries cost as well as employee efforts and resources on

manual procedures. With the help of these advanced technologies, textile sector can easily control the cost of production and increase the level of profit rate. Without investing on these tools, they are unable to improve the productivity as well as quality as per international standards. These technologies can bring major improvements in cotton spinning, home products, fabric processing, cotton yarn and cloth, knitwear, hosiery and towels, readymade textile products. By adopting these technologies, textile sector can increase the exports as well as create attraction for international investors as well as buyers. It is also recommended that there must be significant changes in education sector so that students are aware about these technologies and able to accept technologies without resistance. It is also recommended that government and other stakeholders must provide safe and secure environment which can create trust among international investors regarding the investment and higher rate. By conducting more seminars and conferences, textile sector can exchange knowledge with international businessmen, researchers, buyers, suppliers, and other stakeholders about the potential and growth of textile sector.

7.3 POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS

- The government of Pakistan has to cooperate with textile mills and SMEs with the purpose to prepare training program contents on industry 4 practices, e-procurement, brick and click, online banking system, laser printing, digital printing, and 3D Printers. The purpose of training programs is to educate the owners and employees about how advance technologies can create competitive advantages with respect to quality, cost control, efficiency and effectiveness in work, and decrease the cost of production. The training programs can create motivation among owners and employees with respect to learn and update technology related knowledge and their use with respect to textile sector.

- The SMEs have not enough financial capital as well as did not publish financial reports therefore it is the government responsibility to develop the mechanism which can ensure that SMEs must publish the financial reports to accurately determine the equity, liabilities, and net income for tax purpose. Furthermore, government should offer the loan to these SMEs and ensure

that these loans are only utilized with the purpose to improve the overall technological infrastructure of SME so that these SMEs can decrease the overall cost of production.

- The political instability and security issues have negatively influenced the textile sector growth in Pakistan. Therefore, It is responsibility of Pakistani government to offer risk free environment and support the textile sector to arrange international conferences and seminars with the purpose to invite researchers, investors, buyers, bankers, and other stakeholders for investment, digitalization, knowledge and ideas sharing, and improvement purpose. These international conferences, seminars, and participation of key businessmen can create significant opportunities for textile sector with respect to growth and advance developments.
- The cost of production in textile sector is increased because of the high demand of electricity and gas whereas the supply of both gas and energy is short. Furthermore, the government of Pakistan has increased too many taxes on energy due to external debt. Therefore, it is hard especially for SMEs to survive for long run as these SMEs are already earning normal profit. The government has to prepare immediate plan with respect to produce energy from waste or trash, sun and wind, and other renewable energy resources. It can decrease the overall cost of production as well as bring the minimum government investment as compared to coal which is expensive.
- It has found that the level of external debt has been increased due to corruption and lack of transparency, accountability, and digitalization. The findings of this study has recommended that e-government and digital open government have become essential with the purpose to produce online evidence regarding what budget, planning and support, and strategies are proposed by government and what actions are taken by government to overcome the issues of textile sector in Pakistan. The online record about the textile sector can also give strategic confidence to national and international investors to invest money in the development of textile sector.

- The finding of this study has revealed especially the employees of SMEs are not very informative, skilled, and motivated with respect to bring improvement in their knowledge about advanced technology. Also, it is found that textile industry is far away to produce lean manufacturing therefore they are bearing high level of cost of production and low level of profit as well as competitive advantages. Therefore, it is essential for both textile mills and SMEs to adopt the HPWS work as well as lean manufacturing strategies with the purpose to improve employee skills, job performance evaluation, training and development, quality control, zero waste, and planning for innovation.
- It is found that Pakistani neighbour countries (e.g. china and India) are using advance textile printing machinery such as of laser printing, digital printing, and 3D Printers therefore their quality, cost of production, demand, and share in international market is more compared to Pakistani textile sector. On the other hand, Pakistan fabric is required more technical staff, repair of old machinery, monitoring, and other operational costs. Therefore, it is recommended for textile sector to create a plan that how they can import advance printing technology which can improve fabric quality, demand, and share in international market.
- The findings of this study revealed 80-percent of textile units either small or large have not focus on the effectiveness of research and development department. Therefore, they are far away to utilize the advance level of technologies and gaining limited level of competitive advantages. Therefore, it is recommended for both SMEs and larger textile units to invest in research and development department so that their employees are more aware about the knowledge and use of advanced technologies.
- Finally, the use of traditional procurement technology has increased the cost, time, and efforts of employees especially for SMEs. The world leading textile industries are more focused to create the effectiveness in supply chain management process. Therefore, it is recommended that the adoption of e-procurement technology is able to create and exchange online record about e-informing, e-auctioning, vendor management, order status, e-tendering, and

optimal stock decisions. Furthermore, e-procurement can bring more transparency and accountability in terms of inventory management and performance of employees in operations department.

7.4. Limitations and Future directions

Current study has identified barriers of textile sector as well as recommended some practical solution which must be taken by stakeholders. However, there are many limitations which can undermine the effectiveness, acceptability, and generalizability of this study. For example, cross-sectional time horizon supports to collect data once only therefore it can increase causality issues and results are not highly acceptable for one-time data collection tool. Therefore, it is convenient data must be collected from multiple times from different stakeholders so that it can create more acceptability and generalizability for results. The use of qualitative data collection tool (i.e. semi-structure interviews) can create more challenges with respect to biasness. The qualitative methods are always supportive to increase the leading questions as well as the use of research experiences as well as values, therefore current study cannot claim that results are completely bias free. Therefore, many studies have recommended to use mixture of qualitative and quantitative methods because it can remove the chances of research biasness. The chapter 5 (findings and analysis) lacks data but given the fact that this may not exist therefore future research can be conducted by adding various other stakeholders to provide further rich understanding as well as enhancing more generalizability of results.

Many studies have recommended that how cross-sectional studies, one data collection method, and non-probability sampling create many challenges for the acceptability of findings (Muqadas et al., 2017; Aslam, et al., 2016; Aslam, et al., 2018). Further, these factors always increase the common method variance in results which cannot remove from results. Therefore, it is recommended that same topic must be explored by using more than one data collection tools, different data collection periods, and from different geographical locations. It will ultimately increase the acceptability of results. The proposed research models can be tested in future by using quantitative methods so that researcher and industry may know that

how they can improve the current challenges of textile sector. Previous studies have argued that culture, regional, economic, financial, education, technology, social, and organizational factors are different between developing and developed countries (Muqadas et al., 2017; Aslam, et al., 2016; Aslam, et al., 2018), therefore we cannot say that these results are equally beneficial for both developed and developing countries. Further, data is collected from respondents which are living and working in one province in Pakistan. Therefore, we cannot say that overall textile sector is facing same type of challenges. In future, data can collect from different stakeholders from different geographical locations for enhancing more generalizability of results.

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9.1 APPENDIX 1: INTERVIEW QUESTIONS

Hello and thank you for agreeing to be interviewed for the purpose of my research.

1. Personal and organisational information

- 1.1. Age
- 1.2. Years in the industry
- 1.3. Please briefly describe the organisational structure of your textile business including any details you're happy to share such as you're the size of your firm, production capacity, number of employees and turnover.
- 1.4. Etc

2. Situation within the industry

- 2.1. What is your view of the performance trajectory of the Pakistani textile industry before the end of the past century?
- 2.2. What do you make of the current position of the Pakistani textile industry within the rapidly changing regional and global economic context?
- 2.3. Where do you rank the Pakistani textile industry in terms of regional and global competitiveness?
- 2.4. Do you think that the industry has plunged into a recession?

3. Challenges of the industry

- 3.1. As an industry practitioner, what challenging factors impact your overarching organisational performance and competitive advantages?
- 3.2. Do you believe that the country's power shortage influences the prospects of your organisational growth competitiveness?
- 3.3. How do you view the recent regional and international developments in the industry and where does the industry in Pakistan stand in this connection, particularly in terms of threats and opportunities?
- 3.4. Add a couple of more questions here on risks, challenges etc.

4. Opportunities and growth strategies

- 4.1. From your perspective, what would uplift your productivity and bolster your organisation's international rivalry?
- 4.2. Out of your professional expertise, what do you make of the industry's attractiveness to the recruitment and retention of skilled professionals?
- 4.3. How do you view the textile industry in Pakistan over the coming ten years?
- 4.4. Add a few more questions here on opportunities in terms of internal market, export etc.

5. Is there any question that I didn't ask and you would like to answer? Or, do you have any comments, views or explanations that you would like to add?